

Integrated Cultural Resources Management Plan for the Marine Corps Logistics Base, Barstow, California

FY2020-2025 Update

Prepared for:

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Naval Facilities Engineering Command Southwest
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and

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APPROVAL

Marine Corps Logistics Base, Barstow, California Integrated Cultural Resources Management Plan

Updated 2020-2025

I approve the implementation of all activities in this Integrated Cultural Resources Management Plan for the Marine Corps Logistics Base Barstow as sustaining and enhancing the military mission and conserving cultural resources for the future generations. This Plan has been prepared pursuant to Department of Defense Instruction 4715.16, department of Defense Measure of Merit, Secretary of the Navy Instruction 4000.35A, and Marine Corps Order 5090.2 (Volume 8). The Plan has set appropriate and adequate guidelines for managing cultural resources and conserving and protecting cultural resources of this Marine Corps Installation.

APPROVING OFFICIAL

DATE

C.C. Clemans

Colonel, United States Marine Corps
Commanding Officer
MCLB Barstow

ANNUAL REVIEW

The Marine Corps Logistics Base Barstow Integrated Cultural Resources Management Plan must be updated each year to include changes, amendments, and updates pertaining to the cultural resources on this installation. The review should note changes in stakeholder points of contact, initiatives completed over the past year, and an outline of proposed projects. This Integrated Cultural Resources Management Plan has been reviewed and updated as needed by:

FY2021

Name: _____ **Title:** _____ **Date:** _____
INFORMATION UPDATED **Yes** **No**
Notes: _____

FY2022

Name: _____ **Title:** _____ **Date:** _____
INFORMATION UPDATED **Yes** **No**
Notes: _____

FY2023

Name: _____ **Title:** _____ **Date:** _____
INFORMATION UPDATED **Yes** **No**
Notes: _____

FY2024

Name: _____ **Title:** _____ **Date:** _____
INFORMATION UPDATED **Yes** **No**
Notes: _____

FY2025

Name: _____ **Title:** _____ **Date:** _____
INFORMATION UPDATED **Yes** **No**
Notes: _____

ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

ACHP	Advisory Council on Historic Preservation	MAGTF	Marine Air Ground Task Force Training Command
APE	Area of Potential Effects	MCAGCC	Marine Corps Air Ground Combat Center
ARPA	Archaeological Resources Protection Act	MCIWEST	Marine Corps Installations West
CATEX	categorical exclusion	MCLB	Marine Corps Logistics Base
CFR	Code of Federal Regulations	MCO	Marine Corps Order
CHL	California Historical Landmark	MDMC	Marine Depot Maintenance Command
CHRIS	California Historical Resource Information System	MILCON	Military Construction
CIP	Common Installation Picture	MOA	memorandum of agreement
CMC	Commandant of the Marine Corps	MOU	memorandum of understanding
CO	Commanding Officer	NAGPRA	Native American Graves Protection and Repatriation Act
CRM	Cultural Resources Manager	NAVFAC SW	Naval Facilities Engineering Command Southwest
CPHI	California Point of Historical Interest	NCIS	Naval Criminal Investigation Service
DDBC	Defense Distribution Depot, Barstow, California	NEPA	National Environmental Policy Act
DLA	Defense Logistics Agency	NHPA	National Historic Preservation Act
DoD	Department of Defense	NRHP	National Register of Historic Places
DoN	Department of the Navy	PAO	Public Affairs Office
EIS	Environmental Impact System	POC	point of contact
EO	Executive Order	PWS	Performance Work Statement
FSD	Fleet Support Division	SCCIC	South Central Coastal Information Center
FY	fiscal year	SECNAVINST	Secretary of the Navy Instruction
GIS	graphic information system	SHPO	State Historic Preservation Officer
HQMC	Marine Corps Headquarters	SOP	standard operating procedure
ICRMP	Integrated Cultural Resources Management Plan	TCP	traditional cultural property
INRMP	Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan	THPO	Tribal Historic Preservation Officers
JRP	JRP Historical Consulting	U.S.	United States
KD	Known Distance	USMC	U.S. Marine Corps
MAGTF	Marine Air-Ground Task Force	WMC	William Manley Consulting

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

2 This Integrated Cultural Resources Management Plan (ICRMP) is a five-year plan that
3 establishes a framework for cultural resources management on Marine Corps Logistics Base
4 (MCLB) Barstow. The management of cultural resources must be in compliance with a variety
5 of cultural resources statutes, executive orders (EOs), and presidential memoranda, as well as
6 several other regulations and requirements. ICRMPs are required by Department of Defense
7 (DoD) Instruction 4715.16, Cultural Resources Program; Marine Corps Order (MCO) 5090.2,
8 Volume 8, Cultural Resources Management; and Secretary of the Navy Instruction
9 (SECNAVINST) 4000.35A, Department of the Navy Cultural Resources Program. DoD
10 Instruction 4517.16 states that “All installations with cultural resources will complete and update
11 ICRMPs as per this policy. In addition, all ICRMPs will be current and implemented, in
12 consultation and partnership with State Historic Preservation Officers (SHPOs), Tribal Historic
13 Preservation Officers (THPOs), and other appropriate consulting parties.”

14 The completed ICRMP becomes part of the Master Plan for MCLB Barstow and functions as a
15 way to inform the Commanding Officer of the proper procedures to manage cultural resources in
16 light of the activities that will be carried out at the facility over the next fiscal year. The ICRMP
17 should be reviewed annually and updated every five years based on the status of knowledge at
18 that time and the projected future plans that may affect cultural resources. ,

19 *Land Use*

20 MCLB Barstow is located in western San Bernardino County, California, 3.5 miles (6
21 kilometers) east of the city of Barstow (Figure ES-1). MCLB Barstow encompasses 5,567 acres
22 (2,253 hectares) and is situated within the DoD Southwest Range Complex and Marine Corps
23 Installations West (MCIWEST)-Marine Corps Base Camp Pendleton Area of Operations.

24 The key function and activity at MCLB Barstow is to receive, store, distribute, maintain, and
25 repair military supplies and equipment as well as provide a training venue that supports combat
26 training for United States (U.S.) Marine Corps (USMC) operating forces including tenant, unit,
27 and Marine Air-Ground Task Force (MAGTF)-level training, for the First Marine Expeditionary
28 Force.

29 As one of only two logistics Bases operated by the USMC, MCLB Barstow serves an important
30 role as a primary west coast Marine Corps Logistics and Maintenance Center. Its mission is
31 twofold: to procure, maintain, store, and distribute supplies and equipment as needed and to
32 repair and rebuild USMC and other DoD equipment. MCLB Barstow furnishes supplies for
33 USMC facilities worldwide and is a direct support provider for all installations. Secondly,
34 MCLB Barstow is responsible for the technical training of Marines, including developing and
35 maintaining their skills and job efficiency. Training at MCLB Barstow generally consists of
36 annual marksmanship and tactical combat training. Existing training activities occur on a
37 periodic basis based on training demands.

1 MCLB Barstow is separated into three primary use areas: one range area (a live-fire Known
2 Distance [KD] Range Complex) and two cantonment areas (i.e., developed areas that support
3 military training and operations) (Nebo Annex and Yermo Annex) (Figure ES-2). The Nebo
4 Annex is used for storage, maintenance, and infrastructure support purposes such as
5 administration, housing, and community facilities. Approximately 25 percent of Nebo is
6 undeveloped open space. Of the Burlington Northern Santa Fe Corp line connecting Needles and
7 Barstow, 1.8 miles run east to west just north of Nebo's main warehouse facilities, south of the
8 Mojave River.

9 The Yermo Annex supports two primary functions: storage and repair. Most of the acreage on
10 the Yermo Annex is used for warehouses and open storage facilities. The area also supports a
11 major maintenance depot and an administration facility. Adjacent to the maintenance depot is a
12 state-of-the-art military vehicle test track used in conjunction with the repair facilities.
13 Approximately 2.2 miles of the Union Pacific Railroad run along the southeast boundary of the
14 Yermo Annex, crossing the Mojave River (see Figure 2-5). The Yermo Annex also has extensive
15 rail facilities, consisting of approximately 24.5 track miles, to transport supplies.

16 The Rifle Range is dedicated to range activities, with rifle and pistol ranges to train Marines in
17 marksmanship. Most of the Rifle Range is open space, which serves as a range safety buffer
18 zone. However, Rifle Range West includes a Landing Helicopter Assault/Landing Helicopter
19 Dock and Rifle Range East includes a Landing Zone. Two utility corridors run east to west along
20 the north boundary of the Rifle Range.

21 *Cultural Resources*

22 MCLB contains a diverse array of cultural resources, both prehistoric and historic, which include
23 archaeological sites, historic buildings and structures, cultural landscapes, and sites considered
24 sacred or traditional cultural properties (TCPs) by Native American groups in the area.
25 Archaeological surveys have identified prehistoric and historic sites and isolates, including
26 petroglyph images at the Rattlesnake Rock site, and two identified rock circles. Though no
27 longer managed by MCLB Barstow, segments of the Atlantic and Pacific Railroad constructed in
28 1883 run through the installation. Segments of two historic trails have been identified at MCLB
29 Barstow. The earliest trail dates from the late 1700s and was referred to as the Mojave Trail, the
30 Old Spanish Trail, and the Mormon Trail. Also running through the installation are segments of
31 the National Old Trails Road, which became part of U.S. Route 66 when it was paved in 1920.

32 *Prehistoric and Historic Archaeological Resources*

33 In total, 197 archaeological resources have been identified at MCLB Barstow, consisting of 81
34 sites and 146 isolated resources. Of the 81 sites, 52 are prehistoric, 26 are historic, and three are
35 multi-component (contains both prehistoric and historic components). One archaeological site
36 has been determined eligible for inclusion in the National Register of Historic Places (NRHP)
37 (CA- SBR-2910H); three have been recommended eligible for inclusion in the NRHP (CA-SBR-
38 73, CA-SBR-8319, and CA-SBR-29325); one (CA-SBR-73) has been designated a California
39 Point of Historical Interest (CPHI); and another (CA-SBR-3033/H) has been designated a
40 California Historical Landmark (CHL). Site CA-SBR-11840 was initially recommended eligible

Figure ES-2 MCLB Barstow and the Three Primary Use Areas

1 for listing in the NRHP; however, after further evaluation, the USMC determined it was not
2 eligible for listing in the NRHP. The SHPO did concur with this determination (Polanco 2018).
3 Twenty-six of the archaeological sites have not been evaluated for NRHP eligibility and the
4 remaining 50 sites have been recommended not eligible for NRHP eligibility. The 146 isolated
5 resources comprise 34 prehistoric and 112 historic isolates. Isolated resources by definition are
6 considered not eligible for listing in the NRHP.

7 All artifacts recovered from archaeological sites at MCLB Barstow are curated with Marine Air
8 Ground Task Force Training Command (MAGTFTC), Marine Corps Air Ground Combat Center
9 (MCAGCC), Twentynine Palms, California. All collections are in compliance with federal
10 curation standards per 36 Code of Federal Regulations (CFR) 79, Curation of Federally Owned
11 and Administered Archaeological Collections.

12 *Historic Buildings and Structures*

13 Previous studies have evaluated 714 buildings and structures located at MCLB Barstow. In 1996,
14 William Manley Consulting (WMC) evaluated 115 buildings as part of a larger study; most of
15 the buildings were World War II properties. WMC inventoried and evaluated 627 buildings and
16 structures in 1999 (Manley 1999), including 28 that had previously been inventoried in 1996; the
17 resources addressed in this later study were primarily Cold War Era properties. Following the
18 1999 study, many buildings and structures at MCLB Barstow were destroyed. The most recent
19 study, by JRP Historical Consulting (JRP) in 2011, identified 326 remaining structures at MCLB
20 Barstow. Of these, 80 were modern structures built after 1989; JRP recorded and evaluated the
21 remaining 246 properties. No buildings or structures evaluated in any of the three studies were
22 found to be eligible for inclusion in the NRHP, either as a district or individually.

23 In 2013, SHPO concurred with JRP's NRHP eligibility determinations for 627 buildings and
24 structures at MCLB Barstow, which concluded that all buildings, including those that turned 50
25 years of age since previous evaluation efforts, are not eligible for NRHP inclusion either
26 individually or as contributors to a historic district.

27 *Traditional Cultural Properties*

28 A TCP is defined as a resource that is eligible for inclusion in the NRHP because of its
29 association with cultural practices or beliefs of a living community that are rooted in that
30 community's history, and are important in maintaining the continuing cultural identity of the
31 community. There are currently no identified TCPs at MCLB Barstow. However, Site CA-SBR-
32 73, also known as Rattlesnake Rock, may fit the definition of a TCP.

33 *Paleontological Resources*

34 There are no identified paleontological resources at MCLB Barstow.

35 *Cultural Resources Management*

36 The ICRMP for MCLB Barstow will reside in the Environmental Division of the S-F Facilities
37 Installation and Logistics Department and will be managed by the Cultural Resources Manager
38 (CRM). The CRM is responsible for ensuring that activities taking place on the base that may
39 affect cultural resources are in compliance with all applicable federal requirements and
40 regulations.

1) General Goals:

- To preserve the opportunity for a high quality of life for present and future generations of Americans.
- To preserve the Marine Corps mission access to air, land, and sea resources.
- To strengthen national security by strengthening conservation of aspects of national security.

2) Specific Goals:

- Protect cultural resources heritage under MCLB Barstow’s control as an essential part of the defense mission.
- Maintain standard operating procedures (SOPs).
- Maintain curation standards for archaeological collections (36 CFR § 79).
- Maintain the data system for archaeological site information and collection.
- Educate all personnel on the base about existing base cultural resources and procedures for handling the unanticipated discovery of cultural resources.
- Make periodic visits to all eligible sites to observe their condition.
- Provide continued maintenance of the geographic information systems (GIS) database repository.
- Continue communications with Native American tribes regarding the status of archaeological resources.
- Continue to inventory and catalog cultural resources documents, photographs, site and building plans, old real property records, maps, original drawings, and personal papers.
- Digitize any cultural resource documents not already in a digital format.
- Submit all outstanding archaeological evaluations for SHPO concurrence.
- Evaluate un-evaluated archaeological properties for NRHP eligibility.

The following key management actions are recommended as a result of this ICRMP (additional recommendations are found in Section 2.3):

- Integrate the ICRMP with the newly revised Master Plan and Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan (INRMP).
- Continue to inventory and evaluate built environment resources (buildings, structures, or objects) as they reach 50 years of age.
- Develop, acquire, and maintain all Common Installation Picture data layers with associated metadata (MCO 11000.25A [2013]).
- Submit the revised NRHP nomination for Rattlesnake Rock (CA-SBR-73) to SHPO for concurrence (MCO 5090.2, Volume 8).

1 *Conclusion*

2 These proposed goals build upon previous efforts, and the development, updating, and
3 implementation of an ICRMP must be viewed as an ongoing process. This plan presents what is
4 known of the installation’s land and its history at the time of writing. As new evidence is
5 discovered, or as the military’s use of the installation changes, this document should serve as a
6 basis for management decisions in the present, and for a foundation that will evolve to
7 accommodate changing priorities and goals in the future.

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Appendix C – Discovery Treatment Plan

Appendix D – Agreement Documents

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1.0 INTRODUCTION

1.1 MISSION AND GOALS FOR THE CULTURAL RESOURCE PROGRAM

This updated Marine Corps Logistics Base (MCLB) Barstow, the installation Integrated Cultural Resources Management Plan (ICRMP) describes known cultural resources at MCLB Barstow; identifies and describes the various laws and regulations requiring compliance during the course of planning and executing facility maintenance, new construction, training, and operations; and gives process and protocol guidance for activities that may affect cultural resources.

This update is designed to complement and provide information for other MCLB Barstow plans such as the Master Plan, Base Exterior Architecture Plan, the Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan (INRMP), and other installation orders and directives. The ICRMP serves as the Commanding Officer's (CO's) decision document for the conduct of cultural resources management actions and is also used by the Cultural Resources Manager (CRM) in the day-to-day management of cultural resources. This updated ICRMP is intended to be a technical document used by persons planning and/or preparing approvals, management actions, orders, instructions, guidelines, standard operating procedures (SOPs), and other plans. This ICRMP is not intended to be used by persons operating in the field. Field personnel are expected to be operating under MCLB Barstow guidelines, plans, orders, or other approvals that have been developed using the ICRMP and have already had environmental compliance review and, where applicable, regulatory approvals and/or permitting.

The primary goal of the ICRMP is to provide the cultural resources program at MCLB Barstow with a suite of applicable information that facilitates the planning and decision-making necessary to achieve compliance. The material in this ICRMP is organized to provide the program with the guidance necessary to carry out day-to-day activities that may affect cultural resources. The ICRMP will help the cultural resources program develop a coordination process with regulatory agencies as well as internal and external stakeholders, researchers, and the general public. This coordination ultimately promotes positive partnerships in the proper management and preservation of cultural resources. For these reasons, it is important that the ICRMP be organized in a functional format that is accessible to a variety of users. However, given confidentiality requirements (Marine Corps Orders [MCO] 5090.2, Volume 8), coordination should be through the CRM.

1.2 ORGANIZATION OF THE ICRMP UPDATE

Section 1, Introduction, describes the mission and goals of the Cultural Resource Program and the organization of the ICRMP update (including all information and data gathering). Section 1 also sets the location of the MCLB Barstow and discusses the installation's internal and external integration, as well as cultural resources laws and regulations, including a discussion of all federal laws, regulations, executive orders (EOs), MCOs, and Department of Defense (DoD) guidance applicable to cultural resources management compliance at MCLB Barstow.

1 Section 2, Cultural Resource Management Strategy, is devoted to a discussion of the
2 management goals, the cultural resource responsibilities, and the program’s future management
3 requirements and recommendations.

4 Section 3, Standard Operating Procedures, is designed to function as a stand-alone document that
5 can be distributed to military personnel, tenants, contractors, and various installation programs as
6 appropriate to provide instruction for cultural resources management procedures. Per ICRMP
7 Guidance, each SOP has been prepared to be a standalone document that can be distributed
8 separately or in a set.

9 Section 4, References, comprises a list of all references cited throughout the document.

10 There are five appendices attached to the ICRMP. Appendix A provides the environmental and
11 historic context of MCLB Barstow. Appendix B describes the previously conducted surveys and
12 previously recorded sites. Appendix C includes the Discovery Treatment Plan. Appendix D
13 provides copies of any agreement documents that have been negotiated by MCLB Barstow and
14 Appendix E includes the Section 106 coordination letters.

15 **1.3 INFORMATION GATHERING, INPUT, AND REVIEW FOR THE** 16 **PREPARATION OF THE ICRMP UPDATE**

17 During the preparation of this ICRMP update, information was gathered from the 2016 ICRMP,
18 and the results from recent survey reports (post 2016). It is important that the updated ICRMP
19 contain the most current points of contact (POC) information for all internal and external
20 stakeholders and reflect the most current policies and procedures relevant to cultural resources
21 management and compliance. Because the United States (U.S.) Marine Corps (USMC) is
22 responsible for the identification, evaluation, and protection of cultural resources within its
23 installations, consultation with internal and external stakeholders is vital to assessing the needs of
24 those resources.

25 **Development of the ICRMP and ICRMP Updates**

26 The CRM shall review the MCLB Barstow ICRMP annually to ensure it is current with training
27 mission requirements and the ICRMP will be updated every five years. Annual addendum
28 reports to the ICRMP may include:

- 29 • Additional documentation of cultural resources at MCLB Barstow.
- 30 • Identification of threats or other potential impacts to historic properties resulting from
31 mission-related or other activities not covered in the ICRMP.
- 32 • Additions or changes to procedures outlined in the ICRMP for compliance with cultural
33 resources regulations and for the protection and treatment of historic properties.

34 **1.4 LAWS AND REGULATIONS**

35 Federal laws, regulations, and EOs establish a legal backdrop for the management of cultural
36 resources under federal oversight. Chief among these are the National Environmental Policy Act
37 (NEPA), the National Historic Preservation Act (NHPA), the Archaeological Resources
38 Protection Act (ARPA), the Native American Graves Protection and Repatriation Act
39 (NAGPRA), and EOs 13175 and 13287. Additional direction is provided by the DoD and

1 Department of the Navy (DoN) instructions and MCOs, which establish specific policies for
2 management of cultural resources at MCLB Barstow. This section is organized to present
3 information in that order.

4 **1.4.1 Federal Statutes and Regulations**

- 5
- 6 • NEPA of 1969
- 7 • NHPA of 1966
- 8 • American Antiquities Act of 1906
- 9 • Historic Sites Act of 1935
- 10 • Archaeological and Historic Preservation Act of 1974, as amended
- 11 • American Indian Religious Freedom Act of 1978, as amended
- 12 • ARPA of 1979, as amended, P.L. 96-95, 16
- 13 • U.S. Code 470aa et seq.
- 14 • NAGPRA of 1990
- 15 • 32 Code of Federal Regulations (CFR) § 229, Protection of Archaeological Resources
- 16 • 36 CFR § 60, NRHP
- 17 • 36 CFR § 63, Determinations of Eligibility for Inclusion in the NRHP
- 18 • 36 CFR § 65, National Historic Landmarks Program
- 19 • 36 CFR § 68, The Secretary of the Interior’s Standards for the Treatment of Historic
20 Properties
- 21 • 36 CFR § 78, Waiver of Federal Agency Responsibility under Section 110 of the NHPA
- 22 • 36 CFR § 79, Curation of Federally Owned and Administered Archaeological Collections
- 23 • 36 CFR § 800, Protection of Historic and Cultural Properties, Advisory Council on
24 Historic Preservation (Section 106 Regulations as amended 5 Aug. 2004)
- 25 • 40 CFR § 1500–1508, Council on Environmental Quality, Regulations Implementing the
26 Procedural Provisions of NEPA
- 27 • 43 CFR § 3, Preservation of American Antiquities
- 28 • 43 CFR § 7, Protection of Archaeological Resources
- 29 • 43 CFR § 10, Native American Graves Protection and Repatriation Regulations

30 **1.4.2 Executive Orders**

- 31 • EO 11593, Protection and Enhancement of the Cultural Environment
- 32 • EO 13007, Indian Sacred Sites
- 33 • EO 13175, Consultation and Coordination with Indian Tribal Governments
- 34 • EO 13287, Preserve America
- 35 • EO Memorandum, April 29, 1994, Government-to-Government Relations with Native
36 American Tribal Governments
- 37 • EO Memorandum, November 5, 2009, Tribal Consultation

1.4.3 DoD Guidance Documents and MCOs

- MCO 5090.2, Environmental Compliance and Protection Program, Volume 8, Cultural Resources Management
- MCO 5750.1H, Manual for the Marine Corps Historical Program
- MCO 11000.25A, Installation Geospatial Information and Services
- DoD Instruction 4715.03, Natural Resources Conservation Program, March 18, 2011
- DoD Instruction 4715.16, Cultural Resources Management – 2008
- DoD Directive 4710.1, Archaeological and Historic Resources Management, June 21, 1984
- DoD Instruction 4710.02, DoD Interactions with Federally Recognized Tribes, September 14, 2006
- Secretary of the Navy Instruction (SECNAVINST) 4000.35A, DoN Cultural Resources Program
- SECNAVINST 11010.14A, DoN Policy for Consultation with Federally Recognized Indian Tribes

1.5 MISSION STATEMENTS

1.5.1 Marine Corps Installations West

The mission of Marine Corps Installations West (MCIWEST) is to implement policies; develop regional strategies and plans; prioritize resources; and provide services, direction, and oversight through assigned USMC installations to support the Operating Forces, tenant commands, and activities. The vision of MCIWEST is to provide Operating Forces and tenant commands with the highest quality of continuous, effective service and support to satisfy present and anticipate future joint expeditionary warfare requirements.

1.5.2 Marine Corps Logistics Base Barstow, California

The Mission of MCLB Barstow is to serve as a primary platform for training and installation support providing real estate, infrastructure and services to operating forces. MCLB Barstow provides direct transportation, supply and storage to tenant organizations, Fleet Marine Forces, DoD, and other federal entities and executes actions related to future basing initiatives in order to enable operating force combat readiness.

1.5.3 Marine Corps Logistics Command

The Commandant of the Marine Corps (CMC) directed that on May 1, 2003, a merger of the MCLB Maintenance Center (now Marine Depot Maintenance Command [MDMC]) and the headquarters element of the Marine Corps Material Command be undertaken to create a Marine Corps Logistics Command. The CMC further stipulated that Marine Corps Logistics Command would consist of a headquarters element located at Albany, Georgia, and the following four

1 subordinate commands: MCLB Albany; Maintenance Center, Albany; Maintenance Center,
2 Barstow; and Blount Island Command, Jacksonville, Florida.

3 The Marine Corps Logistics Command mission, as outlined in MCO 4000.58, is to “provide
4 worldwide integrated logistics, including: operational logistics support, supply chain,
5 distribution, depot-level maintenance management; and strategic prepositioning capability in
6 support of the operating forces and other supported units to maximize their readiness and
7 sustainability. To support enterprise level and program level Total Life Cycle Management.”

8 **1.6 ROLES AND RESPONSIBILITIES**

9 Although not all departments at MCLB Barstow are directly or indirectly involved with cultural
10 resources, all personnel on base must be educated on existing cultural resources within the
11 installation and understand the procedures for handling unanticipated discoveries of cultural
12 resources. Although internal staff is primarily responsible for implementing the cultural
13 resources program, various external stakeholders also have responsibilities to and/or vested
14 interests in the program. These roles and responsibilities are outlined below. The organization of
15 MCLB Barstow command staff is shown in Figure 1-1, and the structure of MCIWEST,
16 including and tenant activities, is reflected in the organizational chart provided in Figure 1-2.

17 **1.6.1 Military Personnel Responsibilities**

18 Responsibility for managing the cultural resources program at MCLB Barstow falls under the
19 CRM within the Environmental Division of the Installation and Logistics Department. The
20 ICRMP will be used primarily by the CRM, the CO and his staff, and other divisions of the
21 Installation and Logistics Department. These and other departments at MCLB Barstow are
22 briefly described below.

23 **1.6.1.1 Commanding Officer**

24 The CO of MCLB Barstow reports to the MCIWEST for administrative and facilities support
25 (Figure 1-2). The CO and Executive Officer administer the facility, whereas other departments
26 are involved in providing support to all users, including tenants and transients.

27 The CO is responsible for ensuring that activities and operations at MCLB Barstow fully comply
28 with federal, state, and local laws/regulations, and with written DoD, DoN, and USMC policy.
29 The CO is charged with 15 tasks under MCO 5090.2, Volume 8, to oversee the cultural resources
30 program and ensure the ability to carry out the military mission. The Environmental Division of
31 the Installation and Logistics Department advises the CO and land managers on cultural
32 resources concerns.

MCLB Barstow Base Organizations

Title of Parent Organization: Marine Corps Installations West- Marine Corps Base, Camp Pendleton, CA		Activity title: Marine Corps Logistics Base Barstow, California
Date: 13 December 2017	Approved by: S. S. KAREGA Commanding Officer	

Figure 1-1 MCLB Barstow Base Organizational Chart

Figure 1-2 Marine Corps Installations West Organizational Chart

1 1.6.1.2 CRM

2 This ICRMP places major responsibility on the CRM. Other departments whose activities may
3 affect cultural resources on the base should contact the CRM to identify potential cultural
4 resources issues prior to any undertakings. The responsibilities of the CRM are as follows:

- 5 • Develop, manage, and implement the ICRMP.
- 6 • Through the site approval process (Real Property Facilities Manual Vol. II, MCO
7 P11000.12, Ch. 3, 3003.1 and 2) coordinate cultural resources management activity with
8 other MCLB Barstow departments; offices; tenant groups/organizations; and outside
9 vendors, contractors, and occasional users of the base.
- 10 • Monitor resource condition and management compliance.
- 11 • Coordinate cultural resources data and contract cultural resources projects
12 (archaeological survey, testing, evaluation, and mitigation) at Naval Facilities
13 Engineering Command Southwest (NAVFAC SW).
- 14 • Implement the Section 106 process at MCLB Barstow–funded projects and military
15 construction (MILCON) projects.
- 16 • Request funding for Section 110 cultural resource studies.
- 17 • Coordinate cultural resources management and foster working relationships in the
18 cultural resources community, including:
 - 19 • cultural resource divisions of various military organizations involved with MCLB
20 Barstow;
 - 21 • Native American tribes and cultural groups; and
 - 22 • consulting agencies that provide cultural resource expertise.
 - 23 • Coordinate cultural resources data with Marine Corps Headquarters (HQMC) for annual
24 reporting purposes.

25 1.6.1.3 Installation and Logistics Department (S-F Facilities)

26 The Installation and Logistics Department provides facilities maintenance, housing, utilities,
27 engineering, and planning services for all sections of the base. The Installation and Logistics
28 Department contains the following three distinct divisions.

29 **1.6.1.3.1 Environmental Division**

30 The Environmental Division’s mission is to “conserve MCLB Barstow resources, protect the
31 environment, and enhance the USMC’s reputation while preventing environmental non-
32 compliance that may restrict mission accomplishment.” The CRM falls within this division.

33 **1.6.1.3.2 Housing Division**

34 The Housing Division oversees operation of the Family Housing Branch and Bachelor Housing
35 Branch.

36 **1.6.1.3.3 Public Works Division**

37 The Public Works Division provides professional services that include planning, project
38 management, and engineering for any work conducted outside the Performance Work Statement

1 (PWS) such as MILCONs and other Special Projects. It administers the PWS and provides
2 quality control and assurance.

3 1.6.1.4 Special Staff Department

4 **1.6.1.4.1 Staff Judge Advocate Office**

5 The Office of the Staff Judge Advocate provides legal services and support to command as well
6 as legal assistance for eligible military members, family members, and retirees.

7 **1.6.1.4.2 Public Affairs Office (PAO)**

8 The PAO supports MCLB Barstow and its tenant organizations. This includes any media
9 inquiries, and involves informing personnel, local media, and community members of any
10 relevant matters regarding MCLB Barstow and the USMC through various means of
11 communication. This includes the base's weekly magazine, The Prospector, for which the PAO
12 provides free classified ad services, as well as photography, video, and graphics support. The
13 PAO also coordinates community outreach programs that involve meetings between base
14 personnel and key local organizations.

15 **1.6.1.4.3 Base Safety Office**

16 The Base Safety Office is responsible for providing a safe work/living environment for all
17 personnel at MCLB Barstow and works to reduce operational costs by minimizing day-to-day
18 mishaps and lost time due to training injuries, and by identifying and eliminating any unsafe or
19 hazardous conditions.

20 **1.6.1.4.4 Inspector General Office**

21 The Inspector General Office provides a single POC for various inquiries, comments,
22 complaints, and investigations for the base commander's inspection program; administers the
23 program; and maintains oversight of various command programs. Any issues related to MCLB
24 Barstow policy or functions should be addressed to the Base Inspector.

25 **1.6.1.4.5 Human Resources Office**

26 The Human Resources Office provides services and support for employee training development,
27 employee relations, labor relations, recruitment, staffing, placement, classification,
28 compensation, and equal opportunity employment opportunities.

29 **1.6.1.4.6 Office of the General Counsel**

30 The Office of the General Counsel represents the interests of the DoN and USMC by providing
31 legal counsel and training to commanders, directors, and supervisors of MCLB Barstow and its
32 tenants. This includes civil law, employment law, environmental law, information law, real
33 estate law, fiscal law, business law, and contracts.

34 **1.6.1.4.7 Supply/Logistics Division**

35 The Supply/Logistics Division provides the supplies and services necessary to carry out various
36 activities for departments, tenants, the MDMC, the National Training Center, Fort Irwin, and

1 other DoD activities that utilize portions of MCLB Barstow. This division is also responsible for
2 receiving all Garrison property and equipment.

3 1.6.1.5 Headquarters Battalion

4 The Headquarters Battalion provides administrative, training, and logistical guidance in support
5 of Marines and sailors assigned to the base. Headquarters Battalion also manages all training
6 areas on the base. The battalion commander is also the CO of all troops on base.

7 1.6.1.6 Manpower Department (S-1)

8 The Manpower Department provides administrative, advisory, and support services to base and
9 tenant organizations, and administers the base Historical Program, Government Travel Charge
10 Card Program, and Transportation Incentive Programs. It consists of the following four separate
11 divisions:

- 12 • *Manpower Division.* The Manpower Division validates and manages manpower
13 requirements for base operations' organizations and maintains the Table of Organization
14 for MCLB Barstow.
- 15 • *Adjutant Division.* The Adjutant Division performs those general and personnel
16 administrative and office management functions inherent in the responsibilities assigned
17 by the CO and/or Executive Officer.
- 18 • *Postal Branch.* The Postal Branch administers postal affairs and travel support.
- 19 • *Military Personnel Division.* The Military Personnel Division provides the command and
20 tenant activities at MCLB Barstow.

21 1.6.1.7 Operations Department (S-3)

22 The Operations Department includes the Mission Assurance Division, Strategic Plans, Current
23 Operations Division, Rail Operations Branch, and Business Performance Office. The Operations
24 Department functions to enhance MCLB Barstow's mission capability by protecting the U.S.'
25 homeland and bases of operations. The department carries out these duties by practicing risk
26 management, education, and emergency response, including base mobilization and natural
27 disaster contingency planning.

28 **1.6.1.7.1 Process and Innovation**

29 This office provides business management for cost performance/efficiency improvement
30 programs, strategic sourcing, planning, business process reengineering, and civilian
31 career/leadership development to MCLB Barstow's base commander, staff, and tenants.

32 1.6.1.8 Communications Department (S-6)

33 The Communications Department provides secure, reliable, and timely communications services
34 for MCLB Barstow and its tenant activities. The department strives to implement professional
35 excellence within its staff to empower individuals to achieve seamless communications for its
36 customers.

1 1.6.1.9 Security and Emergency Services Department (S-7)

2 The Security and Emergency Services Department consists of the Marine Corps Police
3 Department and Fire and Emergency Services Division. The Marine Corps Police Department
4 provides basic security for the base, including the gates and patrols. Often this division is the first
5 to respond to unexpected discoveries of cultural resources as staff patrol the base. The
6 department is also responsible for the protection of the petroglyph site on the Yermo Annex, CA-
7 SBR-73 and, in conjunction with the CRM, controls access to the site. The Fire and Emergency
8 Services Department responds to fires, accidents, and any other emergencies on the base.

9 1.6.1.10 Comptroller Department (S-8)

10 The Comptroller Department consists of the Budget Office and Resource Evaluation and
11 Analysis Office. The department interfaces with the Environmental Division in the financial
12 management of cultural resource projects. When a project is identified, the CRM inputs the
13 project into a computer based program, Status Tool for Environmental Programming (STEP). A
14 description of the project and the projected cost are entered into the system. Then the CRM
15 coordinates with NAVFAC SW to develop Statement of Work and projected cost for the project.
16 The CRM revises the estimate in STEP if necessary. If the project is approved, the funds come to
17 the Comptroller. The Comptroller Department consists of two divisions that specialize in
18 different aspects of financial management.

19 ***1.6.1.10.1 Budget Division***

20 The Budget Division formulates budgets and creates execution policies and procedures to
21 manage the base's direct and reimbursable financial resources.

22 ***1.6.1.10.2 The Resource Evaluation and Analysis Division***

23 The Resource Evaluation and Analysis Division analyzes, evaluates, and reviews the adequacy
24 of financial records, budget practices and procedures, and management to promote efficient and
25 effective use of resources. It is the POC for external audit organizations and for all internal
26 management control programs. This division also maintains Interservice Support Agreements for
27 reimbursable customers.

28 1.6.1.11 Marine Corps Community Services Department

29 The Marine Corps Community Services Department consists of various divisions that include the
30 Semper Fit Division (which runs the base gym and exercise programs), the Marine and Family
31 Services Division, the Business Operations Division, the General Support Division, and the
32 Marine Corps Family Team Building. All these divisions are designed to enhance personnel
33 "quality of life" by offering a variety of base support services for the military community and its
34 families.

35 **1.6.2 Nonmilitary Participants**

36 The USMC has the responsibility to consult with external stakeholders on a regular basis (MCO
37 5090.2, Volume 8). This section describes coordination with the State Historic Preservation

1 Office (SHPO), the Advisory Council on Historic Preservation (ACHP), Native American tribes,
2 tenants/organizations, and other stakeholders and parties.

3 1.6.2.1 California State Historic Preservation Officer Consultation

4 The SHPO coordinates state participation in the implementation of the NHPA and is a key
5 participant in the Section 106 process (refer to Section 4.4.1 for a detailed description of the
6 Section 106 process). The SHPO's role is to consult with and assist MCLB Barstow when
7 identifying historic properties, assessing effects upon them, and considering alternatives to avoid
8 or reduce those effects. The SHPO reflects the interests of California and its citizens in the
9 preservation of their cultural heritage and helps MCLB Barstow identify those persons interested
10 in an undertaking and its effects upon historic properties. If the SHPO does not respond within
11 30 days of receiving a written request for a review of a finding or determination, MCLB Barstow
12 may either proceed to the next step of the process based on the finding or determination, or
13 consult with the ACHP in lieu of the SHPO (36 CFR § 800.3[4]). All undertakings at the
14 installation that fall under Section 106 must be coordinated with the SHPO or have a
15 Programmatic Agreement or memorandum of agreement (MOA) in place that allows for agreed
16 upon procedures in place of normal Section 106 compliance. An "undertaking" is defined as

17
18 a project, activity, or program funded in whole or in part under the direct or indirect
19 jurisdiction of a Federal agency, including those carried out by or on behalf of a Federal
20 agency; those carried out with Federal financial assistance; those requiring a Federal
21 permit, license or approval; and those subject to State or local regulation administered
22 pursuant to a delegation or approval by a Federal agency. (36 CFR § 800.16[y])
23

24 Consultation with the SHPO is required if the undertaking has the potential to affect a historic
25 property (36 CFR § 800.3[f]3); absent that circumstance, no consultation is required (36 CFR §
26 800.3[f]1). SHPO consultation is also required for eligibility determinations made as part of
27 Section 110 compliance and in the development of PAs. It is preferable for the SHPO to review
28 ICRMPs, although this is not a regulatory responsibility.

29 1.6.2.2 ACHP Consultation

30 The ACHP may participate in the Section 106 consultation process if invited or if comments are
31 requested from any consulting party. Upon such request, the ACHP has 15 days to respond as to
32 whether it will participate, and if it does so, it has 45 days to provide comment. Additionally,
33 copies of all agreements are to be provided to the ACHP.

34 1.6.2.3 Tribal Consultation

35 Each time an undertaking is proposed, Section 106 of the NHPA requires a consultation
36 communication with the Native American tribes claiming ancestral use of MCLB Barstow's
37 lands. Accordingly, the installation, the SHPO, and the ACHP should be sensitive to the special
38 concerns of Native American tribes and historic preservation issues, which often extend beyond
39 Native American lands to other historic properties (43 CFR § 10, U.S. Code 1996-1996a, EO
40 13007, EO 13084, EO 13175, SECNAVINST 11010.14, and SECNAVINST 11010.14A). When

1 an undertaking will affect traditional or historic Native American territories, MCLB Barstow
2 must invite the governing body of the tribes to be a consulting party and to concur in any formal
3 agreements. When an undertaking may affect properties of historic value to a non-federally
4 recognized Native American tribe on non-Native American lands, the consulting parties shall
5 afford such tribe the opportunity to participate as interested persons. Traditional cultural leaders
6 and other Native Americans are considered interested persons with respect to undertakings that
7 may affect historic properties of significance to such persons. A summary of tribal consultation
8 that has occurred between 2016 and 2020 is provided in Section 2.6.1, Status of Consultation.
9 Tribes included in the consultation process are listed below in Section 2.5.2, External
10 Coordination.

11 1.6.2.4 MCLB Barstow Tenant Organizations

12 A number of tenant groups have offices on the base, some of which are independent and others
13 that directly relate to the base. Furthermore, a number of other groups, both military and civilian,
14 use portions of the base. It is the responsibility of all tenant groups/organizations that use the
15 base to comply with the ICRMP. Major tenant groups/organizations at MCLB Barstow are
16 discussed below.

17 ***1.6.2.4.1 Defense Distribution Center Barstow California***

18 The Defense Distribution Center Barstow California (DDBC) is a co-located depot operating
19 under the command of Defense Logistics Agency (DLA) Distribution Center. DLA Distribution
20 is made up of distribution centers at the Nebo Area and Yermo Annex. The depot receives,
21 stores, and ships supplies to various customers throughout the U.S. and the world. The DDBC is
22 one of 26 depots operated by DLA Distribution. Overall management is provided by the DLA.
23 The major commodities stored by DDBC are electronic parts, radioactive material, clothing and
24 textiles, military equipment parts, engines and transmissions, shafts, reduction gears, wire cable,
25 furniture, boats and anchors, radar units, and propellers (MCLB Barstow 2016).

26 ***1.6.2.4.2 DLA Disposition Services***

27 DLA Disposition Services manages excess property resulting from DoD activities in central
28 California and Nevada. Programs and services provided by DLA Disposition Services include
29 reutilization, transfer, donation, and sales, as well as environmental recycling, demineralization,
30 and precious metals recovery (MCLB Barstow 2016).

31 ***1.6.2.4.3 Marine Depot Maintenance Command***

32 The mission of the MDMC is to provide depot-level maintenance and support to the armed
33 forces for their training, operational, mobilization, and emergency requirements. MDMC's vision
34 is to become the maintenance provider of choice for the operating forces and other customers
35 through teamwork, innovative business practices, and a well-equipped and highly skilled
36 workforce. The MDMC is located at the Yermo Annex and is housed in the largest single-story
37 structure ever constructed for the USMC. This allows the MDMC to repair all ground equipment
38 used by the USMC (MCLB Barstow 2016).

39

1 **1.6.2.4.4 Fleet Support Division**

2 The mission of the Fleet Support Division (FSD) is to receive, inspect, account for, issue, store,
3 and manage the Care-in-Store Program for Stores Account Code 3 Principal End Items and small
4 arms components. The division also manages the Executive Supply Support Program and
5 assembles and disassembles collateral material as well as Supply System Responsibility items,
6 sets, kits, and chests in support of the USMC requirements. The FSD also provides technical
7 assistance to Marine Corps Forces Reserve West and develops and monitors quality control
8 programs. The FSD is located in the Yermo Annex (MCLB Barstow 2016).

9 **1.7 CULTURAL RESOURCES COMPLIANCE**

10 In general, the NHPA and 36 CFR § 800 are the most frequently applicable requirements to the
11 management of cultural resources. Because these laws and regulations form the basis of most
12 day-to-day cultural resources compliance activities, they are discussed below in greater detail.

13 **1.7.1 The National Historic Preservation Act**

14 The NHPA was created to preserve the historical and cultural foundations of the country. Its
15 further purpose is to provide a historical focus for the American people by making cultural
16 resources a living part of community life and development. To protect the cultural resources
17 within its installation, MCLB Barstow shall:

- 18 • review their routine base activities as well as all proposed maintenance, construction, and
19 demolition projects to consider the effects of their actions on cultural resources in
20 accordance with Section 106 of the NHPA (see below);
- 21 • assume responsibility for the preservation of the historic properties and cultural resources
22 located on their property in accordance with Section 110 of the NHPA (see below); and
- 23 • consider submitting a formal nomination to the NRHP in accordance with Section 106 of
24 the NHPA if any cultural resources of particular archaeological or historical interest are
25 discovered that meet the eligibility requirements for the NRHP. Appendix B lists cultural
26 resources that have been recommended or determined eligible for inclusion in the NRHP.

27 1.7.1.1 National Register Criteria for Evaluation

28 Information for the following is taken from the National Register Bulletin “How to Apply the
29 National Register Criteria for Evaluation.” The full bulletin is available here:

30 <http://www.cr.nps.gov/nr/publications/bulletins/nrb/15/>

31 The quality of significance in American history, architecture, archaeology, engineering, and
32 culture is present in districts, sites, buildings, structures, and objects that possess integrity of
33 location, design, setting, materials, workmanship, feeling, and association, and:

- 34 A. That are associated with events that have made a significant contribution to the broad
35 patterns of our history; or
- 36 B. That are associated with the lives of persons significant in our past; or
- 37 C. That embody the distinctive characteristics of a type, period, or method of construction,
38 or that represent the work of a master, or that possess high artistic values, or that

1 represent a significant and distinguishable entity whose components may lack individual
2 distinction; or

3 D. That have yielded, or may be likely to yield, information important in prehistory or
4 history.

5 Criteria Considerations

6 Ordinarily cemeteries, birthplaces, or graves of historical figures, properties owned by historical
7 figures, properties owned by religious institutions or used for religious purposes, structures that
8 have been moved from their original locations, reconstructed historic buildings, properties
9 primarily commemorative in nature, and properties that have achieved significance within the
10 past 50 years shall not be considered eligible for the NRHP. However, such properties will
11 qualify if they are integral parts of districts that do meet the criteria or if they fall within the
12 following categories:

- 13 a. A religious property deriving primary significance from architectural or artistic
14 distinction or historical importance; or
- 15 b. A building or structure removed from its original location but which is significant
16 primarily for architectural value, or which is the surviving structure most importantly
17 associated with a historic person or event; or
- 18 c. A birthplace or grave of a historical figure of outstanding importance if there is no
19 appropriate site or building directly associated with his or her productive life; or
- 20 d. A cemetery which derives its primary significance from graves of persons of transcendent
21 importance, from age, from distinctive design features, or from association with historic
22 events; or
- 23 e. A reconstructed building when accurately executed in a suitable environment and
24 presented in a dignified manner as part of a restoration master plan, and when no other
25 building or structure with the same association has survived; or
- 26 f. A property primarily commemorative in intent if design, age, tradition, or symbolic value
27 has invested it with its own exceptional significance; or
- 28 g. A property achieving significance within the past 50 years if it is of exceptional
29 importance.

30 1.7.1.2 Section 106/36 CFR § 800 Compliance

31 **1.7.1.2.1 Overview**

32 When MCLB Barstow proposes an activity (undertaking), it must determine if the activity is
33 exempt from Section 106 compliance or if the action has the potential to affect historic properties
34 (Figure 1-3). This process includes identification of the resources that will be affected,
35 evaluation of any un-evaluated cultural resources that may be affected by these activities, and the
36 development of a plan for mitigating any adverse impacts. The mitigation plan may recommend
37 protection, avoidance, data recovery of the resource, or other treatments as appropriate.
38 Determination of the proper mitigation process requires consultation with the SHPO, Native
39 American tribal entities/Tribal Historic Preservation Officer (THPO), and any other interested
40 parties. This must occur prior to embarking on the proposed activity.

Figure 1-3 Section 106 Flow Chart

1.7.1.2.2 Procedures

When work orders or other actions are considered that affect the land, buildings, or structures at MCLB Barstow, they should be reviewed by the CRM. Acting on behalf of the CO, the CRM shall determine if the project area has been adequately surveyed and evaluated for cultural resources. If it is found that a resource will be affected, or if additional information is required to make a determination, the CRM shall notify the project manager of the Section 106 requirements that must be complied with prior to proceeding with the project.

Initial Section 106 Process

The initial step that must be taken by the responsible agency official is to establish whether the proposed project is an undertaking, identify the SHPO, Native American groups (THPO) and identify other interested parties such as local governments, and make plans to involve the general public in the process.

An undertaking is defined as “a project, activity, or program funded in whole or in part under the direct or indirect jurisdiction of a Federal agency, including those carried out on or behalf of a Federal agency; those carried out with Federal financial assistance; and those requiring a Federal permit, license or approval” [36 CFR § 800.16 (y)].

- If the CRM determines that a proposed project does not constitute an undertaking, or if it is an undertaking but has no potential to cause effects to historic properties (resources eligible for inclusion in the NRHP), then the Section 106 requirements have been complied with and no further action is necessary.
- If the CRM determines that the project is an undertaking and has the potential to cause effects to historic properties, the CRM must begin the process of identifying the historic properties. The CRM should notify the project manager or other project proponent of the results of the review within two weeks of the submission of a work order. If there is no undertaking or no effect, the project may proceed. If there is an undertaking or there is a potential effect, the Section 106 process must continue.

Identification of Historic Properties

The identification of historic properties involves the determination of the scope of efforts, identification of the area of potential effects (APE), identification of the historic properties, and evaluation of significance of the properties. The CRM may seek the assistance of NAVFAC SW in this process and in engaging a cultural resources management firm or firms to carry out the identification and NRHP evaluation of the potential historic properties.

If the recommendation is that there are no historic properties, or that there will be no effect on identified historic properties, the CO will notify the SHPO/THPO, provide appropriate documentation, and seek concurrence on the recommendations. The CO will also notify the public and other interested parties of the findings. SHPO/THPO concurrence operates at two levels: effect and eligibility.

If the SHPO/THPO agrees that there will be no effect and that none of the resources are eligible according to NRHP criteria, the Section 106 requirements have been complied with. The CRM should notify the project manager as soon as possible that the project can proceed.

- 1 • If the SHPO/THPO does not concur that there will be no effects, the CO must take steps
2 to reevaluate the identification of properties and/or the eligibility recommendations for
3 the properties.
- 4 • If the SHPO does not concur with the recommendation of eligibility, then the CO may
5 either agree or disagree with the finding. If the CO agrees with the SHPO's finding of
6 non-concurrence, the identification and/or eligibility recommendations must be reviewed
7 and reevaluated. If the CO disagrees with the SHPO, he must supply all documentation
8 and apply to the Keeper of the NRHP for a determination. If a federally recognized
9 Native American tribe (THPO) disagrees with a determination of eligibility involving a
10 property it believes has cultural or religious significance, the tribe can ask the ACHP to
11 request that the CO obtain a determination from the Keeper. If at the end of this process
12 the properties are determined not to be eligible for inclusion in the NRHP, the Section
13 106 process is complete. The CRM should notify the project manager as soon as possible
14 so that the project can proceed.
- 15 • If the final determination is that there are eligible properties within the project APE, the
16 CO must assess whether there will be adverse effects.

17 Assessment of Adverse Effects

18 The CO must assess if any adverse effects may result from the project. Such effects occur when
19 an undertaking has the potential to directly or indirectly change the NRHP-qualifying
20 characteristics of a historic property. These effects include physical destruction of or damage to
21 the property; alterations of a property not in accord with the Secretary of the Interior's Standards;
22 relocation of a property; change in the use of features of the property's setting; intrusion from
23 noise or visual impacts; neglect causing deterioration of the property; and transfer, lease, or sale
24 of a property out of federal ownership or control without adequate protection.

25 If the CO assesses that no historic properties will be affected by the undertaking, the CO should
26 notify the SHPO/THPO of this finding, provide documentation supporting the finding, and seek
27 concurrence. The CO should also notify interested parties and the general public of the finding.
28 If the SHPO/THPO concurs with the finding of no effect, the project may proceed, and the CRM
29 should notify the project manager as soon as possible.

- 30 • The SHPO/THPO may also concur with the assessment of no adverse effects but
31 recommend changes or impose conditions to ensure that any adverse effects will be
32 avoided. Compliance with the changes or conditions will result in a determination of no
33 effect. The CO must then take steps to address the conditions imposed by the
34 SHPO/THPO prior to notifying the Project Engineer or other project proponent that the
35 project can proceed.
- 36 • If the SHPO/THPO does not concur with the finding of no effect, the CO will review the
37 decision. If the CO agrees, the issue of adverse effects must be reassessed. If the CO does
38 not agree with the SHPO/THPO, the CO will send the documentation to and seek
39 comments from the ACHP.
- 40 • The ACHP may agree with the CO that there are no adverse effects or may agree as long
41 as certain changes are made, or conditions met. If changes or conditions are imposed, the
42 CO must address the conditions prior to notifying the Project Engineer or other project
43 proponent to proceed.

- If the final determination is that historic properties will be adversely affected by the project, steps must be taken to resolve the adverse effects.

Resolution of Adverse Effects

If adverse effects are found, consultation to resolve them must continue among the CO, SHPO/THPO, and other consulting parties. The CO must notify the ACHP of the adverse effects and invite the ACHP to participate. One of the consulting parties may also ask the ACHP to participate in the consultation. The ACHP will decide within 15 days whether it will participate, and notify all parties involved accordingly.

- The CO will continue to consult with all parties to form a plan to avoid, minimize the effects, or mitigate the effects of the project on historic properties. The CRM may work with NAVFAC SW to engage a cultural resources management firm or firms to prepare plans that will address the issues. The resultant documentation will be sent to the SHPO/THPO, and to the ACHP if it has chosen to participate, for concurrence.
- If the SHPO/THPO and the ACHP concur, then a MOA should be prepared and implemented. If the ACHP has not been part of the process, a copy of the MOA must be provided to the ACHP for their files. Once the provisions of the MOA are complete, the CRM will notify the Project Engineer or other project proponent to proceed with the project.
- If the SHPO/THPO does not concur and the CO agrees, consultation to resolve the adverse effects should continue. If the CO does not agree with the SHPO/THPO, consultation with the ACHP will be sought (if they are not already involved in the consultation). The ACHP comments will become part of the process in eventually preparing and implementing a MOA. Once complete, the CRM will notify the Project Engineer or other project proponent to proceed with the project.
- If there is no concurrence among the consulting parties and there is continued disagreement on the resolution of adverse effects, the consultation can be terminated. If consultation is terminated, the SHPO/THPO, other interested parties, and the general public must be notified.
- If the consulting parties cannot reach agreement, the ACHP will provide advisory comments to the CO that must be taken into account before a final decision is made. This decision can result in the project being abandoned, delayed, or continued.

1.7.1.3 Section 110 Compliance

1.7.1.3.1 Overview

An inventory of the resources that are eligible for inclusion in the NRHP must be compiled and plans for managing and preserving such resources must be prepared. The ICRMP is one step in meeting the base's responsibilities under Section 110, which is designed to ensure that historic properties are identified and protected from unnecessary damage.

1.7.1.3.2 Procedures

- **Archaeological Resource Evaluations.** Known archaeological sites that have not been formally evaluated for NRHP eligibility.

- 1 • Building Condition Assessments. Inventory and evaluate the buildings and structures at
2 MCLB Barstow that have not been previously assessed for NRHP eligibility. If any of
3 these buildings or structures are found to be NRHP–eligible, inspect each of them, assess
4 their current condition, and develop a maintenance program to preserve them. Create and
5 maintain a computerized list of buildings that may need to be inventoried and evaluated
6 over the next years and decades as they reach 45 to 50 years in age.
- 7 • Preserving Building/Historic District Integrity. At the present time, MCLB Barstow has
8 no buildings that make up a historic district. However, should one or more of the un-
9 inventoried buildings or structures be evaluated as NRHP–eligible, then the following
10 steps must be taken: (1) Following the Secretary of Interior’s Standards for Rehabilitation
11 of Historic Buildings (codified in 36 CFR § 67), repairs to the building or structure must
12 be done with appropriate designs, materials, and methods of construction; and (2) the
13 original architectural characteristics of the building or structure must be maintained if the
14 resource is being rehabilitated or planned for adaptive reuse.
- 15 • Historic Landscape Condition Assessments. Currently, no historic landscapes have been
16 identified at MCLB Barstow. An assessment would concentrate on the relationship
17 between the activities that occurred on the landscape and the physical components that
18 remain from those activities. These would include features, buildings, structures,
19 landscaping, roads, vegetation, site furnishings, water features, and elements expressing
20 military cultural traditions. If a landscape is identified at a later date, a management plan
21 must be created and implemented.
- 22 • Traditional Cultural Properties. There may be TCPs at MCLB Barstow. NRHP Bulletin
23 38 defines a TCP as “eligible for inclusion in the National Register because of its
24 association with cultural practices or beliefs of a living community that (a) are rooted in
25 the community’s history, and are (b) important in maintaining the continuing cultural
26 identity of the community” (Parker and King 1998). Rattlesnake Rock, a petroglyph site
27 (CA-SBR-73), may fit the definition of a TCP. Therefore, Native American groups
28 should be consulted about the resource. The resource’s NRHP eligibility status should be
29 updated, taking into account the recommendations of Dr. Goodfellow, and a plan for the
30 protection and maintenance of the property should be developed by the CRM, the Provost
31 Marshal Office, and any other group whose activities might impact the site.

32 1.7.1.4 NHPA Integration with NEPA

33 Integration between the NHPA and NEPA is essential so that federal agencies can meet the
34 purposes and requirements of both statutes in a timely and efficient manner. Compliance with
35 Section 106 of the NHPA requires that agencies take into account the effects that any
36 undertakings may have on historic properties, and compliance with NEPA requires that agencies
37 consider the effects of that undertaking on the quality of the human environment. Under NEPA
38 regulations (40 CFR § 1500–1508), the agency level of analysis depends on the potential of the
39 action to affect the environment. If a proposed action is believed to have no potential for
40 significant impact to the environment, a categorical exclusion (CATEX) may be issued.
41 However, any CATEX must be reviewed to ensure that there are no “extraordinary
42 circumstances” (such as impacts to historic properties) that would negate the exclusionary
43 process. Of particular relevance to cultural resources, MCO 5090.2 states that a CATEX should

1 not be used if the proposed action will “have an adverse effect on archaeological resources or
2 resources (including but not limited to ships, aircraft, vessels, and equipment) listed or
3 determined eligible for listing on the NRHP” (Volume 12, Chapter 3). SECNAVINST 5090.6A
4 also identifies Navy and Marine CATEXs that may affect cultural resources, including those that
5 involve alteration and additions, or demolition, disposal, or improvements to:

- 6 • existing buildings;
- 7 • decommissioning, disposal, or transfer of buildings, structures, vessels, aircraft, vehicles,
8 and equipment;
- 9 • non-routine repair, renovation, and transfer of such items;
- 10 • transfer, receipt, minor acquisition, or disposal of real property;
- 11 • installation and operation of utility and communication systems;
- 12 • closure or decommissioning of facilities;
- 13 • routine testing of military equipment; and
- 14 • routine military training.

15 All these exclusions are subject to review, and the CATEX cannot be used if any of these actions
16 would potentially have an adverse effect on archaeological or historical resources eligible for
17 inclusion in the NRHP. It is also important to note that the NHPA has a lower threshold than
18 does NEPA. Even if an undertaking is exempt from NEPA, Section 106 of NHPA may still
19 apply.

20 If the agency is unsure whether the effects of the action would be significant, it may prepare an
21 Environmental Assessment document. If relevant, EAs will include a section relating to the
22 potential effects the action may have on cultural resources in the project area. If an
23 Environmental Assessment results in a finding that significant impacts are likely to occur as the
24 result of the action, an Environmental Impact Statement (EIS) may be required. The EIS will
25 contain a detailed analysis of alternative approaches to the action and the impacts that each
26 alternative will have.

27 If the Environmental Assessment or EIS also addresses cultural resource concerns, the document
28 will discuss NRHP status, type of effect (adverse or not), and measures that should be
29 implemented to reduce the level of impact. If there is an adverse effect under an EIS, a MOA and
30 implementation of treatment will be required for Section 106 compliance.

31 1.7.1.5 Inadvertent Discovery of Cultural Resources and Human Remains

32 SOP No. 6 applies to the inadvertent discovery of buried cultural resources or historic properties
33 during an undertaking and defines the necessary actions that follow. SOP No. 7 applies to the
34 inadvertent discovery of human remains at MCLB Barstow.

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1 **2.0 CULTURAL RESOURCE MANAGEMENT STRATEGY**

2 **2.1 CULTURAL RESOURCES OVERVIEW**

3 The main purpose of the cultural resources overview is to provide a consolidated status update of
4 MCLB Barstow’s Section 110 inventory, address any evaluation requirements, and identify any
5 data gaps from previous investigations. The successful management of cultural resources at
6 MCLB Barstow requires an understanding of the current status of all cultural resources on the
7 base. This section provides a summary and results of the previous ICRMP, of previous cultural
8 resources investigations, and an inventory of all known cultural resources within the base,
9 including prehistoric and historic archaeological resources, as well as built environment
10 resources (buildings, structures, and objects).

11 Twenty cultural resources studies have been conducted at MCLB Barstow, and an additional 14
12 articles, books, and reports present regional overviews of cultural resources located in the
13 general vicinity. The first study conducted on base was performed by Hearn in 1978, and the
14 most recent studies were completed by SWCA, Leidos, and Far Western (Millington et al. 2016;
15 Treffers et al. 2016, Bryne 2015, and Byerly and Byrd 2018). A list of all previously conducted
16 cultural resource investigations and their locations within MCLB Barstow is presented in
17 Appendix B.

18 **2.1.1 Archaeological Resources**

19 In total, 197 archaeological resources have been identified at MCLB Barstow, consisting of 81
20 sites and 146 isolated resources. Of the 81 sites, 52 are prehistoric, 26 are historical, and three
21 are multi-component (containing both prehistoric and historical components). Six archaeological
22 sites have been evaluated for their NRHP eligibility (Table 2-1). One archaeological site has
23 been determined eligible for inclusion in the NRHP (CA-SBR-2910H); three have been
24 recommended eligible for inclusion in the NRHP (CA-SBR-73, CA-SBR-8319, and CA-SBR-
25 29325); one (CA-SBR-73) has been designated a CPHI; and another (CA-SBR-3033/H) has been
26 designated a CHL. Site CA-SBR-11840 was initially recommended eligible for listing in the
27 NRHP; however, after further evaluation, the USMC determined it was not eligible for listing in
28 the NRHP. The SHPO did concur with this determination (Polanco 2018). Twenty-six of the
29 archaeological sites have not been evaluated for NRHP eligibility and the remaining 50 sites
30 have been recommended not eligible for NRHP eligibility. The 146 isolated resources are
31 comprised of 34 prehistoric and 112 historic isolates. Isolated resources by definition are
32 considered not eligible for listing in the NRHP (MCLB Barstow 2016). A list of all
33 archaeological resources and their locations within MCLB Barstow are presented in Appendix B
34 of the ICRMP.

1 **Table 2-1 Evaluated Archaeological Resources at MCLB Barstow**

<i>State Trinomial Number</i>	<i>Period</i>	<i>NRHP Eligibility</i>
CA-SBR-73	Prehistoric	Recommended Eligible, California Point of Historical Interest
CA-SBR-2910/H	Historic	Eligible
CA-SBR-8319	Prehistoric	Recommended Eligible
CA-SBR-29325	Prehistoric	Recommended Eligible
CA-SBR-3033/H	Historic	California Historical Landmark
CA-SBR-11840	Prehistoric	Determined Not Eligible (Polanco 2018)

2 2.1.1.1 CA-SBR-73

3 Known as Rattlesnake Rock, CA-SBR-73 has been reported on since the late 1800s when it was
 4 named for the abundance of snakes observed by visitors (Crossman 1890; Mallery 1889; Steward
 5 1929). The first formal archaeological recordation was made by G.A. Smith in 1939, with
 6 numerous updates submitted since. The site consists of 54 panels of prehistoric petroglyph
 7 images on a volcanic rock (rhyodacite) outcrop standing approximately 20 feet (6 meters) high.
 8 In addition to the hundreds of petroglyph images believed to be of prehistoric origin, there are 28
 9 dated historic inscriptions that inscribed between 1887 and 1979, as well as dozens of inscribed
 10 initials that lack any date. Surrounded by mostly flat terrain, the rock outcrop is a conspicuous
 11 visual feature of the local landscape. Its location along the Mojave River less than one mile east
 12 of Elephant Mountain lends the site some geographic prominence, which is attested to by the
 13 wide time range of visitors represented in the archaeological and historical record (MCLB
 14 Barstow 2016).

15 Early archaeological recordings describe the presence of flaked stone tools, potsherds, ground
 16 stone tools, and an Olivella bead around the base of the rock outcrop. However, shovel test pits
 17 excavated in 1996 by Manley produced no buried prehistoric artifacts, and only three artifacts on
 18 the surface. Manly noted the presence of historic trash 65 feet (20 meters) to the north but did not
 19 include it as part of the archaeological site. Subsequent archaeological studies at the site have
 20 focused on photographic documentation of the petroglyphs (MCLB Barstow 2016).

21 Throughout the twentieth century, the site has been subject to impacts in the form of mechanical
 22 destruction (e.g., one report of dynamite blasting in 1910, removal of boulders or panels), and
 23 painted and scratched inscriptions of individuals' names going back at least to the late 1960s.

24 The site is listed as CPHI No. 40. In 2000, McCarthy and Manley prepared a draft NRHP
 25 nomination form for CA-SBR-73, finding the site eligible for inclusion in the NRHP under
 26 Criterion C. The nomination describes the site in detail and includes descriptions, photographs,
 27 and drawings of each rock art panel, historic inscriptions, noting the presence of vandalism. The
 28 nomination form was updated in 2005 by EDAW, Inc. for the 2006 MCLB Barstow ICRMP
 29 (Willey et al. 2006), and reviewed in 2008 by Sue Goodfellow, Ph.D.—Cultural Resources
 30 Specialist for the CMC. Dr. Goodfellow provided the MCLB Barstow CRM with comments and
 31 suggested revisions (MCLB Barstow 2016).

1 SWCA performed archaeological studies at the site in 2014–2016 in order to address Dr.
2 Goodfellows’ comments in accordance with recommendations in the 2011 ICRMP. Specifically,
3 SWCA’s site update and periodic monitoring focused on determining the full extent of the site
4 boundary, illustrating and taking additional photographs of petroglyph panels for more detailed
5 analysis, obtaining archival images, assessing the site condition, and recommending management
6 practices on the basis of the findings. Full details of this study are documented in a separate
7 report (Millington et al. 2016). The site boundary was expanded to include a historic and
8 prehistoric archaeological surface component outside the rock outcrop. Analysis of color-
9 enhanced digital photographs using D- Stretch imaging software failed to find any new panels or
10 undocumented elements of known panels. The site condition assessment focused on physical
11 weathering, mechanical destruction, and vandalism. Archival photographs were also obtained
12 and compared to the present-day observations. SWCA found no evidence of differential
13 weathering to the petroglyph panels as a result of sandblasting on the windward side of the rock
14 outcrop. Their study did identify specific rocks and panels potentially subjected to mechanical
15 destruction, including a possible location for the reported dynamite blast in 1910. Lastly, they
16 found no evidence for graffiti or vandalism subsequent to the installation of a locked chain-link
17 fence around the outcrop, ca. 1980–1995 (MCLB Barstow 2016).

18 Additionally, in January of 2015, a single spire-lopped bead was identified during a desert
19 tortoise survey conducted by Leidos, which overlapped with the boundaries of CA-SBR-73.
20 Although identified as an *Olivella biplicata* bead by Leidos, based on SWCA’s review of the
21 photograph of the bead in the site record, it appears to be an *Olivella dama* spire-lopped bead.
22 This bead was not observed during SWCA fieldwork (MCLB Barstow 2016).

23 SWCA revised the NRHP nomination form and California Department of Parks and Recreation
24 523-Series resource forms in 2016. SWCA concurs with the previous recommendations that the
25 site be considered eligible for inclusion in the NRHP under Criterion C and Criterion D (MCLB
26 Barstow 2016). As of 2020, the nomination form has not been submitted to the SHPO for
27 concurrence.

28 No construction, ground training, and/or range maintenance and sustainment activities should
29 occur within a 50-foot (15-meter) buffer zone and no aircraft training activities would occur
30 within a 350-foot (107-meter) buffer zone. Establishment of a buffer zone would avoid impacts
31 to CA-SBR-73. The NRHP evaluation of CA-SBR-73 should be submitted for SHPO
32 concurrence.

33 2.1.1.2 CA-SBR-6693H

34 The Atlantic and Pacific Railroad (CA-SBR-6693H) is a segment of a railroad alignment
35 originally constructed in 1883 by Southern Pacific. This railroad was originally a single track
36 line, and a second track was added in 1923 (Wedding 2003). This property is not owned by
37 MCLB Barstow, and therefore does not fall within its management purview. It is not discussed
38 further in this ICRMP, nor is it included in the totals above. For reference, this resource is
39 mapped in Appendix B, Figure 3, of the ICRMP.

1 2.1.1.3 CA-SBR-2910H

2 CA-SBR-2910H comprises segments of the National Old Trails Road that, in many areas,
3 became U.S. Route 66 early in the twentieth century when the road was paved for automobile
4 traffic. The National Old Trails Road, which parallels in some places the Old Spanish Trail, was
5 constructed in 1914. When it was paved in 1920 it became part of U.S. Route 66. The road was
6 upgraded in 1923 and completed as a two-lane highway in 1953 (Goodman et al. 2000). Maps
7 from the South Central Coastal Information Center (SCCIC) plot the resource running directly
8 through the entire Nebo Area of the base along Joseph L. Boll Avenue. The National Old Trails
9 Road has already been determined eligible for inclusion in the NRHP (MCLB Barstow 2016).

10 SWCA recorded and evaluated the segments of CA-SBR-2910H within MCLB Barstow
11 (Treffers et al. 2016). The subject property is a 1.71-mile segment of highway that runs the entire
12 length of the Nebo Area of the MCLB Barstow. Previously recorded and determined eligible for
13 inclusion in the NRHP, the four-lane highway was initially developed in 1914 as the National
14 Old Trails Highway and was later incorporated into U.S. Highway 66. Located between Barstow
15 to the west and Daggett to the east, the segment has been repaved and follows the original
16 northwest-southeast course for its entire length, but has been slightly realigned at just outside of
17 its western and eastern termini due to the development of I-40. Sloping downhill to the east, the
18 eastern portion of the segment retains the original two-lane design of the highway and crosses a
19 short drainage culvert. The western portion of the segment was expanded to four lanes west of
20 South Iwo Jima Street at an unknown date. As the main circulation route of the MCLB Barstow,
21 the setting of the recorded segment is largely developed and is lined with buildings (MCLB
22 Barstow 2016).

23 Treffers et al. (2016) concluded that the subject property is a highway segment that illustrates the
24 significance of U.S. Highway 66 as a strategic defense highway because it is the physical
25 element of the infrastructure that defines this theme. In assessing its integrity, the segment
26 follows its original alignment, but has been repaved multiple times and partially widened to four
27 lanes, which has negatively affected its design, materials, and workmanship. However, the
28 subject property remains a segment of former U.S. Highway 66 and continues to extend the
29 length of the still-active MCLB Barstow Nebo Area, and therefore retains other aspects of
30 integrity: it remains in the same location where it was originally constructed; it is still associated
31 with the other extant and eligible segments of U.S. Highway 66; and it retains its setting and
32 feeling as a segment of U.S. Highway 66 that continues to traverse MCLB Barstow as it did
33 during the period of significance (MCLB Barstow 2016).

34 The subject property is not associated with any important persons and does not possess integrity
35 of design, materials, and workmanship, and it does not appear eligible for inclusion in the NRHP
36 under Criteria B or C. No evidence was identified to suggest that the subject property is eligible
37 under Criterion D. However, because the subject property is associated with U.S. Highway 66
38 and the Strategic Highway Network, and it retains integrity of location, association, feeling, and
39 setting, it meets the registration requirements outlined in Cassity et al. (2012) and Roland et al.
40 (2012), and it appears eligible for inclusion in the NRHP under Criterion A. As such, it is defined
41 as a historic property in NHPA 16 U.S. Code 470 (w)(5).

1 2.1.1.4 CA-SBR-3033/H

2 CA-SBR-3033/H is a trail that has been referred to under a variety of names: the Mojave Trail,
3 the Old Spanish Trail, and the Mormon Trail. It is believed to be the route taken by Father
4 Francisco Garcés in 1776 on his journey from the Colorado River to San Gabriel, the path taken
5 by Jedediah Smith in 1826, as well as that used by trappers and settlers on their way to the
6 Pacific Coast. Historic maps indicate that a portion of the trail traverses the Yermo Annex. Site
7 location maps provided by the SCCIC plot the resource running parallel to, and just north of, the
8 Mojave River in the southern portion of the Yermo Annex. Specifically, the resource is plotted in
9 Section 10, Township 9 North, Range 1 East of the U.S. Geological Survey Yermo, California
10 7.5- minute quadrangle. The segment of CA-SBR-3033/H within MCLB Barstow has not been
11 previously recorded or evaluated for NRHP eligibility. The trail is listed as CHL No. 963. Recent
12 efforts by SWCA were unable to locate segments of CA-SBR-3033/H within MCLB Barstow
13 (Treffers et al. 2016).

14 2.1.1.5 CA-SBR-8319

15 This site consists of three cleared circles or rock rings. One possibly associated honey-colored
16 crypto-crystalline silicate flake is located nearby (Bryne 2015). Bryne (2015) recommends CA-
17 SBR-8319 as potentially eligible for inclusion in the NRHP. Bryne further recommends
18 evaluation or avoidance of CA-SBR-8319. No construction, ground training, and/or range
19 maintenance and sustainment activities should occur within a 50-foot (15-meter) buffer zone and
20 no aircraft training activities would occur within a 350-foot (107-meter) buffer zone.
21 Establishment of a buffer zone would avoid impacts to CA-SBR-8319. The NRHP evaluation of
22 CA-SBR-8319 should be submitted for SHPO concurrence.

23 2.1.1.6 CA-SBR-11840

24 This site is located near the western boundary of the Range West training area. This site consists
25 of a rock ring measuring 9 feet (2.75 meters) north–south by 7.2 feet (2.2 meters) east–west. The
26 ring is composed of approximately 35 embedded small- to medium-sized boulders of volcanic
27 material. The site is situated on a desert pavement covered ridgeline. No artifacts were observed
28 in association with the rock ring (Bryne 2015).

29 Bryne (2015) recommended CA-SBR-11840 as potentially eligible for inclusion in the NRHP.
30 Bryne further recommended evaluation or avoidance of CA-SBR-11840. Following further
31 archaeological evaluation of this site in 2017, the USMC determined CA-SBR-11840 was not
32 eligible for listing in the NRHP. The SHPO concurred with this determination (Polanco 2018).

33 2.1.1.7 CA-SBR-29325

34 This site is a rock ring located west of the existing trail along the ridgeline on the western
35 boundary of Range West. The site is located at the northern terminus of a ridgetop with a
36 sweeping view of the surrounding terrain. The site is approximately 33 feet (10 meters) west of
37 the existing trail, which runs roughly north–south along this ridgetop. The dimensions of the rock
38 ring are 14 feet (4.2 meters) long by 10.5 feet (3.2 meters) wide. This rock ring is loosely
39 constructed; approximately 50 rocks are arranged in a rough oval shape. The rocks do not appear

1 to be deeply embedded into the ground. Since no diagnostic artifacts are present, it is unclear
2 whether this site represents a prehistoric or a historic site (Bryne 2015).

3 Bryne (2015b) recommends CA-SBR-29325 as potentially eligible for inclusion in the NRHP
4 because the site may contain information important in prehistory or history and/or Native
5 American spiritual values. Bryne further recommends evaluation or avoidance of CA-SBR-
6 29325. No construction, ground training, and/or range maintenance and sustainment activities
7 should occur within a 50-foot (15-meter) buffer zone and no aircraft training activities would
8 occur within a 350-foot (107-meter) buffer zone. Establishment of a buffer zone would avoid
9 impacts to CA-SBR-29325. Additional cultural resources may be considered sensitive based on
10 future Native American consultation, and this should be taken into consideration when
11 developing final avoidance and/or mitigation measures. The NRHP evaluation of CA-SBR-
12 29325 should be submitted for SHPO concurrence.

13 **2.1.2 Historic Buildings and Structures**

14 Three previous studies have evaluated 714 buildings and structures located at MCLB Barstow
15 (JRP 2011; Manley 1996, 1999). In 1996, WMC evaluated 115 buildings as part of a larger
16 study; most of the buildings were World War II properties. WMC inventoried and evaluated 627
17 buildings and structures in 1999 (Manley 1999), including 28 that had previously been
18 inventoried in 1996; the resources addressed in this later study were primarily Cold War Era
19 properties. Following the 1999 study, many buildings and structures at MCLB Barstow were
20 destroyed. The most recent study, by JRP in 2011, identified 326 remaining structures at MCLB
21 Barstow. Of these, 80 were modern structures built after 1989; JRP recorded and evaluated the
22 remaining 246 properties. No buildings or structures evaluated in any of the three studies were
23 found to be eligible for inclusion in the NRHP, either as a district or individually.

24 In a letter dated May 14, 2013, SHPO concurred with JRP's NRHP eligibility determinations for
25 627 buildings and structures at MCLB Barstow, which concluded that all buildings, including
26 those that turned 50 years of age since previous evaluation efforts, are not eligible for NRHP
27 inclusion either individually or as contributors to a historic district. A comprehensive list of the
28 built environment properties is presented in Appendix B of the ICRMP. Properties that were
29 recently evaluated by JRP have not yet been designated with primary numbers. All buildings and
30 structures should be reevaluated for NRHP eligibility as they reach 50 years in age.

31 **2.1.3 Cultural Landscapes**

32 No cultural landscapes have been identified at MCLB Barstow.

33 **2.2 MONUMENTS AND MEMORIALS**

34 There are no monuments owned or maintained by MCLB Barstow. Manley (1996) identified and
35 recorded one monument at MCLB Barstow. The grave marker and monument of Walter P. Ross
36 (1887–1933), who at one time farmed land that is now part of MCLB Barstow, is located in the
37 Nebo Area. The monument is marked with a handmade concrete marker and polished metal
38 monument that reads “BELOVED HUSBAND WALTER H. ROSS. BORN NOV. 7, 1887,

1 DIED NOV. 15, 1933.” The entire area is enclosed by a black steel fence and covered with
2 poured concrete. The Walter H. Ross memorial belongs to, and is managed, by S-3 Ops.

3 **2.3 MANAGEMENT ACTIONS**

4 The purpose of this section is to discuss the current status of the cultural resources program at
5 MCLB Barstow since the signing of the original ICRMP, and to outline the compliance and
6 management needs that are required to maintain and enhance the program in the years to come.
7 As demonstrated in Section 1.4, MCLB Barstow is responsible for compliance with a wide range
8 of laws, regulations, policies, and directives related to cultural resources. This section addresses
9 management actions at MCLB Barstow to support the installation’s compliance with these
10 requirements, while fulfilling its mission and supporting the missions of its tenants.

11 This section addresses the following management items at MCLB Barstow:

- 12 • Summary and results of the 2016 ICRMP.
- 13 • Management goals for the ICRMP update.
- 14 • Future year undertakings, including MILCONs.
- 15 • Cultural resources compliance actions, including an overview of Section 106 and Section
16 110 of the NHPA, integration with NEPA, and the site plan approval process.
- 17 • Coordination and staffing for implementing the ICRMP.
- 18 • Data management, including annual reporting and metrics, Geographic Information
19 System (GIS), historical documents, and cultural resources documents.
- 20 • Curation of MCLB Barstow’s archaeological collections.
- 21 • Native American consultation history.
- 22 • Training and outreach efforts.
- 23 • Confidential information restrictions.
- 24 • Cultural resources management action items that should be addressed in the years to
25 come.
- 26 • The 2006 ICRMP recommended implementing a Memorandum of Understanding (MOU)
27 for Native American access to Rattlesnake Rock (CA-SBR-73), but subsequent
28 consultation did not reveal Native American groups with an active interest in accessing
29 the site. Should ongoing consultation with Native American tribes indicate an interest in
30 developing an MOU with MCLB Barstow, or if issues arise regarding access to the site,
31 the recommendation of developing an MOU should be revisited.

32 **2.3.1 Summary and Results of the Previous ICRMP**

33 2.3.1.1 Summary of the 2017- 2022 ICRMP Update

34 The 2011 ICRMP provided inventory and management requirements that it recommended the
35 cultural resources program pursue at MCLB Barstow over the next five years. Table 2-2 provides
36 a summary of these recommended actions and indicates which of the proposed actions have been
37 completed, or not completed, to date by MCLB Barstow, and also indicates which actions are no
38 longer applicable since the previous ICRMP. Actions marked as “not complete” may also refer
39 to actions that are in progress but have not yet reached the point of total completion.

1 **Table 2-2 Status of Action Items as Recommended in the 2016 ICRMP**

<i>Recommended Actions in 2016 ICRMP</i>	<i>Completed</i>	<i>Not Completed</i>	<i>No Longer Applies</i>
Archaeological Resources			
Monitor the conditions of known eligible sites and all recommended eligible sites (this includes annual site visits documenting any changes in site conditions, and mitigation measures as appropriate).		Ongoing	
Native American Concerns			
Develop a NAGPRA Comprehensive Agreement with Native American groups to provide procedures in the event that Native American remains are discovered.	yes		
Develop a Native American Consultation and Outreach Program.		Ongoing	
Documents			
Digitize the aforementioned items and create an intranet site providing access to these items as well as the ICRMP, Master Plan, INRMP, and any other pertinent documents.		Ongoing	
Create a summary database for prehistoric and historic archaeological site records, historic building and structure records, and survey reports.		Ongoing	
Create a database of GIS layers for the locations of archaeological sites, buildings, structures, objects, monuments, and memorials.		Ongoing	

2 Between 2014 and 2016, SWCA performed archaeological studies at Rattlesnake Rock (CA-
3 SBR-73) in order to address recommendations in the 2011 ICRMP (Millington et al. 2016). This
4 work entailed a site update and periodic monitoring focused on determining the full extent of the
5 site boundary, illustrating and taking additional photographs of petroglyph panels for more
6 detailed analysis, obtaining archival images, assessing the site condition, recommending
7 management practices on the basis of the findings, and updating the NRHP nomination form and
8 California Department of Parks and Recreation 523-Series resource forms (Millington et al.
9 2016).

10 SWCA also conducted an historic resources survey that identified, recorded, and evaluated
11 segments of U.S. Highway 66 (CA-SBR-2910H) within MCLB Barstow (Treffers et al. 2016).
12 This study also attempted to locate a trail (CA-SBR-3033/H) plotted on historical maps; efforts
13 by SWCA were unable to locate segments of CA-SBR-3033/H within MCLB Barstow.

14 Between 2013 and 2015, Leidos conducted intensive archaeological surveys in support of the
15 Barstow Training and Range Environmental Assessment (Bryne 2015). Leidos conducted

1 archaeological surveys on approximately 1,061.5 acres (429.6 hectares) of land within the APE
2 that had not been recently surveyed. The survey area included the Range West training area,
3 Range East and Known Distance Range Complex training area, Range Main Supply Route
4 training area, and Yermo Stables training area. A total of 26 newly identified archaeological sites
5 and 116 newly identified isolated artifacts were recorded during the archaeological surveys. The
6 newly identified sites consisted of prehistoric lithic scatters, historic refuse scatters, historic can
7 scatters, a historic refuse scatter and campsite, a historic camp, and a rock ring of undetermined
8 era. In addition, 17 previously recorded archaeological sites were located within the APE. These
9 sites included prehistoric lithic scatters, a rock ring, sleeping circles, and a petroglyph site (CA-
10 SBR-73). MCLB-SITE-7, a rock ring, is recommended as potentially eligible for inclusion in the
11 NRHP. Of the 17 previously recorded sites that occur within the APE, three prehistoric sites
12 including CA-SBR-73 (Rattlesnake Rock Petroglyph), CA-SBR-8319 (Sleeping Circles), and
13 CA-SBR-11840 (Prehistoric Rock Ring) are potentially eligible for inclusion in the National
14 Register (Byrne 2015).

15 Far Western Anthropological Research Group, Inc. conducted an NRHP evaluation of site CA-
16 SBR-11840 for Leidos in 2017 (Byerly and Byrd 2018). A total of 0.14 cubic meters of sediment
17 was excavated and sifted from two 0.5-x-0.5-meter shovel test probes (STP), including STP-1
18 within the 3.53-square-meter rock ring, and STP-2 just outside the feature (1.28 meters distant),
19 to depths not exceeding 30 centimeters below surface. No subsurface cultural material (artifacts,
20 faunal, archaeobotanical remains, or charcoal) was recovered, and an ancient pre-cultural duripan
21 was encountered between 25 and 30 centimeters below surface. A battered flaked felsite cobble/
22 core tool was recorded and left in situ on the surface, and this is the only artifact observed in
23 association with the rock ring. Far Western recommended from an archaeological perspective
24 that the site was considered ineligible for NRHP listing under Criteria A through D, and it is
25 suggested that based on currently available evidence that the site would not make a significant
26 contributing element to a proposed district. The SHPO did concur that CA-SBR-11840 is not
27 eligible for listing in the NRHP (Polanco 2018)

28 ASM Affiliates, Inc., in conjunction with Stratum Limited, removed painted white enamel
29 graffiti from five panels at CA-SBR-73 (Rattlesnake Rock) Petroglyph Site (Loubser and Becker
30 2019). The report also documented the condition assessment of the graffiti, its rock support, and
31 a description of the white paint graffiti's removal (Loubser and Becker 2019).

32 Earle and Associates (2019) submitted a workplan regarding a structured program of
33 consultation meetings with Native American tribes regarding cultural resources located at MCLB
34 Barstow, the management of these resources by MCLB Barstow personnel, and MCLB Barstow
35 compliance with federal regulations for CRM and protocols. This project is intended to facilitate
36 and document such consultation meetings, and to establish with the tribes a plan for future
37 ongoing consultation between MCLB Barstow and Native American tribes. The consultation
38 meetings and the implementing program for consultation are to be carried out in accordance with
39 Section 106 and Section 110 of the NHPA, as amended (Earle and Associates 2019). Native
40 American consultation is a component of the ongoing implementation of MCLB Barstow's 2016
41 ICRMP.

1 2.3.2 Goals and Objectives for The ICRMP Update

2 The management goal of this ICRMP is to provide MCLB Barstow with an implementation
3 process to integrate cultural resources management with base operations. This process can be
4 used to fulfill its mission in such a way that the actions and activities at MCLB Barstow are
5 consistent with cultural resources laws and environmental stewardship policy. It has the further
6 specific objectives to locate and evaluate the significance of archaeological sites and historic
7 buildings and structures at MCLB Barstow, to protect all NRHP–eligible properties, to address
8 Native American issues, to enforce federal laws against vandalism of archaeological sites and
9 historic buildings, to curate any archaeological or historical artifacts according to federal
10 curation standards, to contract with and oversee cultural resources management firms that
11 provide cultural resources services, and to set priorities for cultural resources activities that will
12 have the least impact on military activities at the various facilities that make up MCLB Barstow.
13 Listed below are ongoing cultural resources management practices that MCLB Barstow should
14 maintain and continue to implement.

- 15 • Protect cultural resources heritage under MCLB Barstow’s control as an essential part of
16 the defense mission; this includes the protection of all NRHP–eligible properties.
- 17 • Maintain SOPs (see Section 3) to manage cultural resources in accordance with
18 established laws and regulations, as well as DoD, DoN, and USMC policy.
- 19 • Maintain curation standards for archaeological collections as set forth in 36 CFR § 79.
- 20 • Maintain the data system for archaeological site information and collection to ensure that
21 it is current and accurate.
- 22 • Educate all MCLB Barstow personnel on existing base cultural resources and the
23 procedures for handling the unanticipated discovery of cultural resources, as described in
24 SOPs 6 and 7 (even though not every MCLB Barstow department is directly or indirectly
25 involved with cultural resources).
- 26 • Visit all eligible sites periodically to observe their condition.
- 27 • Provide continued maintenance of the GIS database repository within the Public Works
28 Division and continue to add specific information related to MCLB Barstow’s
29 archaeological sites, buildings, and areas surveyed.
- 30 • Evaluate all buildings and structures as they reach 50 years in age for NRHP eligibility
31 during the five-year term of this update.
- 32 • Continue communications with tribal representatives to ensure sacred sites are not
33 adversely impacted by training or construction.
- 34 • Continue to inventory and catalog cultural resources information (documents,
35 photographs, site and building plans, old real property records, maps, original drawings,
36 and personal papers maintained by the S-F Facilities Installation and Logistics
37 Department).
- 38 • Digitize any cultural resources documents held by MCLB Barstow not already in digital
39 formats. Submit all outstanding archaeological evaluations for SHPO concurrence.
40 Evaluate un-evaluated archaeological properties for NRHP eligibility.

2.3.3 Cultural Resources Compliance Actions, Future Year Undertakings

In summary of all items discussed in this section, it should be the goal of the MCLB Barstow cultural resources program to address each of the following management action items in the coming years.

- CA-SBR-2910H been determined eligible for inclusion in the NRHP and the segment that occurs within MCLB Barstow has been evaluated to determine whether it is a contributing element to the larger resource (Treffers et al. 2016). The segment of CA-SBR-2910H that occurs within MCLB Barstow appears eligible for inclusion in the NRHP. To ensure that this historic property is not adversely affected by future development projects, any project work that includes portions of the historic road or areas immediately adjacent should be reviewed for conformance with the Secretary of the Interior's Standards for Rehabilitation. During the project planning phase (prior to any construction activities), input shall be sought from a qualified architectural historian or historic architect meeting the Secretary of the Interior's Professional Qualifications Standards. This input will ensure the avoidance of any direct/indirect physical changes to those character-defining features that convey the historic significance of CA-SBR-2910H such as its alignment and setting. The findings and recommendations of the architectural historian or historic architect shall be documented in a Secretary's Standards Project Review Memorandum, at the schematic design phase. This memorandum shall analyze all project components for compliance with the Secretary's Standards for Rehabilitation. Project components to be analyzed shall include direct and indirect changes to historical resources and their setting. Should design modifications be necessary to bring projects into compliance with the Secretary's Standards for Rehabilitation, the memorandum will document those recommendations.
- CA-SBR-8319, a prehistoric rock ring, has been recommended eligible for listing in the NRHP (Bryne 2015). Bryne further recommends evaluation or avoidance of CA-SBR-8319. No construction, ground training, and/or range maintenance and sustainment activities should occur within a 50-foot (15-meter) buffer zone and no aircraft training activities would occur within a 350-foot (107-meter) buffer zone. Establishment of a buffer zone would avoid impacts to CA-SBR-8319. Additional cultural resources may be considered sensitive based on future Native American consultation, and this should be taken into consideration when developing final avoidance and/or mitigation measures. The NRHP evaluation of CA-SBR-8319 should be submitted for SHPO concurrence.
- CA-SBR-29325, a rock ring of prehistoric or historic age, has been recommended eligible for listing in the NRHP (Bryne 2015). Bryne further recommends evaluation or avoidance of CA-SBR-29325. No construction, ground training, and/or range maintenance and sustainment activities should occur within a 50-foot (15-meter) buffer zone and no aircraft training activities would occur within a 350-foot (107-meter) buffer zone. Establishment of a buffer zone would avoid impacts to CA-SBR-29325. Additional cultural resources may be considered sensitive based on future Native American consultation, and this should be taken into consideration when developing final avoidance and/or mitigation measures. The NRHP evaluation of CA-SBR-29325 should be submitted for SHPO concurrence.
- Following the completion of JRP's 2011 study, all extant World War II and Cold War Era built resources have been inventoried and evaluated for NRHP eligibility, and the

1 SHPO concurred with that study’s finding. Post-1989 buildings will need to be
2 inventoried as they come of age.

- 3 • Develop, acquire, and maintain (at a very minimum) all Common Installation Picture
4 (CIP) data layers with associated metadata, as identified in the GEOFidelis data model
5 per the guidance/standards set forth in MCO 11000.25A (2013).
- 6 • Submit all outstanding archeological evaluations for SHPO concurrence and evaluate the
7 26 remaining un-evaluated archeological properties for NRHP eligibility.
- 8 • In compliance with 36 CFR § 79, MCLB Barstow will consult with appropriate Native
9 American groups/individuals regarding the collection of artifacts and their conservation
10 at MCAGCC. MCLB Barstow may discuss the possibility of the reburial process of
11 artifacts during consultation with appropriate Native American groups/individuals.
- 12 • MCLB Barstow will consult with appropriate Native American groups/individuals on the
13 development of a NAGPRA Comprehensive Agreement in the event that Native
14 American remains are discovered.
- 15 • MCLB Barstow may discuss buffer zone standards around archaeological sites during
16 consultation with the appropriate Native American groups/individuals.

17 Recommended management action items specific to Rattlesnake Rock (CA-SBR-73) are as
18 follows:

- 19 • A revised NRHP nomination form of Rattlesnake Rock (CA-SBR-73) was updated in
20 2016 by SWCA. SWCA concurred with the previous recommendations that the site be
21 considered eligible for inclusion in the NRHP under Criterion C and Criterion D (MCLB
22 Barstow 2016). As of 2020, the revised nomination form has not been submitted to the
23 SHPO for concurrence. MCO 5090.2, Volume 8, contains policy regarding nomination
24 for listing in the NRHP.
- 25 • The 2016 ICRMP recommended implementing a MOU for Native American access to
26 Rattlesnake Rock (CA-SBR-73), but subsequent consultation did not reveal Native
27 American groups with an active interest in accessing the site. Should ongoing
28 consultation with Native American tribes indicate an interest in developing an MOU with
29 MCLB Barstow, or if issues arise regarding access to the site, the recommendation of
30 developing an MOU should be revisited.
- 31 • Block unofficial roads on the north and south sides of the site, and train MCLB staff to
32 enter the area only on-foot. Restricting vehicle access will facilitate revegetation and help
33 restore the look and feeling of the prehistoric setting, as well as prevent further
34 destruction of the adjacent archaeological material. Because this represents the sole
35 source of visible, ongoing impacts during this study’s monitoring period, addressing this
36 issue should take the highest priority.
- 37 • No construction, ground training, and/or range maintenance and sustainment activities
38 should occur within a 50-foot (15-meter) buffer zone and no aircraft training activities
39 would occur within a 350-foot (107-meter) buffer zone. Establishment of a buffer zone
40 would avoid impacts to CA-SBR-73.
- 41 • Continue on-foot location monitoring by Military Police patrolling the Yermo Annex
42 area.
- 43 • Provide a vandalism-resistant lock on the gates, and key control.

- 1 • Establish a contact person and a protocol for a simplified vetting process to grant
2 extended visitation outside the fenced area, which would distinguish legitimately
3 interested parties from potential vandals. The same contact person and vetting protocol
4 can be applied for researchers. Visitation inside the fenced area for research purposes
5 should be accompanied by trained MCLB staff.
- 6 • Conduct regular (minimally, quarterly) site visits to assess condition. Consider special
7 visits after extreme weather events such as heavy rains and major windstorms.
8 Appropriately vetted citizen scientists (e.g., the Society for California Archaeology’s
9 California Site Stewardship Program or local historical associations such as the Mojave
10 River Natural History Association or Mojave Desert Heritage and Cultural Association)
11 can be leveraged to help if base support is not available.
- 12 • Visibility can lead to protection. If the site has well-informed and frequent visitors, it may
13 be more efficient to protect, detect, and quickly repair damage. Consider creating
14 pamphlets and interpretative signage on the outside of the protective fence.
- 15 • Invite Native American tribal group members to site visits through email and telephone
16 calls. A Native American contact program undertaken during the preparation of the 2011
17 ICRMP received no responses. MCLB Barstow personnel have indicated that no Native
18 American visits have been arranged in recent years. However, recent outreach conducted
19 for a 2016 Range and Training Environmental Assessment has yielded at least two
20 responses from Native American tribal groups. A program of outreach focused on
21 providing access to Rattlesnake Rock is likely to be more fruitful than previous, more
22 general outreach attempts.
- 23 • Conduct additional historical research on the historic inscriptions, including attempting to
24 identify the individuals represented by initials such as “A.W.” to determine whether they
25 were important historical figures.

26 Recommended management action items specific to Archaeological sites CA-SBR-8319 and
27 CA-SBR-29325:

- 28 • MCLB Barstow will provide copies of Extended Phase I or Phase II SOWs being
29 prepared to test archaeological resources for NRHP eligibility and any updated site
30 records to consulting tribes that show interest in receiving these SOWs.
- 31 • Conduct regular monitoring (minimally, biannually) site visits to assess condition.
32 Consider special visits after extreme weather events such as heavy rains and major
33 windstorms. Appropriately vetted citizen scientists (e.g., the Society for California
34 Archaeology’s California Site Stewardship Program or local historical associations such
35 as the Mojave River Natural History Association or Mojave Desert Heritage and Cultural
36 Association) can be leveraged to help if base support is not available.

37 2.3.3.1 Future Cultural Resource Planned Projects

38 Table 2-3 lists the future cultural resources planned projects with a short description and their
39 funding status.

1

Table 2-3 Future Cultural Resource Planned Projects

<i>Project Title</i>	<i>Funding Status</i>	<i>Description</i>
Cultural Resources Preservation and Management, CA-SBR-2910H, U.S. Historic Route 66	Approved in Encore- Awaiting funds	In order to preserve the CA-SBR-2910H segment of U.S. Route 66, MCLB Barstow will display road signs along the shoulder of the highway, pavement stencils along the right-of-way, information kiosk with flagpole at the front gate, an additional information kiosk at the back gate, and a historical 3D monument along the verge of the highway.
Recover Displaced Rock Panels at CA-SBR-73 Rattlesnake Rock Petroglyph Site	Submitted as Research Project	Examination of the surrounding area may locate and uncover overturned petroglyph panels that have broken off during natural occurrences and/or human impacts.
Identification and Analysis of Historic Properties at CA-SBR-73 Rattlesnake Rock Petroglyph Site	Approved in Encore – Awaiting funding approval in Encore	Photogrammetry, both aerial and close-rang is to be conducted to record and detect petroglyph panels due to corrosion and vandalism.
Incised Inscriptions Removal at Rattlesnake Rock Petroglyph Site	Approved in Encore – Awaiting funds	Secretary of Interior certified archaeologist to removed incised graffiti from 38 panels.
Inventory and Evaluation of Historic Properties at CA-SBR-73 Rattlesnake Rock Petroglyph Site	Approved in Encore – Awaiting funds	Ground-penetrating Radar to locate any buried artifacts and investigate the stone and soil berm located in the surrounding area of the site.
Heritage and Designation of Historic Properties at CA-SBR-73 Rattlesnake Rock Petroglyph Site	Approved in Encore – Awaiting funding approval in Encore	Intense research to determine the true heritage behind Rattlesnake Rock, identify stakeholders and to recognize ancestral significance.
Public Outreach and Education at CA-SBR-73 Rattlesnake Rock Petroglyph Site	Approved in Encore – Awaiting funding approval in Encore	Informational brochures and kiosk with historical information about the site, and/or low pedestals in front of petroglyphs with minimal interpretive text; for example, on the petroglyphs' age and stylistic affiliations.

1 **Table 2-3 Future Cultural Resource Planned Projects (continued)**

<i>Project Title</i>	<i>Funding Status</i>	<i>Description</i>
Research Historic Property Inventory and Evaluation	Approved in Encore – Awaiting funding approval in Encore	Intern to conduct background research at the state and national repository for historic and archaeological resources data to identify buildings for NRHP eligibility in regard to support involving World War II, World War II Prisoners of War, and the National Old Trails Highway (U.S. Route 66).

2 2.3.3.2 Proposed Military Construction Projects and Special Projects

3 Sixteen MILCON Projects are currently planned for MCLB Barstow between Fiscal Year (FY)
4 2020 and FY 2026 (Table 2-4). Because there could be impacts to cultural resources or NRHP–
5 eligible sites at MCLB Barstow, the CRM should review all proposed projects at the installation
6 to assess possible effects to cultural resources.

7 Funding for construction projects comes directly from HQMC or from Base Operational Funds.
8 The Public Works Division has its own budget to fund minor construction and repair projects.

9 The project may be imminent or one that is projected for the future. The Public Works Division
10 must consult with the CRM to determine what projects will affect cultural resources, and the
11 CRM will review all project requests that may affect such resources. The CRM will work with
12 project managers to reduce any adverse effects, will ensure that all projects are in compliance
13 with Section 106 of the NHPA, and will further coordinate with the state SHPO concerning the
14 appropriate treatment of the resource(s). The CRM may ask for assistance from NAVFAC SW
15 regarding management of cultural resources projects.

16 **Table 2-4 Proposed MILCON Projects at MCLB Barstow**

<i>FY</i>	<i>MILCON No.</i>	<i>Project Description</i>
Nebo Development Projects		
20	P958	Construction of three aboveground fuel storage tanks and fuel dispersing spot.
22	P941	Construction of a new bi-directional interconnecting potable water supply line between separate MCLB Barstow sites (Nebo and Yermo) to support the operation of the Logistics Base. Construction will include approximately 10,300 meters (33,800 feet) of pipeline and a pump station.
22	P948	Purchase of 600 acres of privately held land, transfer 4,500 acres of U.S. Bureau of Land Management property, and obtain two easements.
22	P964	Construction of an adequately sized warehouse to provide covered space for bulk and in storage; aisle space; space for receiving, packing, and crating; office space for direct warehouse supervision (non-administrative); and toilet facilities.

1 **Table 2-4 Proposed MILCON Projects at MCLB Barstow (continued)**

<i>FY</i>	<i>MILCON No.</i>	<i>Project Description</i>
24	P962	Construction of a Family Services Center, supporting informational programs, and family services to qualified DoD personnel and their family members. It will be a total of 287 m ² (3,091 SF).
26	P110	Construction of a multi-story Bachelor Officer Quarters with 26 1+IE rooms for grades 01-010, W1-W5 personnel.
26	P968	Construction of a new training facility at the main Nebo site at MCLB Barstow to accommodate the new increased mission for the Warrior Strengthening Program. The facility will include computerized training classrooms, private one-on-one training rooms, administrative space for training staff and storage of classroom material. It will have 579 m ² (6,230 SF) of space and 2,575 m ² (335 square yards) for 88 parking spaces.
Yermo Development Projects		
20	P804	Construction of a 9,515-SF steel frame structure to house the vehicle and equipment maintenance shop, lubrication shop, and railroad support maintenance facility at Yermo Annex.
20	P953	Construction of a new facility for the Materials Handling Equipment Section, which will be used to house all Materials Handling Equipment functions and provide direct labor support to the Maintenance Center. It will produce 523m ² of consolidated work area.
20	P961	Construction of a standard structural fire station for the Yermo Area of MCLB Barstow. The station will support 2.5 engine companies, 16 crew members, and a Hazmat Response Trainer.
21	P950	Construction of three evaporation basins at the Industrial Waste Treatment Facility. Each basin will be 110 x 100 feet with a depth of 6 feet.
21	P949	Consolidation of Maintenance Center Barstow nonproduction personnel and Maintenance Center Training into one centrally located facility.
22	P935	Construction of a new building at Yermo Annex, MCLB Barstow to house all administrative operations of the Fleet Support Center.
22	N/A	Construction of a 9, 700-SF Welding Facility at the Marine Depot Maintenance Center Complex.
23	N/A	Construction of a 27,000-SF Road Testing Facility at the Marine Depot Maintenance Center Complex.
26	P967	Construction of a new Combat Vehicle Repair facility designed specifically for FSD preservation/receiving functions. The project will construct 557 m ² (6,000 SF) of space and 56 m ² (600 SF) of concrete.

2 **2.4 DATA MANAGEMENT**3 **2.4.1 Data Calls and Annual Reporting**

4 The CRM at MCLB Barstow is responsible for responding to data calls and asset management
5 inventories on an annual basis. These responses may include inputting cultural resources data
6 into DoN databases or providing responses to HQMC personnel via telephone or email. It is
7 imperative that the CRM maintain accurate records of each data call response. The CRM should
8 implement a systematic approach to annual reporting and metrics that includes creating an
9 electronic file for each response labeled with the correct FY, and containing any supporting

1 documentation used to explicate their data call responses. Additional guidance for this process is
2 provided in DoD Instruction 4715.16, Enclosure 5, and MCO 5090.2, Volume 8.

3 Annual reviews should be conducted following publication of the initial ICRMP. The annual
4 review process involves contacting internal and external stakeholders to update any POC
5 changes, note upcoming projects, discuss initiatives completed within the last year, and address
6 any other concerns/issues that may have arisen. Changes in the status of cultural resources (e.g.,
7 eligibility determinations, building demolition, damages or improvements), and MCLB
8 Barstow’s response to metrics in DoD Instruction 4715.16 should also be included in the annual
9 review. During the annual review process, installations are also expected to complete a self-
10 evaluation of the cultural resources program’s performance over the past year, and address any
11 outstanding issues, challenges, or successes that the program has experienced. Annual reviews at
12 MCLB Barstow are provided to the SHPO in a letter each year.

13 **2.4.2 Federal Archaeological Activities**

14 Once a year, the CRM is expected to complete two standardized questionnaires regarding the
15 archaeological activities that have taken place at MCLB Barstow. The two questionnaires tend to
16 emphasize different points. The Marine Corps Cultural Resources Year End Report is sent to
17 HQMC and is due in January. The Report to Congress is also sent to the HQMC. This latter
18 questionnaire is compiled with those from other USMC facilities, and a report is submitted to the
19 Secretary of the Interior. The Secretary of Interior’s Report to Congress on Federal
20 Archaeological Activities is required by ARPA 16 U.S. Code Section 470.

21 **2.4.3 Geographic Information Systems**

22 As stated in MCO 5090.2, Volume 8, paragraph 030309, integrating cultural resources
23 management data with MCLB Barstow’s GIS program supports the USMC mission of readiness.
24 A database of GIS layers should be developed for all archaeological sites, historic built
25 environment resources, survey coverage to date, and any sensitivity assessments that have been
26 conducted at MCLB Barstow in conformance with MCO 11000.25A (2013).

27 The mission of the MCLB Barstow’s GIS program is to create, analyze, manage, and distribute
28 authoritative, standardized geospatial information, products, and services to support military
29 readiness and quality of life with an emphasis on natural and cultural resources. As many of the
30 training areas and cultural resources are not demarcated in the field, GIS-based maps are the
31 primary tool for implementing programmatic instructions and for integrating land use and
32 cultural resources management. This geospatial technology provides MCLB Barstow with
33 potentially increased accuracy in communicating changes in land use and cultural resources
34 information. In addition, well-maintained and accessible GIS-based data also improve the
35 likelihood of success for long-term planning.

36 MCO 11000.25A provides installations with guidance for acquiring, using, and implementing
37 Marine Corps Installation Geospatial Information and Services, also referred to as GEOFidelis,
38 in support of USMC installation management. As the GIS program at MCLB Barstow continues
39 to develop and become more sophisticated over time, the Installation Geospatial Information and

1 Services should be implemented per the Digital Spatial and Geospatial Standards provided in
2 MCO 11000.25A.

3 **2.4.4 Historical Documents**

4 Documents such as maps, plans, photographs, and property records that have been acquired
5 throughout the existence of a base can be an important part of the historical use and development
6 of a facility. At MCLB Barstow, there is no museum or central repository for the various
7 elements that make up the installation's documentation record. The various elements are
8 distributed among numerous departments, although the base historian is in the process of
9 collecting material. The historic records that are maintained include:

- 10 • Certificates of lineage and honors;
- 11 • Command chronologies;
- 12 • Listing of former COs;
- 13 • Press clippings concerning the command from local civilian newspapers;
- 14 • Unit insignia;
- 15 • Listing of facilities named in commemoration;
- 16 • Photographs of historical interest (functions, ceremonies, buildings);
- 17 • Correspondence of historical interest (significant command or staff actions); and
- 18 • Oral history interviews.

19 **2.4.5 Data Integration with the California Historical Resource Information System**

20 The California Historical Resource Information System (CHRIS) operates as the state repository
21 for historic and archaeological resources data. Federal, state, and local land-managing agencies
22 as well as academic institutions and private consultants submit cultural resources site records and
23 reports to one of nine CHRIS information centers located throughout the state of California.
24 Previously, the local CHRIS information center for MCLB Barstow was located at the San
25 Bernardino County Museum. At present, the local CHRIS information center for MCLB Barstow
26 is the SCCIC at California State University, Fullerton. Copies of cultural resources site records
27 and reports for MCLB Barstow are submitted to the SCCIC by the CRM. Contact information
28 for the SCCIC is provided below.

29 **South Central Coastal Information Center**

30 California State University, Fullerton
31 Department of Anthropology 800 North State College Blvd.
32 P.O. Box 6846
33 Fullerton, CA 92834-6846
34 Contact: Ms. Stacy St. James, Coordinator Telephone: (657) 278-5395
35 Fax: (657) 278-5542
36 Email: scsic@fullerton.edu
37 Website: <http://anthro.fullerton.edu/scsic/>

2.5 COORDINATION AND STAFFING

The ICRMP focuses on management of the cultural resources at MCLB Barstow. This includes identification, evaluation, and protection, as well as compliance for projects that may affect known or unknown cultural resources. To adequately achieve this management, the ICRMP must be integrated with the daily activities of the base, other planning documents, and with outside entities.

2.5.1 Internal Coordination and Staffing Overview

The CRM must work with MCLB Barstow personnel on a daily basis to ensure that essential mission activities are fully supported and that base cultural resources are adequately protected. The integration of the ICRMP with the INRMP is relatively straightforward because the management of both resource types falls under a single manager within the Environmental Division (the CRM). The ICRMP should become an integral part of the base Master Plan, be referenced in the text, and be attached as an appendix to the Plan. Planning documents prepared for projects should reference the ICRMP and its procedures, especially if any of the planned activities may impact cultural resources. All outside entities that utilize the base should be informed of their responsibilities in regard to cultural resources as defined by the ICRMP.

Prior to any maintenance, training, or construction/demolition activity that has the potential to affect cultural resources, the installation office, division, or user must notify the CRM and provide plans of the proposed action(s). If records on file with the Environmental Division indicate that the area has been adequately inventoried and no eligible resources have been reported, the CRM will notify the applicant and the proposed action can proceed, pending other mandated approvals (e.g., natural resource concerns, conformance with the Master Plan, etc.). Table 2-5 provides the contact name and phone number for staff within the Environmental Division.

Contact with the CRM should occur well in advance of the proposed action to allow for adequate review time, inventory, and evaluation, along with implementation of avoidance or other compliance measures as needed. For example, if an eligible or recommended eligible building is slated for demolition, time would be needed for an inventory and evaluation. If the building is determined to be eligible, and adversely affected, a treatment plan would be needed, along with a MOA. The time and funds required to obtain compliance will vary based on the size and complexity of the proposed action. The basic steps of this process are outlined below.

- 1) Action/activity is proposed.
- 2) Applicant notifies CRM.
- 3) CRM identifies required cultural resource compliance measures and report back to Applicant.
- 4) Applicant authorizes required measures.
- 5) CRM oversees compliance.

1

Table 2-5 Environmental Division Points of Contact

<i>Points of Contact</i>	<i>Organization</i>	<i>Contact Information</i>
Jason Thompson	Environmental Director	760-577-6937
Karen Donovan	Environmental Protection Assistant	760-577-6416
Miguel Arandaguillen	Environmental Services Branch (Branch Chief)	760-577-6784
Melvin Bracey	ENV. Services HAZ Waste Materials Program Manager	760-577-7549
Scott Figueroa	ENV. Services HMMS/HW Operator	760-577-7442
Tyrone Turner	ENV. Services HM/Toxics	760-577-6836
Arley A. Lessard	ENV. Services QRP/Solid Waste Program Manager	760-577-6941
Arley A. Lessard	ENV. Services Storage Tank AST/UST	760-577-6941
VACANT	Plans & Conservation Branch (Supervisor)	760-577-6443
Willam Bueno	Plans & Conservation Branch NEPA Planner	760-577-6318
Benjamin (Cody) Leslie	Plans & Conservation Branch Natural Resources Specialist/ Cultural Resources Program	760-577-6744
James Fejeran	ENV. Compliance Branch (Supervisor)	760-577-6888
VACANT	ENV. Compliance Water Program	760-577-6811
Michael Fernandez	ENV. Compliance Air Program	760-577-6188
VACANT	ENV. Compliance ER/IR	760-577-6982
Paul Willis	ENV. Managers EMS Program	760-577-6363
Cathey L. De Vault-Donaldson	ENV. Managers CETEP Program Coordinator	760-577-6890
VACANT	ENV. Managers ECC/ECE Program	760-577-5846

2.5.2 External Coordination (Agencies and Stakeholders) Overview

External stakeholders include Native American tribes, the SHPO, the ACHP, MCLB Barstow tenant organizations, and others. Consultation with Native American tribes includes government-to-government interactions related to the ownership, use, access, and disposal of properties of significance to Native Americans; and as interested parties in consultation pursuant to the NHPA and NEPA. Non-federally recognized tribes are consulted as interested parties, whereas federally recognized tribes are consulted in both instances. Consultation with the California SHPO is required for NHPA Section 106 implementation, and the ACHP may be invited to comment on the Section 106 process. Other external stakeholders may include the City of Barstow, the Bureau of Land Management, and any parties that have a vested interest in the management of cultural resources at MCLB Barstow.

The SHPO is a key agency with respect to the cultural resources at MCLB Barstow in that the SHPO advises and assists the base in carrying out its responsibilities as defined by Section 106 of the NHPA. NAVFAC SW is also involved, helping the base meet its regulatory requirements and stewardship goals. Copies of archaeological and historical site records and reports are kept by the SCCIC at California State University, Fullerton. Because the City of Barstow has annexed a large portion of the Nebo Area and Rifle Range, it should be informed of any decisions that may affect cultural resources on that portion of MCLB Barstow. The CRM should provide the City Planning Department with copies of any project work plans that may affect cultural resources. The City Planning Department staff should review these plans and make comments if there are concerns. It is recognized that the City has no authority over projects on federal lands, and any comments provided would be solely in an advisory capacity.

Upon completion of a project, the final draft of the project report should be sent to the City to be placed in a confidential file. Additional groups interested in the cultural resources and their protection at MCLB Barstow are the Bureau of Land Management, the ACHP, and local Native American groups. Copies of project plans that adversely affect NRHP-eligible cultural resources will be sent to the ACHP for comment.

Table 2-6 lists the external stakeholders that should be consulted, as appropriate, regarding cultural resources management issues at MCLB Barstow.

Table 2-6 List of External Stakeholders

<i>Name</i>	<i>Contact Information</i>
MCLB Barstow Tenant Organizations	
S-4 Installation and Logistics Department, Public Works Division	United States Marine Corps Marine Corps Logistics Base, Barstow Barstow, CA 92311-5013
S-1 Manpower Department	United States Marine Corps Marine Corps Logistics Base, Barstow Barstow, CA 92311-5013
Special Staff Department, Public Affairs Office	United States Marine Corps Marine Corps Logistics Base, Barstow Barstow, CA 92311-5013

Table 2-6 List of External Stakeholders

<i>Name</i>	<i>Contact Information</i>
Defense Distribution Depot Barstow	United States Marine Corps Marine Corps Logistics Base, Barstow Barstow, CA 92311-5013
Defense Reutilization and Marketing Office	United States Marine Corps Marine Corps Logistics Base, Barstow Barstow, CA 92311-5013
Marine Depot Maintenance Command	United States Marine Corps Marine Corps Logistics Base, Barstow Barstow, CA 92311-5013
Fleet Support Division (FSD)	United States Marine Corps Marine Corps Logistics Base, Barstow Barstow, CA 92311-5013
Agencies	
State Historic Preservation Officer (SHPO)	Office of Historic Preservation, CA State Parks 1725 23rd Street, Suite 100 Sacramento, CA 95816 Phone: (916) 445-7000 POC: State Historic Preservation Officer Phone: 916-445-7000 Email: julianne.polanco@parks.ca.gov
Native American Heritage Commission (NAHC)	915 Capitol Mall, Room 364 Sacramento, CA 95814 Phone: (916) 373-3715 Email: nahc@nahc.ca.gov POC: Commissioner Phone: (916) 373-3712
Bureau of Land Management (BLM)	Barstow Field Office 2601 Barstow Road Barstow, CA 92311 Phone: (760) 252-6000
Advisory Council on Historic Preservation (ACHP)	1100 Pennsylvania Avenue NW, Suite 803 Old Post Office Building Washington, DC 20004 Phone: (202) 606-8503
City of Barstow, Planning Division	City Hall 220 E. Mountain View St, Suite A Barstow, CA 92311 Phone: (760) 255-5152
Federally Recognized Native American Tribes	
Chemehuevi Indian Tribe	PO Box 1976 Havasu Lake, CA 92363 Office: 760-858-4301 Fax: 760-858-5400 POC: Chairman

Table 2-6 List of External Stakeholders

<i>Name</i>	<i>Contact Information</i>
Colorado River Indian Tribes	26600 Mohave Road Parker, AZ 85344 Office: 928-669-9211 Fax: 928-669-1216 POC: Chairman
Fort Mojave Indian Tribe	AhaMaKav Cultural Society P.O. Box 5990 Mohave Valley, AZ 86440 Office: 928-768-4475 Fax: 928-768-7996 POC: Director
Fort Mojave Indian Tribe	500 Merriman Avenue Needles, CA 92363 Office: 760- 629-4591 Fax: 760 629-5767 POCs: Chairman Cultural Resources Coordinator
Morongio Band of Mission Indians	12700 Pumarra Road Banning, CA 92220 Office: (951) 849-4697 Fax: (951) 849-4425 POC: Chairman
San Manuel Band of Mission Indians	26569 Community Center Drive Highland, CA 92346 Office: 909-864-8933 Fax: 909-864-3770 POCs: Chairperson Director, CRM Department
Twentynine Palms Band of Mission Indians	46200 Harrison Place Coachella, CA 92236 Office: (760) 863-2444 POCs: Chairman Cultural Resource Manager

1 **2.6 TRIBAL CONSULTATION PROGRAM**

2 One of the most important steps in the project process is determining whether a project could
3 affect cultural resources valued by Native American groups. These resources may not be limited
4 solely to archaeological sites or artifacts, and such a determination must rely on past
5 consultations. When it appears that a proposed undertaking may affect Native American interests
6 or concerns, consultation should be initiated as soon as the project undertaking can be described.
7 Once the need for consultation has been established and the consulting partners for the project
8 identified, reasonable efforts should be taken to obtain information from the affected Native
9 American groups/individuals. Initial contact should be made with all interested Native American
10 parties by certified letter explaining the reason for the contact and containing a description of the
11 proposed project. SOP No. 1 provides a step-by-step process for consulting with Native
12 American groups, as well as a list of current Native American contacts. SOP No. 2 provides
13 guidance for the NAGPRA process.

14 **2.6.1 Status of Consultation**

15 Native American Consultation that has occurred between 2016 and 2020 is described below in
16 Table 2-7.

1

Table 2-7 Native American Consultation between 2016 and 2020

<i>Year</i>	<i>Description</i>
2016	MCLB Barstow sent notification letters to nine Native American tribes for consultation on Cultural Resources for Training and Range Environmental Assessment. Interests expressed by the San Manuel Band of Mission Indians about site CA-SBR-11840 being an archaeological resource of concern.
2017	MCLB Barstow sent notification letters to nine Native American tribes for consultation on the monitored excavation in support of the National Register eligibility of CA-SBR-11840 (prehistoric rock ring feature). The Colorado River Indian Tribes responded that they “do not have any specific comment on the proposed project and instead defer to the comments of other affiliated tribes.”
	MCLB Barstow sent notification letters to nine Native American tribes for consultation, requesting input on CA-SBR-11840 National Register of Historic Places Eligibility Evaluation. The Colorado River Indian Tribes responded, “given the potential impact of the project on important cultural resources, the Colorado River Indian Tribes request in-person government-to-government consultation. Please contact the Colorado River Indian Tribes THPO to discuss our concerns and schedule a meeting with Tribal Council.”
	MCLB Barstow sent notification letters to nine Native American tribes for consultation on BA17021 Demolition of Building 129. No responses have been received to date from any of the Native American groups contacted.
	MCLB Barstow sent notification letters to nine Native American tribes for consultation on BA17022 Demolition of Building 163. No responses have been received to date from any of the Native American groups contacted.
2018	MCLB Barstow sent notification letters to six Native American tribes for consultation on the United States Army Reserve 63D Readiness Division Equipment Concentration Site (ECS) Construction Project. The Chemehuevi Indian Tribe responded, “While we no longer have intimate daily contact with the specific area in question we do have grave concerns, but we would not oppose the project as presented.” The Twenty-Nine Palms Band of Mission Indians responded, “...THPO concurs with the finding of “No Historic Properties Affected.”
	MCLB Barstow sent notification letters to eight Native American tribes for Government-to-Government consultation introducing the new Commanding Officer. The Fort Mojave Indian Tribe and the Twenty-Nine Palms Band of Mission Indians sent comments.

1 **Table 2-7 Native American Consultation between 2016 and 2020 (continued)**

<i>Year</i>	<i>Description</i>
2019	MCLB Barstow sent notification letters to ten Native American tribes for Government-to-Government consultation introducing the new Cultural Resources Coordinator. The Fort Mojave Indian Tribe and the Twenty-Nine Palms Band of Mission Indians sent comments.
	MCLB Barstow sent notification letters to ten Native American tribes for consultation on the Graffiti Removal at CA-SBR-073 Rattlesnake Rock Petroglyph Site. The Morongo Band of Mission Indians responded, “We have no additional information to provide at this time.” The Fort Mojave Indian Tribe responded, “The Fort Mojave Indian Tribe, through AhaMaKav Cultural Society has evaluated your submission and agrees that the project as described will not adversely affect properties of cultural sacred significance to the Fort Mojave Indian Tribe. The findings of this Section 106 review resulted in a determination of No Adverse Effects.” The Twenty-Nine Palms Band of Mission Indians responded, “THPO is currently not aware of any additional impacts this project may have to CA-SBR-073. However, the THPO requests a completed cultural report for CA-SBR-073 and a shapefile of the site and Area of Potential Effects for the undertaking. Additionally, the THPO requests to be notified of the updates dates for the graffiti removal and the opportunity to visit the site prior to or during the removal process.”
	MCLB Barstow responded by emailing the Twenty-Nine Palms Band of Mission Indians an AMRDEC file of the Rattlesnake Rock (CA-SBR-73) Condition Assessment And Monitoring Report, a Non-Disclosure Agreement (NDA) for the GIS shapefile data and requested, persons or party information to provide them with passes to come aboard MCLB Barstow to access the CA-SBR-073 (Rattlesnake Rock) Petroglyph Site during the graffiti removal process. The Twenty-Nine Palms Band of Mission Indians responded by stating that they were going to check with the Chairman to see if he wanted them to come out for the graffiti removal. MCLB Barstow tried 2 more email attempts to confirm they received the report and to collect information needed to release the GIS data and provide them passes for the site visit. No other responses were received from the Twenty-Nine Palms Band of Mission Indians and no site visit during the graffiti removal was ever conducted.
	MCLB Barstow sent notification letters to ten Native American tribes for consultation on the Native American Consultation and Outreach work plan. Morongo Band of Mission Indians responded, “Regarding the above referenced project, we have no additional comments to provide at this time.”
2020	MCLB Barstow sent notification letters to ten Native American tribes to follow-up on the Graffiti Removal at CA-SBR-073 Rattlesnake Rock Petroglyph Site providing a final report. The Colorado River Indian Tribes responded, “given the potential impact of the project on important cultural resources, the Colorado River Indian Tribes request in-person government-to-government consultation. Please contact the Colorado River Indian Tribes THPO to discuss our concerns and schedule a meeting with Tribal Council.” The Fort Mojave Indian Tribe responded, “The Fort Mojave Indian Tribe, through AhaMakav Cultural Society has reviewed your submittal regarding the Graffiti Removal at CA-SBR-073 Rattlesnake Rock Petroglyph Site. ...From your report we are now aware that all painted inscriptions of graffiti have been removed from Rattlesnake Rock “leaving no damage done by the removal or any visible traces to the surface of the rock.” (letter January 7, 2020). The Morongo Band of Mission Indians responded, “Thank you for the final report on the Rattlesnake Rock site project and your agency’s restoration work.” The San Manuel Band of Mission Indians responded, “Thank you for sharing a copy of the report for the graffiti removal project at CA-SBR-073 (Rattlesnake Rock).”

1 **Table 2-7 Native American Consultation between 2016 and 2020 (continued)**

<i>Year</i>	<i>Description</i>
2020	MCLB Barstow sent notification letters to ten Native American tribes to follow-up on the Graffiti Removal at CA-SBR-073 Rattlesnake Rock Petroglyph Site providing a final report, along with a list of proposed project ideas that we requested their feedback on. The Fort Mojave Indian Tribe responded, “The Fort Mojave Indian Tribe, through AhaMaKav Cultural Society has evaluated your submission and agrees that the project as described will not adversely affect properties of cultural or sacred significance to the Fort Mojave Indian Tribe. The findings of this Section 106 review resulted in a determination of No Adverse Effects.” The San Manuel Band of Mission Indians responded, “I would like to emphasize our desire to continue to be a part of the management conversation for this resource and look forward to discussing these project ideas during our TBD meeting in April.”
	MCLB Barstow sent notification letters to eleven Native American tribes on the consultation on the Follow-up on Native American Consultation and Outreach, (face-to-face meeting). As previously stated, San Manuel Band of Mission Indians responded, “I would like to emphasize our desire to continue to be a part of the management conversation for this resource and look forward to discussing these project ideas during our TBD meeting in April.” A different point of contact from the San Manuel Band of Mission Indians also responded: “As of Monday, 2/10, I am now the Director of Cultural Resources Management for San Manuel Band of Mission Indians and I am interested in attending, on behalf of the Tribe, the proposed meeting in April 2020.” The Fort Mojave Indian Tribe responded, “...we have received your invitation for consultation and outreach regarding a meeting at your offices in April 2020. We appreciated the invitation and are very much interested in attending.”
	MCLB Barstow sent notification emails to eleven Native American tribes, inquiring dates for the Native American Consultation meeting. San Manuel Band of Mission Indians responded by providing dates they could attend the meeting.
	MCLB Barstow sent notification letters to eleven Native American tribes inviting them to the Native American Consultation meeting in April 2020.
	MCLB Barstow sent notification emails to eleven Native American tribes, inviting them to the Commanding Officer’s Complimentary Golf Tournament and Luncheon in April 2020. With responses from San Manuel Band of Mission Indians and the San Fernando Band of Mission Indians.
	MCLB Barstow sent notification emails to eleven Native American tribes, postponing the Native American Consultation meeting in April 2020, due to the COVID-19 pandemic. The San Manuel Band of Mission Indians responded, “I was wondering if we could try to schedule our consultation over WebEx instead.”
	MCLB Barstow responded, “We have put some thought into this and decided that we would like meet face-to-face for the initial consultation meeting. We are not absolutely confident that all tribes involved would be comfortable with a teleconference for the first initial consultation, and would not want to conduct a meeting if it troubled anyone by not being part of it. I hope you understand our reasoning for postponing this meeting. I will be in contact with you to reschedule this meeting as soon as day-to-day operations are back to normal.”
	MCLB Barstow sent notification emails to eleven Native American tribes, cancelling the Commanding Officer’s Complimentary Golf Tournament and Luncheon in April 2020, due to the COVID-19 pandemic.

Table 2-7 Native American Consultation between 2016 and 2020 (continued)

<i>Year</i>	<i>Description</i>
2020	MCLB Barstow sent notification emails to eleven Native American tribes introducing the new CRM and informing the tribes of our intent to welcome feedback on the ICRMP update and Native American Consultation project on July 16, 2020.

2.6.2 Ongoing CRM Responsibilities

Consultation and coordination shall be conducted openly and in good faith, through meetings, submittal of reports, email, phone conversations, and official correspondence. MCLB Barstow shall regularly update official POC prior to initiating consultation with all tribal governments who may have an interest in the matter (see Section 2.5).

Evidence of notification and consultation (or the failure of such efforts) are documented and maintained in the environmental documentation for projects. Consultation is narrowly focused on the proposed MCLB Barstow action to concentrate on specific description of the places and/or values that are at issue and potential management strategies to be used in order to avoid or minimize impacts to Native American cultural and religious values and practices.

2.7 CURATION

The CRM is responsible for the proper care of archaeological collections recovered from MCLB Barstow. This requires that archaeological collections be curated in facilities that meet the federal standards set forth in 36 CFR § 79, Curation of Federally Owned and Administered Archaeological Collections.

In November 2014, an MOU was established between Marine Air Ground Task Force Training Command (MAGTFTC), Marine Corps Air Ground Combat Center (MCAGCC), Twentynine Palms, California, and MCLB Barstow (Appendix E). The MOU states that MAGTFTC, MCAGCC will provide professional curatorial services in accordance with the standards set forth in 36 CFR § 79. This includes providing and maintaining a repository facility with proper equipment, space, and adequate safeguards for the security of all collections and associated records in the possession of MAGTFTC, MCAGCC. Annual inspections will also be conducted to ensure the physical integrity of all collections. Following the inspections, a status report will be sent to MCLB Barstow providing a current inventory of all collections and inspections as well as any treatments performed on the collections. SOP No. 3 provides an outline of MCLB Barstow's curation procedures. A copy of the MOU is provided in Appendix E of this ICRMP. As of this writing, MAGTFTC, MCAGCC holds one box of archaeological artifacts from MCLB Barstow, registered under Accession No. 2011.01.

2.8 INFORMATION RESTRICTIONS

To protect and preserve cultural resources at MCLB Barstow, resource locational data must be kept confidential. The location of cultural resources on federal lands is protected under Section 304 of the NHPA, and under Section 9 of the ARPA, which each provide authority to withhold information if public disclosure would result in a substantial risk of harm, theft, or destruction to the resource. Information regarding the specific location of cultural resources at MCLB Barstow

1 is considered confidential and is maintained as such by the CRM. Specific information regarding
2 archaeological sites and built environment resources should only be made available to project
3 planners on a “need to know” basis. Requests for resource location information from
4 professional archaeologists not under Navy contract, or from the general public, should be
5 referred to the SCCIC.

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1 **3.0 STANDARD OPERATING PROCEDURES**

2 The purpose of standard operating procedures (SOPs) for the management of cultural resources
3 at Marine Corps Logistics Base (MCLB) Barstow is to ensure that cultural resources policies,
4 plans, and strategies are properly implemented by creating step-by-step processes and
5 procedures. SOPs ultimately streamline the cultural resources compliance process by creating
6 uniformity and integrating cultural resources issues into the procedures of other installation
7 programs. SOPs should be disseminated, as appropriate, to all personnel, including internal
8 stakeholders, tenants, contractors, and other occasional users.

9 The following SOPs for cultural resources management at MCLB Barstow are detailed in the
10 pages that follow.

- 11 • SOP No. 1: Native American Consultation
- 12 • SOP No. 2: Native American Graves Protection and Repatriation Act Compliance
- 13 • SOP No. 3: Curation of Archaeological Collections
- 14 • SOP No. 4: Maintenance of Cemeteries, Memorials, and Monuments
- 15 • SOP No. 5: Treatment of National Register of Historic Places-eligible Resources
- 16 • SOP No. 6: Inadvertent Discovery of Cultural Resources
- 17 • SOP No. 7: Inadvertent Discovery of Human Remains
- 18 • SOP No. 8: Treatment of Traditional Cultural Properties and Sacred Sites

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3.1 STANDARD OPERATING PROCEDURE NO. 1: NATIVE AMERICAN CONSULTATION

Contact: Plans and Conservation Branch, Telephone: (760) 577-6744, 6888, 6318

Scope: This standard operating procedure (SOP) applies to communication with Native American groups/individuals regarding cultural resources management concerns and future undertakings. Federal requirements as well as Department of Defense (DoD) and Department of the Navy (DoN) policies define two primary aspects of consultation with Native Americans: (1) within government-to-government interactions related to the ownership, use, access, and disposal of properties of significance to Native Americans; and (2) as interested parties in consultation pursuant to the National Historic Preservation Act (NHPA) and National Environmental Policy Act (NEPA). To facilitate efficient consultation, a conciliatory relationship with tribal representatives should be established in advance of an undertaking requiring formal consultation. Per DoD Instruction 4710.02, Marine Corps Logistics Base Barstow will consult with appropriate Native American groups/individuals in these instances: land-disturbing activities, construction, training, over-flights, management of properties of traditional religious and cultural importance, protection of sacred sites from vandalism and other damage, access to sacred sites, access to treaty-reserved resources, disposition of cultural items, and land use decisions.

Consultation with Native Americans prior to the initiation of an undertaking serves as a valuable means of receiving ideas, advice, and additional information concerning the appropriate treatment of cultural resources. If human remains, funerary objects, sacred objects, or objects of cultural patrimony are found as the result of intentional excavation or inadvertent discovery on federal lands, the Native American Graves Protection and Repatriation Act (NAGPRA) requires Native American consultation (see SOP No. 2).

Legal Requirements, Standards, and Guidance:

- NHPA and associated regulation (36 Code of Federal Regulations [CFR] § 800)
- NEPA of 1969
- NAGPRA and associated regulation (43 CFR § 10)
- Archaeological Resources Protection Act (ARPA) and associated regulation (32 CFR § 229)
- Executive Order (EO) 13007, Indian Sacred Sites
- EO 13084, Consultation and Coordination with Indian Tribal Governments, May 14, 1998
- EO 13175, Consultation and Coordination with Indian Tribal Governments, November 6, 2000
- Executive Memorandum 1994, Government-to-Government Relations with Native American Tribal Governments
- Marine Corps Order (MCO) 5090.2A, Environmental Compliance and Protection Program, Volume 8, Cultural Resources Management
- DoD Instruction 4710.02, DoD Interactions with Federally Recognized Tribes
- DoD Instruction 4715.16, Cultural Resources Management

- 1 • DoD Policy 1998, Department of Defense American Indian and Alaska Native Policy
2 [Annotated]
- 3 • Secretary of the Navy Instruction 11010.14A, DoN Policy for Consultation with
4 Federally Recognized Indian Tribes

5 **Procedures:**

- 6 • The Cultural Resources Manager (CRM) will initiate government-to-government
7 consultation with the appropriate Native American groups/individuals (see Section 2.5) at
8 the conceptual phase of any undertaking requiring formal consultation. This initial letter
9 will include a description of the undertaking, a figure depicting the area of potential
10 effects (APE), and any known cultural resources within the APE. **MCLB Barstow**
11 **Commanding Officer will sign any correspondence to the Native American**
12 **groups/individuals.**
 - 13 ○ The CRM should make a good faith effort to consult with the Native American
14 community via letters, emails, and telephone calls, as appropriate.
 - 15 ○ Initial contact is made by in writing (certified letter recommended) explaining:
16 ▪ identification of the purpose of the letter;
17 ▪ identification of a MCLB Barstow contact person and how to reach him or
18 her;
19 ▪ a specific request for the kind of input needed;
20 ▪ the provision of an opportunity to meet in person; and
21 ▪ solicitation of the names and contact information of additional persons
22 who should be contacted regarding the project.
 - 23 ○ Additional information may also be requested, including:
24 ▪ referrals to appropriate consulting partners;
25 ▪ suggestions for dates and times to meet and discuss projects in person; and
26 ▪ documentation requests (i.e., mapping of sensitive areas).
 - 27 ○ Returned letters are followed by additional attempts at consultation.
 - 28 ○ Evidence of notification and consultation (or failure of such efforts) is
29 documented.
 - 30 ○ If consultation is refused or declined, MCLB Barstow's good faith effort has been
31 met.
 - 32 ○ Once decisions on undertakings are made, those consulted are notified of the
33 decision.
 - 34 ○ Invitation to site visits made via phone calls and email.
- 35 • The CRM will consult with appropriate Native American groups/individuals on the
36 discovery of pre-contact or historic Native American resources regarding their NRHP
37 eligibility assessment and treatment plans (if appropriate) within 30 days.
- 38 • MCLB Barstow will prepare an annual curation report, which summarizes the artifact
39 collections curated at Marine Corps Air Ground Combat Center (MCAGCC); this report
40 will be provided to appropriate Native American groups/individuals for their records.

3.2 STANDARD OPERATING PROCEDURE NO. 2: NATIVE AMERICAN GRAVES PROTECTION AND REPATRIATION ACT COMPLIANCE

Contact: Plans and Conservation Branch, Telephone: (760) 577-6744, 6888, 6318

Scope: This standard operating procedure (SOP) applies to human remains that can be culturally associated with a modern Native American group, and that are not identified as the remains of a historic settler, homicide victim, etc. The Native American Graves Protection and Repatriation Act (NAGPRA) provides a mechanism for determining the disposition of such human remains or cultural items.

Legal requirements, standards, and guidance:

- National Historic Preservation Act (NHPA) and associated regulation (36 Code of Federal Regulations [CFR] § 800)
- NAGPRA and associated regulation (43 CFR § 10)
- Archaeological Resources Protection Act (ARPA) and associated regulation (32 CFR § 229)
- Advisory Council on Historic Preservation (ACHP) Policy Statement Regarding Treatment of Burial Sites, Human Remains and Funerary Objects

Procedures:

- For all undertakings, human burials, marked or unmarked, shall be strictly avoided whenever possible.
- The Cultural Resources Manager (CRM) will then retain an appropriate cultural resources professional to evaluate the discovery.
- The CRM will determine whether an undertaking may result in the intentional excavation or inadvertent discovery of cultural resources. If the undertaking includes excavation or removal of NAGPRA–related items, an ARPA permit is required.
- If NAGPRA–related items are unexpectedly encountered, the California State Historic Preservation Officer (SHPO) should be informed by the CRM, and consultation with the appropriate Native American groups (see Section 2.5) should be initiated. The proposed undertaking must be reevaluated in relation to whether the remains can be avoided. If the remains cannot be avoided, then mitigation efforts must be explored in consultation with the tribes, archaeologists, and the base. All mitigation efforts must be in compliance with NAGPRA regulations.
- If there is no response to the written notification, tribes should be contacted by telephone.
- After consultation is complete, a written plan of action is prepared to include a description of the items of concern; the specific information used to determine their custody; planned treatment and handling; planned archaeological recording and analysis; and their planned disposition consistent with Section 106 of the NHPA.
- The plan of action is provided to the appropriate tribe/lineal descendants and signed.
- Prior to transfer of NAGPRA–related objects, a general notice of the proposed disposition is published twice (one week apart) in a newspaper with circulation that covers an area in which interested Native American parties currently reside. Transfer of the objects occurs at least 30 days after publication of the second notice.

- 1
 - 2
- MCLB Barstow may then transfer custody of the NAGPRA–related objects to the tribe with respect to traditional customs and practices of the affiliated tribes.

1 **3.3 STANDARD OPERATING PROCEDURE NO. 3: CURATION OF**
2 **ARCHAEOLOGICAL COLLECTIONS**

3 Contact: Plans and Conservation Branch, Telephone: (760) 577-6744, 6888, 6318

4 Scope: This standard operating procedure (SOP) applies to the curation of all archaeological
5 collections from sites at Marine Corps Logistics Base (MCLB) Barstow. It requires that all
6 archaeological collections be curated in facilities that meet the federal standards set forth in 36
7 Code of Federal Regulations [CFR] § 79, Curation of Federally Owned and Administered
8 Archaeological Collections. These procedures are intended to ensure that archaeological
9 collections are protected from external or climatic conditions, or any other factors that could
10 compromise their integrity. For the purposes of this SOP, collections are defined as material
11 remains that are excavated or removed during a survey, excavation, or other study of a
12 prehistoric or historic resource, and associated records that are prepared or assembled in
13 connection with the survey, excavation, or other study. Associated records are original records
14 (or copies thereof) that are prepared or assembled that document efforts to locate, evaluate,
15 record, study, preserve, or recover a prehistoric or historic resource.

16 The overall goal of the federal curation program is to ensure the integrity and accessibility of
17 cultural resources collections and documents for use by members of the public interested in the
18 archaeology and history of the region. All archaeological collections should be curated with
19 Marine Air Ground Task Force Training Command (MAGTFTC), Marine Corps Air Ground
20 Combat Center (MCAGCC), Twentynine Palms, California, per the provisions of a
21 Memorandum of Understanding (MOU) established between MAGTFTC, MCAGCC, and
22 MCLB Barstow dated November 2014 (Appendix E).

23 The MOU between MAGTFTC, MCAGCC, and MCLB Barstow states that artifact collections
24 will be stored at MCAGCC per 36 CFR § 79.6- “(1) When possible, the collection should be
25 deposited in a repository that: (i) Is in the State of origin; (ii) Stores and maintains other
26 collections from the same site or project location; or (iii) Houses collections from a similar
27 geographic region or cultural area. (2) The collection should not be subdivided and stored at
28 more than a single repository unless such subdivision is necessary to meet special storage,
29 conservation or research needs. (3) Except when non-federally-owned material remains are
30 retained and disposed of by the owner, material remains, and associated records should be
31 deposited in the same repository to maintain the integrity and research value of the collection.”

32 **Legal requirements, standards, and guidance:**

- 33 • National Historic Preservation Act (NHPA) and associated regulation (36 CFR § 800)
- 34 • 36 CFR § 79, Curation of Federally Owned and Administered Archeological Collections
- 35 • Marine Corps Order (MCO) 5090.2, Environmental Compliance and Protection Program,
36 Volume 8, Cultural Resources Management
- 37 • Department of Defense (DoD) Instruction 4715.16, Cultural Resources Management
- 38 • Memorandum of Agreement (MOA) between MAGTFTC, MCAGCC, and MCLB
39 Barstow (April 2011)

1 **Procedures:**

- 2 • Before permanent curation, all artifacts recovered at MCLB Barstow will be analyzed
3 using commonly accepted methods for artifacts in the region. Artifact analyses will be
4 consistent with current archaeological research objectives for the region.
- 5 • Cleaning and storage of artifacts and associated documents will meet professional
6 standards as set forth in 36 CFR § 79.
- 7 • Artifacts and associated documents will be stored in clean, spacious, temperature-
8 controlled facilities while on the installation and kept in archival-quality bags, folders, or
9 boxes.
- 10 • Contractors shall provide the Cultural Resources Manager at MCLB Barstow with copies
11 of all associated records, including site records, field notes, and a master artifact catalog.
- 12 • Archaeological materials will be submitted to MAGTFTC, MCAGCC for long-term
13 curation at MCLB Barstow’s expense in accordance with the MCAGCC Instructions for
14 Submission of Collections.
- 15 • MCLB Barstow will prepare an annual curation report, which summarizes the artifact
16 collections curated at MCAGCC; this report will be provided to appropriate Native
17 American groups/individuals for their records.

1 **3.4 STANDARD OPERATING PROCEDURE NO. 4: MAINTENANCE OF**
2 **CEMETERIES, MEMORIALS, AND MONUMENTS**

3 Contact: Plans and Conservation Branch, Telephone: (760) 577-6744, 6888, 6318

4 Scope: This standard operating procedure (SOP) applies to all memorials and cemeteries at
5 Marine Corps Logistics Base (MCLB) Barstow. Presently, there are no known Native American
6 cemeteries located at MCLB Barstow. A tomb and memorial of Walter P. Ross, a former
7 landowner of the area, is owned and maintained by S-3 Operations.

8 **Legal requirements, standards, and guidance:**

- 9 • National Historic Preservation Act (NHPA) and associated regulation (36 Code of
10 Federal Regulations [CFR] § 800)
- 11 • Archaeological Resources Protection Act (ARPA) and associated regulation (32 CFR §
12 229)
- 13 • Marine Corps Order (MCO) 5750.1H, Manual for the Marine Corps Historical Program

14 **Procedures:**

- 15 • Identified gravestones and memorial markers should be cleaned periodically to remove
16 accumulations of tree residue, road debris, bird droppings, etc.
- 17 • The landscaping should be kept neat and bushes and trees trimmed. A regular
18 maintenance schedule should be created to ensure that all gravesites and memorials look
19 well groomed.

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1 **3.5 STANDARD OPERATING PROCEDURE NO. 5: TREATMENT OF**
2 **NATIONAL REGISTER OF HISTORIC PLACES-ELIGIBLE**
3 **RESOURCES**

4 Contact: Plans and Conservation Branch, Telephone: (760) 577-6744, 6888, 6318

5 Scope: This standard operating procedure (SOP) applies to archaeological sites and historical
6 resources that have been determined eligible for inclusion in the National Register of Historic
7 Places (NRHP). These resources must be managed by Marine Corps Logistics Base (MCLB)
8 Barstow and adverse effects to such resources must be avoided or mitigated.

9 **Legal requirements, standards, and guidance:**

- 10 • National Historic Preservation Act (NHPA) and associated regulation (36 Code of
11 Federal Regulations [CFR] § 800)
- 12 • National Environmental Policy Act (NEPA) and associated regulation (40 CFR § 1500-
13 1508), Council on Environmental Quality, Regulations Implementing the Procedural
14 Provisions of NEPA
- 15 • 32 CFR § 60, NRHP
- 16 • 36 CFR § 61, Secretary of the Interior’s Historic Preservation Professional Qualifications
17 Standards
- 18 • 36 CFR §63, Determinations of Eligibility for Inclusion in the NRHP
- 19 • 36 CFR § 68, The Secretary of the Interior’s Standards for the Treatment of Historic
20 Properties
- 21 • Marine Corps Order (MCO) 5090.2, Environmental Compliance and Protection Program,
22 Volume 8, Cultural Resources Management
- 23 • Department of Defense (DoD) Instruction 4715.16, Cultural Resources Management
- 24 • Secretary of the Navy Instruction 4000.35A, DoN Cultural Resources Program

25 **Procedures:**

- 26 • Whenever possible, passive preservation of archaeological sites is the preferred
27 management approach. Where needed, fencing should be used to prevent damage to
28 archaeological sites of importance.
- 29 • Archaeological sites that have been determined eligible for inclusion in the NRHP should
30 be periodically monitored to ensure that the resources do not suffer from natural or
31 cultural degradation or destruction.
- 32 • Evaluate or avoid all sites determined eligible for inclusion in the NRHP.
- 33 • No construction, ground training, and/or range maintenance and sustainment activities
34 should occur within a 50-foot (15-meter) buffer zone and no aircraft training activities
35 would occur within a 350-foot (107-meter) buffer zone. Establishment of a buffer zone
36 would prevent impacts to sites.
- 37 • If adverse effects to NRHP-eligible resources cannot be avoided, as determined through
38 the Section 106 consultation process, a treatment plan must be developed in consultation
39 with the State Historic Preservation Office (SHPO) and Native American tribes (if
40 appropriate).

- 1 • For archaeological resources, data recovery (“salvage excavation”) is the common form
2 of mitigation for adverse effects. This requires a treatment plan that describes the site, the
3 kinds of information to be gained by the data recovery, study questions, sample design,
4 cataloging methods, special studies, and report preparation. Such a treatment plan and
5 any adverse effects are to be determined through consultation with appropriate Native
6 American groups/individuals. Other forms of mitigation could be decided upon during
7 Native American consultation. Archaeological data recoveries generally include site
8 mapping, controlled surface collection, controlled subsurface excavations, artifact
9 analyses and interpretations, report preparation, and artifact curation.
- 10 • Buildings and structures that have been determined eligible for inclusion in the NRHP
11 should have a Maintenance and Treatment Plan to guarantee their long-term preservation.
- 12 • For historic structures, Historic American Building Survey-level documentation typically
13 serves as a mitigation of adverse effects.
- 14 • For industrial historical resources, especially machinery, Historic American Engineering
15 Records documentation typically serves as a mitigation of adverse effects.
- 16 • Adverse effects to historical and cultural landscapes are mitigated using Historic
17 American Landscape Survey documentation.

1 **3.6 STANDARD OPERATING PROCEDURE NO. 6: INADVERTENT**
2 **DISCOVERY OF CULTURAL RESOURCES**

3 Contact: Plans and Conservation Branch, Telephone: (760) 577-6744, 6888, 6318

4 Scope: This standard operating procedure (SOP) applies to the inadvertent discovery of buried
5 cultural resources or historic properties during an undertaking and defines the necessary actions
6 that follow.

7 **Legal requirements, standards, and guidance:**

- 8 • National Historic Preservation Act (NHPA) and associated regulation (36 Code of
9 Federal Regulations [CFR] § 800)
- 10 • Archaeological Resources Protection Act (ARPA) and associated regulation (32 CFR §
11 229)
- 12 • Native American Graves Protections and Repatriation Act (NAGPRA) and associated
13 regulation (43 CFR § 10)
- 14 • Marine Corps Order (MCO) 5090.2, Environmental Compliance and Protection Program,
15 Volume 8, Cultural Resources Management
- 16 • MCO 5090.2 Volume 10, Environmental Restoration Program

17 **Procedures:**

18 If cultural resources are inadvertently discovered during an undertaking, including Installation
19 Recovery activities, the following procedures must be followed (more detailed procedures for
20 unanticipated discoveries are provided in Appendix C, The Discovery Treatment Plan):

- 21 • All ground-disturbing activities must stop in the immediate vicinity of the discovery and
22 the area must be protected from further disturbance.
- 23 • The Cultural Resources Manager (CRM) must be notified of the inadvertent discovery as
24 soon as possible, but no later than 3 working days after the initial discovery.
- 25 • The CRM will then retain an appropriate cultural resources professional to evaluate the
26 discovery and its eligibility for listing in the National Register of Historic Places
27 (NRHP).
- 28 • The CRM will notify and consult with the appropriate Native American
29 groups/individuals in the case of inadvertent discoveries within 3 working days. The
30 appropriate Native American groups/individuals must be notified by telephone with
31 written confirmation and must include information about the kinds of human remains,
32 associated funerary objects, unassociated funerary objects, sacred objects, or objects of
33 cultural patrimony, their condition, and the circumstances of their discovery. The
34 consulting Native American groups/individuals will respond to the CRM within 30 days
35 of the discovery notification. Following consultation, the Federal agency official must
36 prepare, approve, and sign a written plan of action. A copy of this plan of action must be
37 provided to the appropriate Native American groups/individuals involved (43 CFR § 10).
- 38 • If the discovery is found to be eligible for inclusion in the NRHP by the cultural
39 resources professional, its management must comply with Section 106 of the NHPA and
40 all processes therein.

- 1 • Those resources not meeting NRHP eligibility criteria require no further management
2 treatment, except under specific conditions in which construction monitoring has been
3 recommended.
- 4 • If the resources discovered are determined to be associated funerary objects with a
5 cultural affiliation, NAGPRA procedures will apply (see SOP No. 2).
- 6 • If an undertaking-specific Memorandum of Agreement (MOA) or relevant Programmatic
7 Agreement exists, the discovery is handled according to the procedures described therein.
- 8 • If the inadvertent discovery is determined to include human remains, then it will be
9 handled according to the Inadvertent Discovery of Human Remains procedures outlined
10 in SOP No. 7.
- 11 • If cultural resources are discovered in Installation Restoration Sites, the contractor and/or
12 personnel will comply with the guidelines in MCO 5090.2 Volume 10, Environmental
13 Restoration Program and California Supplement Section 6.
- 14

1 **3.7 STANDARD OPERATING PROCEDURE NO. 7: INADVERTENT**
2 **DISCOVERY OF HUMAN REMAINS**

3 Contact: Plans and Conservation Branch, Telephone: (760) 577-6744, 6888, 6318

4 Scope: This standard operating procedure (SOP) applies to the inadvertent discovery of human
5 remains at Marine Corps Logistics Base (MCLB) Barstow.

6 **Legal requirements, standards, and guidance:**

- 7 • National Historic Preservation Act (NHPA) and associated regulation (36 Code of
8 Federal Regulations [CFR] § 800)
- 9 • Archaeological Resources Protection Act (ARPA) and associated regulation (32 CFR §
10 229)
- 11 • Native American Graves Protections and Repatriation Act (NAGPRA) and associated
12 regulation (43 CFR § 10)
- 13 • Office of the Chief of Naval Operations Instruction 11170.2, Navy Responsibilities
14 Regarding Undocumented Human Burials and Cemeteries

15 **Procedures:**

16 If human remains are encountered at MCLB Barstow, the following procedures must be followed
17 (more detailed procedures for unanticipated discoveries are provided in Appendix C, Discovery
18 Treatment Plan):

- 19 • All work must cease in the immediate area of the discovery and the site must be protected
20 from further disturbance. The Cultural Resources Manager (CRM) and Commanding
21 Officer must be immediately notified of the discovery.
- 22 • The CRM will then retain an appropriate cultural resources professional to evaluate the
23 discovery.
- 24 • The Naval Criminal Investigation Service (NCIS) must then be notified. The NCIS may
25 handle investigation of the discovery or refer the case to the San Bernardino County
26 Coroner. The NCIS or the county coroner will then determine if the remains are part of a
27 recent crime scene or are archaeological in nature.
- 28 • If the remains are determined to be modern, then crime scene investigation procedures as
29 prescribed by the NCIS or county coroner will be followed. If the remains are
30 archaeological, the procedures for handling Native American and non-Native American
31 human remains outlined below must be followed.
- 32 • If the human remains are determined to be of Native American ancestry, NAGPRA
33 procedures as codified in 43 CFR § 10.4 must be followed (see SOP No. 2).
- 34 • If human remains are discovered that are not of Native American ancestry, MCLB
35 Barstow will follow the procedures outlined in Office of the Chief of Naval Operations
36 Instruction 11170.2, Navy Responsibilities Regarding Undocumented Human Burials and
37 Cemeteries.

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1 **3.8 STANDARD OPERATING PROCEDURE NO. 8: TREATMENT OF**
2 **TRADITIONAL CULTURAL PROPERTIES AND SACRED SITES**

3 Contact: Plans and Conservation Branch, Telephone: (760) 577-6744, 6888, 6318

4 Scope: This standard operating procedure (SOP) applies to the treatment of traditional cultural
5 properties (TCPs) and sacred sites at Marine Corps Logistics Base (MCLB) Barstow. These
6 resources must be managed by MCLB Barstow and adverse effects to such resources must be
7 avoided or mitigated. A TCP can include archaeological resources, buildings, neighborhoods,
8 prominent topographic features, habitats, plants, animals, and minerals that American Indians or
9 other groups consider essential for the continuance of traditional cultures. A TCP is defined as
10 one of these resources that is eligible for inclusion in the National Register of Historic Places
11 (NRHP) because of its association with cultural practices or beliefs of a living community that
12 are rooted in that community’s history, and are important in maintaining the continuing cultural
13 identity of the community. Per Executive Order (EO) 13007, Indian Sacred Sites, a sacred site is
14 defined as “any specific, discrete, narrowly delineated location on Federal land that is identified
15 by an Indian tribe, or Indian individual determined to be an appropriately authoritative
16 representative of an Indian religion, as sacred by virtue of its established religious significance
17 to, or ceremonial use by, an Indian religion; provided that the tribe or appropriately authoritative
18 representative of an Indian religion has informed the agency of the existence of such a site.” Per
19 Department of Defense (DoD) Instruction 4710.02, MCLB Barstow will consult with appropriate
20 Native American groups/individuals regarding the management of properties of traditional
21 religious and cultural importance, protection of sacred sites from vandalism and other damage,
22 access to sacred sites, and access to treaty-reserved resources.

23 **Legal requirements, standards, and guidance:**

- 24 • National Historic Preservation Act (NHPA) and associated regulation (36 Code of
25 Federal Regulations [CFR] § 800)
- 26 • Native American Graves Protection and Repatriation Act (NAGPRA) and associated
27 regulation (43 CFR §10)
- 28 • EO 13007, Indian Sacred Sites
- 29 • EO 13175, Consultation and Coordination with Indian Tribal Governments
- 30 • Religious Freedom Restoration Act
- 31 • American Indian Religious Freedom Act
- 32 • 2012 Sacred Sites Inter-Agency Memorandum of Understanding
- 33 • National Park Service Bulletin 38, Guidelines for Evaluating and Documenting
34 Traditional Cultural Properties

35 **Procedures:**

- 36 • Whenever possible, passive preservation of TCPs and sacred sites is the preferred
37 management approach.
- 38 • Avoid harming TCPs and sacred sites; develop buffer zones around TCPs and sacred
39 sites that will be avoided in planning (and all) stages of projects and protect locations
40 from inadvertent impacts.

- 1 • TCPs and sacred sites should be periodically monitored to ensure that the resources do
2 not suffer from natural or cultural degradation or destruction.
- 3 • MCLB Barstow shall maintain the confidentiality of TCPs and sacred site locations.
- 4 • Develop use agreements with Tribes for TCPs and sacred sites used to gather traditional
5 products, plants, and animals and agreements for co-management and joint stewardship
6 of Sacred Land.

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Appendix A. Environmental and Historic Context

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1 **A-1 HISTORICAL CONTEXT**

2 **A-1.1 Environmental Context**

3 **A-1.1.1 Installation Location**

4 Marine Corps Logistics Base (MCLB) Barstow is located just east of the city of Barstow in San
5 Bernardino County, California (Figure A-1). The base is made up of three distinct components:
6 the Nebo Area (1,285 acres), the Yermo Annex (1,691 acres), and the Rifle Range (2,458 acres).
7 The base is near the junction of two major interstate highways, Interstate (I-) 15 and I-40. State
8 highways 58 and 247 enter Barstow west of the base, and historic Route 66 (National Old Trails
9 Road) runs directly through the Nebo Area, where it is called Joseph Boll Avenue. The Burlington
10 Northern and Santa Fe (BNSF) Railway crosses the northern section of the Nebo Area, and a rail
11 spur east of Daggett runs along the eastern side of the Yermo Annex. The railroad and right-of-
12 way are owned by the Atchison, Topeka, and Santa Fe (ATSF) Railroad Company (Parcels 0424-
13 161-59-0000, 0424-161-61-0000, 0424-171-32-0000) and are not included in the MCLB Barstow
14 boundary. Base Headquarters is located in the Nebo Area, along with the main facilities for
15 administration, storage, housing, shopping, and recreational activities. The Yermo Annex serves
16 primarily as a storage, maintenance, and industrial complex. The Rifle Range provides Marines
17 with facilities for small arms training. Altogether, MCLB Barstow comprises approximately
18 5,434 acres (Figure A-2).

19 **A-1.1.2 Geological Setting**

20 MCLB Barstow is located in the north-central portion of the Mojave Desert in eastern California,
21 a region surrounded by mountains and fault lines, including the San Andreas Fault to the
22 southwest and the Garlock Fault to the north (Schoenherr 1992:13). Two 1993 studies specifically
23 addressed the geologic features in an area that includes the Yermo Annex (Cox and Wilshire
24 1993a) as well as the Nebo Area complex and the Rifle Range (Cox and Wilshire 1993b). Five
25 faults of the Camp Rock-Harper Lake system run through the Nebo Area and the Rifle Range,
26 including one fault that is believed to be active (Cox and Wilshire 1993b:2-4). The geology of
27 the region is complex: the underlying material consists of sandstone, shale, and gravel deposits
28 from the Pliocene (5.3–1.8 million years before present [MYBP]) and/or Pleistocene (1.64–0.01
29 MYBP) epochs. Tertiary (65–1.64 MYBP) volcanic flow rocks, Mesozoic (248–65 MYBP)
30 volcanic and metavolcanic rocks, and granitics are also present in the region (Jennings 1977;
31 Figure A-3).

32 **A-1.1.3 Soils and Topography**

33 Soils near the MCLB Barstow are mostly alluvial, unconsolidated sediments consisting of sand,
34 silt, and gravel. The topography is characterized by low ridges and terraces dissected by shallow
35 braided washes. The topography slopes generally northward to the Mojave River. Portions of the
36 terraces and low ridges on the base are covered by desert varnish. The presence of desert varnish
37 is indicative of surface exposure and weathering. Although no precise measure has been
38 established for dating these materials, it is known that thousands of years are needed for the
39 varnish to accrete (Dorn 2004). On the Rifle Range portion of MCLB Barstow, there are large
40 numbers of cryptocrystalline nodules in addition to significant areas of desert varnish.

Figure A-1. MCLB Barstow Vicinity Map

Figure A-2. MCLB Barstow Location Map

Figure A-3. MCLB Barstow Geologic Map

The surficial geology of the Yermo Annex has been mapped in detail by Cox and Wilshire (1993a). The area consists primarily of Holocene to Pleistocene unconsolidated sand and gravels, as is commonly found throughout the western Mojave Valley (Cox and Wilshire 1993a). In the southeast portion of the Yermo Annex, a variety of other sediments are found, primarily younger Holocene alluvium in the form of sand bars and low stream terraces, Holocene colluvium formed as a result of erosion, and older Holocene alluvium consisting of sand and gravel units draping stream terraces (Cox and Wilshire 1993a). Small areas of Holocene sand dunes and playa deposits are also present (Cox and Wilshire 1993a). It should be noted that a single outcrop of Miocene Elephant Mountain rhyodacite is present along Agate Road to the southeast of 21st Street (Cox and Wilshire 1993a). This formation consists of a porphyritic biotite-hornblende rhyodacite that forms extrusive (domes) and shallow-intrusive (plugs) bodies, primarily at Elephant Mountain (Cox and Wilshire 1993a). Andesite and rhyodacite have been used as a base for petroglyphs and quarried for use as milling stones elsewhere in the Mojave Desert (Schneider et al. 1995).

The surficial geology of the Nebo Area and Rifle Range has been mapped in detail by Cox and Wilshire (1993b). In the Nebo Area, the majority of the surface has been disturbed. However, to the northeast, the surface consists primarily of Holocene alluvium from the Mojave River with small amounts of Holocene to Pleistocene undissected alluvial fan deposits. The far northeastern corner of the Nebo Area contains the edge of Elephant Mountain and presents a complex mix of Holocene alluvial sediments and Miocene volcanics (intrusive basalts) and sandstones. The southeastern portion of the Nebo area is composed primarily of Holocene to Pleistocene undissected alluvial fan deposits without much desert varnish, with lesser amounts of active Holocene alluvium, moderately dissected Pleistocene alluvium, and heavily dissected gravel and conglomerate from possibly Pleistocene to Miocene alluvial fans. These heavily dissected old alluvial fan sediments make up the majority of the surficial geology of the Rifle Range. This area is heavily crossed with erosional features that contain predominantly Holocene to Pleistocene alluvial deposits with varying degrees of desert varnish (Cox and Wilshire 1993b).

A.1.1.4 Surface Hydrology

The region's major hydrologic feature is the Mojave River (Figure A-4). Its headwaters are to the west in the San Bernardino Mountains. Surface water rarely flows in the river east of Victorville, but water travels underground, beneath the sand and gravel. The river traverses MCLB Barstow approximately 0.7 mile north of the Rifle Range and is directly adjacent to the northern portion of the Nebo Area. A small northeastern part of the Nebo Area includes a portion of the riverbed. The channel is generally dry in this area, except for brief periods during the rainy season.

A.1.1.5 Climate

The area is extremely arid during the entire year, averaging fewer than 5 inches of rain annually. Although it can happen in any month, most rainfall occurs between December and March. Even then, the average monthly total rarely exceeds 1 inch of precipitation. During the summer months, widely scattered torrential thunderstorms can occur. The high temperatures range from approximately 60 degrees Fahrenheit (°F) in the winter months to well above 100°F during the warmest summer months of June through September. However, during the winter nights, temperatures occasionally may drop below freezing. Snow is rare, but it has been known to occur, most often during December or January (Western Regional Climate Center 2004).

Figure A-4. MCLB Barstow Hydrologic Map

1 A.1.1.6 Vegetation and Wildlife

2 The vegetation community is best characterized as creosote bush scrub consisting of creosote bush
 3 (*Larrea tridentata*), white bursage (*Ambrosia dumosa*), Indian or Mormon tea (*Ephedra*
 4 *nevadensis*), yucca (*Yucca schidigera*), Russian thistle (*Salsola tragus*), nonnative grasses
 5 (*Schismus* spp.) and various cactus species (Barbour and Major 1988:837; Manley 1996). Sensitive
 6 wildlife species with potential to occur in the area include desert tortoise (*Gopherus agassigii*),
 7 burrowing owl (*Athene cunicularia*), and loggerhead shrike (*Lanius ludovicianus*). Other wildlife
 8 species known to occur in the area includes black-tailed jackrabbit (*Lepus californicus*), coyote
 9 (*Canis latrans*), common raven (*Corvus corax*), house finch (*Carpodacus mexicanus*), mourning
 10 dove (*Zenaida macroura*), yellow-rumped warbler (*Dendroica coronata*), and Anna's
 11 hummingbird (*Calypte anna*), along with rodents, snakes, and lizards (Harrison 1979; Reid 2006).

12 A-2 CULTURAL CONTEXT

13 A-2.1 Prehistoric Overview

14 The prehistory of southern California is varied and rich, encompassing a period of more than
 15 12,000 years. Numerous chronological sequences have been devised to explicate cultural changes
 16 for various areas in southern California over the past 75 years (Moratto 2004). This prehistoric
 17 overview is structured using the latest Mojave Desert culture history (Sutton et al. 2007). The
 18 framework is thus divided into four major periods: Pleistocene, early Holocene, middle Holocene,
 19 and late Holocene (Table A-1).

20 **Table A-1. Mojave Desert Chronology**

<i>Temporal Period</i>	<i>Cultural Complex or Period</i>	<i>Approximate Dates</i>	<i>Marker Artifact</i>
Pleistocene	Pre-Clovis (hypothetical)	Pre-10,000 cal. B.C.	Unclear
	Paleoindian	10,000–8000 cal. B.C.	Fluted points (Clovis)
Early Holocene	Lake Mojave	8000–6000 cal. B.C.	Stemmed points (Lake Mojave, Silver Lake)
Middle Holocene	Pinto		
Late Holocene	Gypsum	2000 cal. B.C.–cal A.D. 200	Gypsum and Elko Series points
	Rose Spring	cal. A.D. 200–1100	Rose Spring and Eastgate Series points
	Late Prehistoric	cal. A.D. 1100–Contact	Desert Series points, ceramics

Source: Sutton et al. 2007:236.

21 A-2.1.1 Paleoindian Period (ca. 10,000–8000 Before Christ [B.C.])

22 A firm date for the initial human occupation of the Mojave Desert has not yet been established.
 23 Although there have been several controversial claims of Pleistocene-age (pre-Clovis) finds such
 24 as the Early Man Site of Calico Hills (Leakey et al. 1968, 1972), most archaeologists remain

1 unconvinced by the available Mojave Desert data. The growing acceptance of evidence for pre-
2 Clovis occupations elsewhere in the Western Hemisphere suggests the possibility that such
3 evidence may yet be found in this region as well.

4 The earliest broadly accepted cultural complex in the Mojave Desert is the Clovis Complex (Sutton
5 et al. 2007:233). The hallmark artifacts of this complex are large lanceolate-shaped bifaces with
6 distinctive fluting used to thin and flatten the base for hafting (Justice 2002:73). Paleoindian
7 populations associated with fluted point technology consisted of small, mobile groups that hunted
8 and gathered near permanent sources of water such as pluvial lakes.

9 There is some doubt as to whether the Clovis Complex had a temporally or geographically
10 extensive presence in the Mojave Desert. Fluted points have traditionally been interpreted as tools
11 used for hunting Pleistocene megafauna due to their clear association with megafaunal remains in
12 the American Southwest, but most fluted points found in California have been recovered as
13 isolated surface finds without confirmed Pleistocene radiocarbon dates (Arnold 2004).

14 **A-2.1.2 The Early Holocene (8000–6000 B.C.)**

15 The communities that lived in the Mojave Desert witnessed and were profoundly affected by great
16 environmental changes during the gradual Pleistocene-Holocene transition. Temperatures became
17 warmer but remained cooler and moister than today’s climate. The Mojave Desert of the early
18 Holocene was marked by shallow lakes and marshes that were biologically very productive.
19 Warmer temperatures, reduced precipitation, and the eventual dehydration of the pluvial lakes are
20 believed to have led to irregularities in the distribution and abundance of resources. These climatic
21 changes created the need for a more diversified subsistence strategy; the archaeological pattern
22 associated with this adaptation is known as the Lake Mojave Complex (Sutton et al. 2007:237).

23 Named for a Pleistocene lake in southern California, the Lake Mojave Complex is recognized by
24 the heavy, stemmed projectile points of the Great Basin Stemmed Series, such as Lake Mojave
25 and Silver Lake. Other tools include bifaces, steep-edged unifaces, crescents, the occasional
26 cobble-core tool, and, rarely, ground stone implements (Justice 2002:91). This toolkit represents
27 a generalized adaptation to highly variable terrain (Justice 2002:116).

28 The changing climate, distribution of occupational sites, and the all-terrain toolkit suggest that the
29 inhabitants of the Mojave Desert during the early Holocene developed a broad-ranging subsistence
30 strategy based on patterns of “intensive environmental monitoring” (Sutton et al. 2007:237). These
31 people monitored the seasons and moved in the direction of known resource patches.

32 **A-2.1.3 The Middle Holocene (7000–3000 B.C.)**

33 The middle Holocene climate, although more arid than periods before and after, was still highly
34 variable, with multiple oscillations between wetter and drier conditions occurring throughout. In
35 addition, although the lakes and marshes of the early Holocene dried up, streams and springs in
36 the Mojave Desert may have still maintained water flow from nearby ranges, at various times and
37 places, providing suitable water sources to sustain human activity, albeit at low densities (Aikens
38 1978; Basgall 2000; Cleland and Spaulding 1992; Sutton 1996; Warren 1984). Between 7000 and
39 5000 B.C., temperatures appear to have risen, and aridity appears to have increased, peaking
40 between 6000 and 5000 B.C. Lowland ephemeral lakes and streams began to dry up, and
41 vegetation communities capable of supporting large game animals became limited to a few isolated
42 contexts. Settlement patterns adapted, shifting to upland settings where sources of water still

1 existed (Sutton 1996). This land-use change also correlated with adjustments in tool assemblage
2 content and diversity, resulting in the emergence of the Pinto Complex.

3 Originally defined by Campbell and Campbell (1935), the Pinto Complex appears to represent
4 shifts in subsistence patterns and adaptations, with greater emphasis placed on the exploitation of
5 plants, as well as a continued focus on artiodactyls and smaller animals. It had a wider distribution
6 throughout the Mojave Desert than the previous complexes. The pan-desert nature of the complex
7 suggests that it represents a settlement system with a high degree of residential mobility. The
8 distinctive characteristics of the Pinto Complex toolkit—as defined by Justice (2002:126) and
9 Zyniecki (2003:12)—include “indented base and bifurcate base projectile points with robust basal
10 ears and weak shoulders.”

11 Near the end of the middle Holocene, the climate became hotter and drier, marked by a period of
12 “cultural hiatus” between 3000 and 2000 B.C. During this gap there appears to have been little to
13 no human occupation in much of the Mojave (Sutton et al. 2007:241).

14 **A-2.1.4 The Late Holocene (2000 B.C.–Contact)**

15 The climate of the prehistoric late Holocene approximates that of today, with cooler and moister
16 conditions than the middle Holocene but not as cool and moist as the early Holocene. At least two
17 major droughts are thought to have occurred within the Sierras (Stine 1994), at ca. Anno Domini
18 (A.D.) 892 to 1112, and ca. A.D. 1209 to 1350. This was followed by a cooler and wetter period
19 between 600 and 150 years ago (Cleland and Spaulding 1992:4). People returned to the region,
20 and human subsistence strategies, compared to previous settlement behavior, changed
21 significantly. This subsistence strategy correlated with adjustments in artifact/tool assemblage
22 content and diversity, resulting in the emergence of the Gypsum Complex.

23 The Gypsum Complex is characterized by dart-point-size projectile points in notched or eared
24 (Elko), concave-base (Humboldt), and small-stemmed (Gypsum) forms. In addition to diagnostic
25 projectile points, Gypsum Complex sites consist of leaf-shaped points, rectangular-based knives,
26 flake scrapers, T-shaped drills, and, occasionally, large scraper planes, choppers, and
27 hammerstones (Warren 1984:416). Manos and milling stones are common, and the mortar and
28 pestle were also introduced during this period. Other artifacts associated with this complex include
29 split-twig animal figurines, *Olivella* sp. shell beads, and *Haliotis* sp. beads and ornaments.

30 By A.D. 200, the climate had become slightly cooler. Population size appears to have increased,
31 as evidenced by a higher frequency of archaeological sites. This period in California prehistory
32 is marked by the Rose Spring Complex, an archaeological pattern associated with a timeframe
33 known as the Saratoga Springs period, Haiwee period, or Amargosa period, depending on the
34 region (Sutton 1996; Sutton et al. 2007:236). By the onset of this period at A.D. 200, dart-point-
35 size projectile points were being replaced with smaller Rose Spring projectile points, signaling
36 the introduction of the bow and arrow (Yohe 1998).

37 Generally speaking, archaeological evidence left by highly mobile hunter-gatherers in the Mojave
38 Desert most often takes the form of sparse scatters of flaked stone, ground stone, and ceramic
39 artifacts and features such as hearths, rock rings, and trails. These remains represent resource
40 extraction and processing sites as well as short-term encampments. Repeated use of specific
41 locations may result in more diverse and substantial archaeological deposits.

1 A-2.2 Ethnographic Overview

2 Ethnographic boundaries in the Mojave Desert are loosely defined because of the highly mobile
3 nature of desert settlement strategies and the variety of alternatives presented by previous
4 researchers. According to available ethnographic maps (Bean and Smith 1978:570; Kroeber 1925;
5 Sutton et al. 2007:232), MCLB Barstow falls within the traditional territory of the Desert Serrano
6 people, and is situated south of the Kawaiisu, east of the Kitanemuk, and west of the Chemehuevi
7 or Southern Paiute.

8 By the mid-1700s, the Spanish had begun their colonization of the California coast. At this time,
9 California was occupied by native populations who spoke Takic and Numic languages, branches
10 of the Uto-Aztecan language family (Mithun 2006:539, 543). Serrano, a language in the division
11 of the Takic branch, was spoken in the areas of the southern Antelope Valley, along the Mojave
12 River, and around the San Bernardino Mountains. The central and western Mojave Desert region
13 may have acted as a boundary between native Californian Takic-speaking groups and Numic-
14 speaking groups with links to the Great Basin (Earle 2019).

15 Serrano territory was a trade nexus between inland tribes and coastal tribes. Although the Serrano
16 language group controlled a large geographic range and significant travel corridors, their villages
17 were politically autonomous, and they were not a unified tribe with a common political leadership
18 (Earle 2019). Based on regional alliances, distinct names such as “Beñemé” (Vanyumé) and
19 “Jenigueche” (Hanyuveche) were given by the Mojave to distinguish Serrano residents of the
20 Mojave River. Though early explorers believed these were separate groups, new scholarship
21 reveals that they were divisions within a single ethnic group. (Kroeber 1925; Sutton and Earle
22 2017; Earle 2019).

23 The subsistence economy of the Serrano was one of hunting and collecting plant goods, with
24 occasional fishing carried out (Bean and Smith 1978:571). Trade and exchange was an important
25 aspect of the Serrano economy. Those living in the lower-elevation desert floor villages traded
26 foodstuffs with people living in the foothill villages who had access to a different variety of edible
27 resources. The Mojave River was especially important as a travel and trade corridor between the
28 Southwest and southern California (Earle 2005). “It is known that Mojave River villages
29 maintained large stores of Pacific Coast shell beads, presumably as a result of their hosting
30 Mojave shell bead traders” (Earle 2019: 13). Acorns, pinyon pine nuts, and juniper berries were
31 also transported down the river. According to Spanish and Mexican era travel accounts and
32 mission records, and from 20th century ethnographic information, names and approximate
33 locations of several Mojave River Serrano villages are known. These villages were relatively
34 small in population, some populated by sixty to eighty people or more (Earle 2019).

35 Contact between Serrano and Europeans was relatively minimal prior to the early 1800s. As early
36 as 1790, however, Serrano were drawn into mission life (Bean and Vane 2002). Military
37 campaigns sought to move village populations to missions San Gabriel and San Fernando in 1810
38 (Earle 2019). Most of the remaining western Serrano were moved to an *asistencia* built near
39 Redlands in 1819 (Bean and Smith 1978:573). Some explorers, such as Jedidah Smith, observed
40 small numbers of Desert Serrano living near the Mojave River in the late 1820s (Earle 2019).
41 However, by 1834, most western Serrano had been moved to the missions, with some Serrano
42 possibly moved to the mission at San Fernando Rey (Kroeber 1908). Only small groups of
43 Serrano remained in the area northeast of the San Gorgonio Pass and were able to preserve some
44 of their native culture (Earle 2019).

1 **A-2.3 Historic Overview**

2 **A-2.3.1 Spanish Period (1769–1822)**

3 In the course of a 1769 overland expedition, Captain Gaspar de Portolá established the Presidio
4 of San Diego, a fortified military outpost, as the first Spanish settlement in Alta California. Also,
5 in July of 1769, Franciscan Father Junípera Serra founded Mission San Diego de Alcalá, the first
6 of the 21 missions that would be established in Alta California by the Spanish and the Franciscan
7 Order between 1769 and 1823.

8 Although Pedro Fages traveled near the Cajon Pass as early as 1772, the first known Spanish
9 explorer to enter the area that would become San Bernardino County was Father Francisco
10 Garcés, traveling from the Colorado River in 1776 (Hoover et al. 2002:321). The San Bernardino
11 Valley was named in 1810 by the Franciscan missionary Francisco Dumetz, who led a party from
12 the San Gabriel Mission into the valley in observance of the Feast of St. Bernardine of Siena.

13 The 21 missions paralleled the California coastline between San Diego and Sonoma. Near-coastal
14 locations were preferred by the Spaniards for colonization because they were easier to defend and
15 supply from ships and were also bordered by populous Native American villages with potential
16 converts. Although present-day San Bernardino County did not formally host Spanish missions,
17 the region remained connected to the California presidio and mission system through the
18 Franciscan rancho and *asistencia* outposts. Near today's city of Redlands in San Bernardino
19 County, the San Bernardino de Sena Estancia (also known as the San Bernardino Rancho) was
20 established in 1819 for grazing cattle owned by the Mission San Gabriel Arcángel.

21 **A-2.3.2 Mexican Period (1822–1848)**

22 After more than a decade of intermittent rebellion and warfare, New Spain (Mexico and the
23 California territory) won independence from Spain in 1821. The influence of the California
24 missions waned in the late 1820s through the early 1830s, and as a consequence, extensive land
25 grants in the interior were initiated in the Mexican period, in part to entice populations away from
26 the more settled coastal areas where the Spanish had concentrated their colonization efforts.
27 Following adoption of the Secularization Act of 1833, the Mexican government privatized most
28 Franciscan lands, including holdings of their California missions. By 1836, this sweeping process
29 effectively reduced the California missions to parish churches and released their vast
30 landholdings. The vast mission lands and livestock holdings were redistributed by the Mexican
31 government through several hundred land grants to private, non-Native American ranchers
32 (Langum 1987:15– 18).

33 During the Mexican period, the large ranchos became important economic and social centers.
34 Some 20 ranchos covering nearly 500,000 acres were granted in northwestern Riverside and
35 southwestern San Bernardino counties. These included Ranchos El Rincón and Jurupa, which
36 straddled both of today's counties; and Cucamonga, Santa Ana, and San Bernardino in San
37 Bernardino County.

38 **A-2.3.3 American Period (1848–Present)**

39 The Mexican-American War ended with the Treaty of Guadalupe Hidalgo, signed in 1848,
40 ushering California into its American period. Horticulture and livestock, based primarily on cattle
41 as the currency and staple of the rancho system, continued to dominate the southern California
42 economy through the first decade of the Gold Rush beginning in 1848. California attained
43 statehood with the Compromise of 1850. San Bernardino County was organized from parts of

1 Los Angeles and San Diego counties in April 1853, and the city of San Bernardino became the
2 county seat in 1854.

3 During the Gold Rush, thousands of people traveled the Gila Trail or Southern Overland Trail
4 from Texas to Arizona, then crossed the Colorado River at present-day Yuma into California and
5 proceeded across the Colorado Desert to the San José Valley. Thousands traveled the Mojave
6 River Trail, named the Old Spanish Trail by Captain John C. Frémont in 1844.

7 As miners and settlers began to occupy the Mojave River valley, U.S. Army forts were established
8 to protect them and keep the trail open as the Mohave Indians periodically attacked homesteads
9 and wagon trains. Railroad surveyors first visited the area in the 1850s, but it was not until 1868,
10 after the Civil War, that congressional approval was given for a railroad charter (McCoy
11 1994:114–116). The ATSF Railroad and the Southern Pacific Railroad (SPRR) began building
12 lines in the early 1880s. The SPRR had already reached the extreme southwest corner of San
13 Bernardino County in 1876. The Atlantic and Pacific Railroad (later the ATSF and currently the
14 BNSF) soon crossed the central part of the county, the Southern California Railway linked
15 Barstow to San Diego in 1885, and San Bernardino was connected to the eastern states in 1887
16 via the AT&SF through Barstow and Needles. The railroad activity led to the establishment of
17 Barstow in 1885, and the town continued to grow with additional rail lines and later the
18 establishment of the interstate highway system in the 1920s and 1930s (McCoy 1994:155; Oxsen
19 1994:111).

20 In the late 1800s, the development of a new city between Daggett and Newberry was proposed.
21 The development was predicated on using Mojave River water to supply agricultural and
22 industrial endeavors. Although all the plans for the city of Minneola ultimately failed, 11 miles
23 of the proposed canal were completed. The canal (CA-SBR-7883H) ran from the vicinity of
24 MCLB Barstow to Daggett (Salisbury and Van Dyke 1976:37–38). The possibility exists that
25 there was a 1919 extension of the canal onto MCLB Barstow (Thompson 1929) has not been
26 verified to date.

27 The Cajon Pass-Barstow-Needles route established by the Southern California Railway and the
28 AT&SF led the way for the first highways across the Mojave Desert. The Ocean-to-Ocean
29 Highway was established in 1912 and stretched from Baltimore, Maryland, to California, and is
30 now known as the National Old Trails Road (Cassity et al. 2012). The route across the California
31 deserts followed the Mojave River/Old Spanish Trail through Needles and Barstow to San
32 Bernardino. Established in 1926, most of U.S. Route 66 largely followed the Ocean-to-Ocean
33 Highway, passing through the desert region south of Needles on its way across the country to Los
34 Angeles. After U.S. Route 66 was decommissioned in 1985, parts of it became I-40 as well as I-
35 15. Remains of the route in several western states, including California, have been designated a
36 National Trails Highway.

37 **A-2.4 History of MCLB Barstow**

38 The section below was developed using JRP Historical Consulting's (JRP) 2011 *Historic*
39 *Resources Inventory and Evaluation Update*.

40 With the onset of World War II in 1939, the United States increased military funding and began
41 to develop and expand new and existing facilities. To meet this demand, the Navy's Bureau of
42 Yards and Docks developed a set of standardized plans that provided for the efficient construction
43 of temporary facilities, bases, and buildings. This type of construction is commonly referred to

1 as World War II temporary and was utilized because of wartime shortages of time, manpower,
2 and materials.

3 As the military's personnel and facilities rapidly expanded, so did a demand for additional
4 supplies and logistical support. In 1940, the Navy only had two continental Naval Supply Depots
5 and two small Marine Corps Depots, which procured, stored, and delivered materials to individual
6 installations. As a result, the Navy began a campaign to develop a number of new depots in
7 remote inland locations with standardized plans and new palletizing and forklift storage systems.

8 Barstow was chosen as the site of a new depot because of its proximity to existing roads and
9 highways, and a dry climate that allowed for outdoor storage. Congress authorized construction
10 of the new depot on May 8, 1942 and contacted James T. Holmes and D. Lee Narver's Los
11 Angeles engineering firm to design and construct the new supply depot. Prior to construction,
12 naval engineers addressed concerns over flooding from the Mojave River by constructing a series
13 of culverts. Other preliminary considerations included the development of wells and provision of
14 electricity through lines run along highway and railroad rights-of-way.

15 Holmes and Narver began working on plans in June 1942 with construction beginning in
16 September of the same year. In late 1942, the Navy made the decision to transfer the supply depot
17 to the Marine Corps. The new supply depot was officially activated on January 4, 1943 and would
18 continue to develop into the following months. Throughout the rest of World War II, MCLB
19 Barstow supported the war effort by providing supply and warehouse functions.

20 After World War II, MCLB Barstow grew in size and expanded the scope of its operations.
21 Equipment that was damaged during the war was repaired, and new equipment was added. In
22 1946, MCLB Barstow was re-designated as the Marine Corps Storage and Repair Depot
23 (MCSRDP) in response to the installation's new function. By April 1946, the Navy was looking
24 to expand MCSRDP by acquiring a nearby World War II Army post known as U.S. Army
25 Quartermaster Depot at Yermo. After successful negotiations in July 1946, the United States
26 Marine Corps (USMC) officially moved into the Yermo facility.

27 During the early post-war period, new residential units and storage facilities were added to the
28 base. A 1947 housing project constructed 100 family apartments for both civilian and military
29 personnel, 44 apartments for officers and enlisted personnel, 20 dormitory units for women, and
30 30 dormitory units for men. As the population of installation personnel grew, the number of
31 Morale, Welfare, and Recreation facilities, medical facilities, and civilian-operated businesses
32 increased. Along with this growth came the addition and upgrade of storage and repair facilities.

33 In March 1948, the installation's official designation was changed to Marine Corps Depot of
34 Supplies, Barstow. The installation was now composed of two separate areas: the original
35 location, known as the Nebo Area, and the newly acquired Yermo Annex. In response to a labor
36 shortage on base, the USMC pushed for the recruitment of Navajo Indians to fill the labor gap.
37 In March 1949, the installation was re-designated Barstow Annex, Marine Corps Depot of
38 Supplies, San Francisco. By this time, the base had grown to accommodate more than 1,200
39 personnel. In response, Commanding Officer Colonel Chester R. Allen looked to the Wherry
40 Housing program under Title VIII of the National Housing Act for a solution to the housing
41 shortage.

42 Throughout the Korean Conflict (1950–1953), the installation performed the same supply
43 function as it did during World War II, with the addition of the new Yermo repair facility. During

1 the conflict, the installation was able to expand its capabilities, upgrading existing systems and
 2 adding new storage and housing projects. The base now served the USMC in the western United
 3 States, overseas forces, provided storage for the California National Guard 140th Heavy Tank
 4 Battalion, and conducted automotive maintenance for the Army at Camp Irwin.

5 In the mid-1950s, the San Francisco depot was phased out and its functions transferred to
 6 Barstow. From 1958 on, MCLB Barstow was responsible for all USMC logistics west of the
 7 Mississippi River, as well as the Pacific and Far East. These new responsibilities led to further
 8 expansion of the base with the acquisition of the Rifle Range along Highway 66. During this
 9 time, MCLB Barstow constructed a repair facility building at Yermo (Building 573), which
 10 became the largest single-story workspace ever constructed for the USMC, covering 10 acres and
 11 equipped with several cranes to repair and service equipment. This new repair facility elevated
 12 the installation's level of support during the Vietnam War, continuing to expand throughout the
 13 1960s and 1970s.

14 In November 1978, the installation was given its current name, MCLB Barstow. MCLB Barstow
 15 would go on to have an active support role following Iraq's invasion of Kuwait in 1990, providing
 16 Marines stationed in Saudi Arabia with thousands of tons of supplies. Between 2004 and 2005,
 17 MCLB Barstow was faced with the possibility of a base closure or substantial reduction after
 18 Congress called for base closures across the United States. Despite this congressional action,
 19 MCLB Barstow managed to remain open and is currently one of the Barstow region's largest
 20 employers.

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Appendix B. Previously Conducted Surveys and Previously Recorded Sites

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1 **B-1 METHODOLOGY**

2 This appendix presents details for previously recorded cultural resources and previously conducted
3 cultural resources studies conducted at Marine Corps Logistics Base (MLCB), Barstow. This
4 appendix combines information taken from the 2016 Integrated Cultural Resources Management
5 Plan (ICRMP) with additional studies completed between 2016 and 2020. Maps of these sites and
6 studies are also presented here. The geospatial data presented here were created by digitizing the
7 maps located in the 2016 ICRMP

8 Because most of the survey areas and resource locations were not acquired directly from a global
9 positioning system (GPS) device, there is some error in the accuracy of the site and study
10 boundaries. Additionally, several of the cultural resources studies were built environment surveys
11 that did not utilize intensive pedestrian survey transect methods, and at least one archaeological
12 survey employed sample survey methods. Thus, while the entirety of MLCB Barstow has been
13 subjected to previous cultural resources studies, less than 100 percent of the property has been
14 covered by intensive pedestrian archaeological survey methods. These limitations should be
15 considered when consulting for a proposed project.

16 **B-2 PREVIOUS CULTURAL RESOURCES INVESTIGATIONS**

17 **Cultural Resources Inventory Survey (Manley 1996)**

18 *Report No. 1063519*

19 This survey addressed archaeological and built resources in all three areas of MCLB Barstow.
20 Approximately 1,050 acres at Nebo and 875 acres at Yermo were surveyed by vehicle (windshield
21 survey) with stops for pedestrian inspection. The areas of pedestrian inspection were not described.
22 An additional 160 acres in the far northeast and south of the Yermo Annex were not surveyed for
23 cultural resources, nor was a 30-acre section in the northeastern portion of the Nebo Area. In the
24 remaining areas of the base, pedestrian surveys were carried out in intervals that ranged from 20
25 to 40 meters. One previously recorded archaeological site (CA-SBR-73) was reexamined and the
26 site record was updated. Three previously unrecorded archaeological sites (CA-SBR-8317, -8318,
27 and -8319) were also recorded. The archaeological component of the investigation identified and
28 described the cultural resources as part of an inventory. However, the built environment
29 component of this study included evaluation of 115 buildings and structures built before 1950
30 (primarily World War II resources). None of the built resources were found to be eligible for
31 inclusion in the NRHP, either individually or as part a district (Widell 1997).

32 **Cold War Era Historic Resources Eligibility Survey (Manley 1999)**

33 *Report No. 1064561*

34 The investigation consisted of a National Register of Historic Places (NRHP) eligibility survey of
35 627 buildings and structures, most of which were constructed during the Cold War Era (1946 to
36 1989). The inventory and evaluation addressed built resources located on the base and included
37 on-site recordation and archival research. Thirty-seven properties mentioned in the report
38 (sidewalks, roadways, parking lots, and underground utilities) were not formerly recorded on State

1 of California Department of Parks and Recreation (DPR) Series 523 forms. Twenty-eight of the
2 properties had been inventoried in 1996 (Manley 1996). None of the built environment resources
3 were found to be eligible for inclusion in the NRHP, either as a district or individually. The State
4 Historic Preservation Office (SHPO) concurred with this finding in 2000 (see correspondence in
5 Appendix C, letter USMC000203A).

6 **Final Cultural Resources Survey of 250 Acres on the Western Edge and Proposed**
7 **Fence Line for the Rifle Range and Reevaluation of a Portion of CA-SBR-8318**
8 **(Berryman and Bull 2003)**

9 ***Report No. 1064559***

10 This intensive cultural resources survey included approximately 250 acres on the western edge of
11 the Rifle Range as well as the proposed fence line along the southern edge of the Rifle Range, and
12 reevaluated the southern portion of the extensive lithic scatter site designated as CA-SBR-8318.
13 The survey resulted in the identification of eight sites and 12 isolates within this portion of
14 CA-SBR-8313. All the sites were described as low-density lithic scatters. In addition, a remnant
15 of a possible historic trail was identified and recorded as CA-SBR-11296/H.

16 **Final Archaeological Survey Report of the Western Portion of the Rifle Range**
17 **(Berryman and Cheever 2003)**

18 ***Report No. 1064560***

19 This study consisted of an intensive cultural resources survey of approximately 200 acres on the
20 western edge of the Rifle Range to locate and document previously unknown cultural resources
21 sites, features, and isolates. Berryman and Cheever identified 18 previously unrecorded cultural
22 resources (archaeological sites) during this survey. The report was sent to the SHPO, but
23 concurrence on the evaluation results was not requested (Mellon 2004).

24 **Archaeological Survey of the Northern Portion of CA-SBR-8318 (Willey et al. 2005)**

25 ***Report No. 1065410***

26 This intensive archaeological survey of approximately 250 acres in the Rifle Range included the
27 northern part of site CA-SBR-8318 (previously identified by Berryman and Cheever in 2003).
28 Willey et al. divided the site into 22 smaller entities: 15 lithic scatters with flaking stations and
29 seven isolates. Willey et al. expanded the boundaries of three sites previously identified by
30 Berryman and Cheever (2003) and Berryman and Bull (2003).

31 **Final: A Phase I Cultural Resources Inventory of 37 Acres at Lot 505, Yermo Annex**
32 **(Hale et al. 2009)**

33 ***Report No. 1066663***

34 This study consisted of an intensive archaeological survey of approximately 37 acres at Lot 505
35 in the Yermo Annex in support of plans to use the lot for equipment storage. Hale et al. identified
36 and recorded one historic archaeological site (CA-SBR-13385). No previously recorded sites were
37 located in the survey area.

1 **Final: A Station-Wide Cultural Resources Survey at MCLB Barstow (Daniels et al.**
2 **2011)**

3 *Report No. Not Available*

4 This study consisted of the intensive archaeological survey of approximately 182 acres in the
5 Yermo Complex, recordation of two previously identified historic resources located in the Nebo
6 Area (Well 1 and Well 2), and a survey of selected portions of the Rifle Range (totaling 244 acres)
7 to determine whether previous surveys had overlooked archaeological deposits. The pedestrian
8 survey of the Yermo complex resulted in the identification and recordation of three isolated finds,
9 whereas the Rifle Range survey resulted in identification and recordation of four archaeological
10 sites and two isolated finds.

11 **Technical Synthesis Report: Intensive Archaeological Survey for Barstow Training**
12 **and Range Environmental Assessment, Marine Corps Logistics Base Barstow, San**
13 **Bernardino County, California (Bryne 2015)**

14 *Report No. Not Available*

15 The study consisted of the intensive archaeological survey of approximately 1,061.5 acres MCLB
16 Barstow that had not been recently surveyed. A total of 26 newly recorded archaeological sites and
17 116 locations of isolated artifacts were identified, and 17 previously recorded archaeological sites
18 were revisited. A single spire-lopped bead was identified during a desert tortoise survey which
19 overlapped with the boundaries of CA-SBR-73. Based on a photograph of the bead in the site
20 record, it appears to be an *Olivella dama* spire-lopped bead.

21 The study concluded that, one of the newly identified archaeological sites (CA-SBR-29325,
22 temporary number MCLB-SITE-7, a rock ring) is recommended as potentially eligible for
23 inclusion in the NRHP. Of the 17 previously recorded sites, three prehistoric sites including CA-
24 SBR-73 (Rattlesnake Rock Petroglyph), CA-SBR-8319 (Sleeping Circles), and CA-SBR-11840
25 (Prehistoric Rock Ring) are potentially eligible for inclusion in the NRHP. The remaining 14
26 previously recorded sites were recommended ineligible for inclusion in the NRHP.

27 **Rattlesnake Rock (CA-SBR-73) Condition Assessment and Monitoring Report**
28 **Marine Corps Logistics Base Barstow, California (Millington et al. 2016)**

29 *Report No. Not Available*

30 The scope of this work included: (1) formal documentation of the archaeological assemblage
31 surrounding the fenced rock outcrop at CA-SBR-73; (2) photo documentation of the petroglyph
32 panels and analysis of the images after post-processing with DStretch software; (3) the compilation
33 of historical records for comparison with current conditions, facilitating assessment of impacts to
34 the integrity of the site over time. Archival documents, historical photographs, and other published
35 background material were obtained through the San Bernardino County Museum and various
36 Internet sources; (4) sketching and photo documentation of the rock art panels; (5) an update to
37 the DPR 523 Form for CA-SBR-73; and (6) an update to the National Register Nomination Form.
38 In addition to initial site documentation fieldwork, SWCA conducted quarterly visits to CA-SBR-

1 73—in May, August, and November of 2014 and February of 2015—to detect any seasonal
2 changes and inform management recommendations with regard to site accessibility and risks to
3 the integrity of the site and included the results of these observations in this report.

4 **Historic Resources Survey and Evaluation Report, CA-SBR-2910H and CA-SBR-**
5 **3033/H, Marine Corps Logistics Base, Barstow, California (Treffers et al. 2016)**

6 *Report No. Not Available*

7 This study conducted a historic resources survey in an effort to identify, record, and evaluate the
8 NRHP eligibility of segments of two linear resources: the National Old Trails Highway (CA-SBR-
9 2910H [P-36-002910]) and the Mojave Trail (CA-SBR- 3033/H [P-36-003033]). This study
10 determined that the segment of the National Old Trails Road/U.S. Highway 66 (CA-SBR-2910H)
11 that traverses MCLB Barstow appears eligible for inclusion in the NRHP under Criterion A for its
12 direct and important associations with the development of strategic defense highways during
13 World War II. As such, it is defined as a *historic property* in National Historic Preservation Act
14 16 United States Code 470 (w)(5). Although historical maps indicate that the trail traversed the
15 Yermo Annex of MCLB Barstow, the current study was unable to locate segments of CA-SBR-
16 3033/H.

17 **National Register of Historic Places Evaluation of CA-SBR-11840, Marine Corps**
18 **Logistics Base, Barstow, California (Byerly and Byrd 2018)**

19 *Report No. Not Available*

20 This report was a NRHP evaluation of CA-SBR-11840, located at MCLB in Barstow, California.
21 This was intended to support efforts to finalize National Environmental Policy Act (NEPA)
22 requirements to complete the Barstow Training and Range Environmental Assessment. Testing
23 and evaluation fieldwork of this rock ring site took place in November 2017. A total of 0.14 cubic
24 meters of sediment was excavated and sifted from two shovel test probes. No subsurface cultural
25 material was recovered, and an ancient pre-cultural duripan was encountered between 25 and 30
26 centimeters below surface. A battered flaked felsite cobble/core tool was recorded and left *in situ*
27 on the surface, and this is the only artifact observed in association with the rock ring. The site was
28 recommended ineligible for NRHP listing under Criteria A through D. The proposed action, which
29 included the construction of a nearby Simulated Flight Deck, would not constitute a significant
30 archaeological impact to the resource.

31 **Final Graffiti Removal at CA-SBR-73 (Rattlesnake Rock) Petroglyph Site for**
32 **Marine Corps Logistics Base Barstow, San Bernardino County, California**
33 **(Loubser and Becker 2019)**

34 *Report No. Not Available*

35 This report described how the painted white enamel graffiti from five panels was removed at CA-
36 SBR-73 (Rattlesnake Rock) Petroglyph Site on MCLB Barstow. The report also documented the
37 condition assessment of the graffiti, its rock support, and a description of the white paint graffiti's
38 removal. This project was in support of the MCLB Barstow and Navy's plans to conduct Native

- 1 American outreach and consultation with those tribes interested in the cultural resources
- 2 throughout MCLB Barstow.
- 3
- 4

Table B-1. Previous Cultural Resources Studies Conducted at MCLB Barstow

SBAIC Report Number	Author(s) and Year	Document Title	Relationship to MCLB Barstow	MCLB Barstow Area
1062369	Lindgreen 1887	<i>The Silver Mines of Calico, California</i>	Overview	—
1060052	Smith et al. 1961	<i>Indian Picture Writing of San Bernardino and Riverside Counties</i>	Overview	—
1060070	Prewett 1966	<i>Manix Lake Problems: An Alternate View</i>	Overview	—
1060078	Walker 1967	<i>Life and Adventure Along the Mojave River Trail</i>	Overview	Yermo
1062147	Heizer 1973	<i>Prehistoric Rock Art of California</i>	Overview	—
1062550	Glennan 1976	<i>The Manix Lake Lithic Industry: Early Lithic Tradition or Workshop Refuse?</i>	Overview	—
1062549	Meighan 1976	<i>Two Views of the Manix Lake Lithic Industry</i>	Overview	—
1062551	Simpson 1976	<i>A Commentary on W. Glennan's Article</i>	Overview	—
1060700	Hearn 1978	<i>Archaeological - Historical Resources Assessment of Portions of Sections 1, 2, and 11 (T9N R1E), Yermo Area</i>	In	Yermo
1062164	Bean et al. 1979	<i>Lucerne Valley Project: Ethnographic and Historical Resources</i>	Overview	—
1060891	Stickel 1980	<i>An Overview of the Cultural Resources of the Western Mojave Desert</i>	Overview	—
1060937	Sutton 1980	<i>Cultural Resource Assessment - CA-060-MPO-7, Nebo Area</i>	In	Rifle Range
1062370	Harthrong 1983	<i>Renewed Mining Activity in the Calico Mountains: A Report on the Asarco-Waterloo Project</i>	Overview	—
1062280	Bamforth and Dorn 1988	<i>On the Nature and Antiquity of the Manix Lake Industry</i>	Overview	—
1061820	Peak and Associates 1988	<i>Cultural Resource Survey and Clearance for Re-Routed Portions of the Proposed American Telephone and Telegraph Las Vegas to San Bernardino Fiber Optics Communication Route</i>	In	Nebo
1062233	Clay and Hause 1990	<i>An Archaeological Inventory of Two Proposed PG&E Pipeline Corridor Segments: Newberry Springs to Hinkley, 29.6 Mi. by 200 Ft. (717.6 AC), San Bernardino County, California and Arvin to Kern River 25.2 Mi. by 200 Ft. (610.9 AC), Kern County, California</i>	In	Nebo; Rifle Range
1062388	McGuire 1990	<i>A Cultural Resources Inventory and Limited Evaluation of the Proposed Mojave Pipeline Corridor in California and Arizona</i>	In	Rifle Range
1066504	Lerch 1994	<i>Class III Cultural Resources Inventory of the Mojave River Pipeline Project, Phelan to Minneola, San Bernardino County, California</i>	In	Nebo
1063022	McKenna and Williams 1994	<i>Pioneer Mojave Settlers: Pioneer Settler List of the Mojave River 1862-1880 and Miscellaneous Entries from the San Bernardino County Tax Assessor Rolls</i>	Overview	—
1063519	Manley 1996	<i>Cultural Resources Inventory Survey, Marine Corps Logistics Base Barstow, California</i>	In	Nebo; Rifle Range; Yermo
1064561	Manley 1999	<i>Cold War Era Historic Resources Eligibility Survey, Marine Corps Logistics Base, Barstow, California</i>	In	Nebo; Rifle Range; Yermo
N/A	McCarthy and Manley 2000	<i>(Draft) National Register of Historic Places Nomination: Rattlesnake Rock (SBR-73) Petroglyph Site, Marine Corps Logistic Base, Barstow, California</i>	In	Yermo
1064213	Schmidt 2000	<i>Bug 33 kV Transmission Line, San Bernardino County</i>	In	Yermo
1066134	Blair et al. 2001	<i>Cultural Resources Class I and Class III Investigations for the Proposed 2003 Kern River Expansion Project California</i>	In	Rifle Range
1066336	Molenaar et al. 2002	<i>The 2003 Kern River Expansion Project: Native American Consultation and Identification of Traditional Cultural Places</i>	In	Rifle Range

Table B-1. Previous Cultural Resources Studies Conducted at MCLB Barstow

SBAIC Report Number	Author(s) and Year	Document Title	Relationship to MCLB Barstow	MCLB Barstow Area
1064559	Berryman and Bull 2003	<i>Final Cultural Resources Survey of 250 Acres on the Western Edge and Proposed Fence Line for the Rifle Range and Reevaluation of a Portion of CA-SBR-8318, Marine Corps Logistics Base, Barstow, California</i>	In	Rifle Range
1064560	Berryman and Cheever 2003	<i>Final Archaeological Survey Report for the Western Portion of the Rifle Range, Marine Corps Logistics Base, Barstow, California</i>	In	Rifle Range
1064234	Earle 2004	<i>Ethnohistorical and Ethnographic Overview and Cultural Affiliation Study of the Fort Irwin Region and Central Mojave Desert</i>	Overview	—
1064848	Wise and Way 2004	<i>Final Cultural Resource Survey of One Workstation on the Mule Canyon 33kV Circuit, Southern California Edison Deteriorated Pole Replacement Program, Marine Corps Supply Center, Naval Reserve, Yermo, San Bernardino County, California</i>	In	Yermo
1065411	McKenna et al. 2005	<i>Results of a Class III Archaeological Survey for the Proposed Materials Testing Locations at the Service Rock Products/BLM Exchange Project Area Near Barstow, San Bernardino Co., California</i>	In	Rifle Range
1065410	Willey et al. 2005	<i>Survey Report for a Portion of the Rifle Range at Marine Corps Logistics Base, Barstow, California</i>	In	Rifle Range
1066293	Dougherty 2008	<i>Cultural Resources Inventory of United States Army Reserve 63D Regional Support Command Yermo Annex Project, San Bernardino County, California</i>	In	Yermo
1066663	Hale et al. 2009	<i>Final: A Phase I Cultural Resources Inventory of 37 Acres at Lot 505, Yermo Annex, MCLB Barstow</i>	In	Yermo
N/A	Daniels et al. 2011	<i>Draft: A Station-Wide Cultural Resources Survey at MCLB Barstow, San Bernardino County, California</i>	In	Station-wide
N/A	Bryne 2015	<i>Final Technical Synthesis Report for Intensive Archaeological Surveys for Barstow Training and Range Environmental Assessment, Marine Corps Logistics Base Barstow, San Bernardino County, California</i>	In	Yermo
N/A	Millington et al. 2016	<i>Rattlesnake Rock (CA-SBR-73) Condition Assessment and Monitoring Report Marine Corps Logistics Base Barstow, California</i>	In	Yermo
N/A	Treffers et al. 2016	<i>Historic Resources Survey and Evaluation Report, CA-SBR-2910H and CA-SBR-3033/H, Marine Corps Logistics Base, Barstow, California</i>	In	Yermo, Nebo
N/A	Byerly and Byrd 2018	<i>Final National Register of Historic Places Evaluation of CA-SBR-11840, Marine Corps Logistics Base, Barstow California. Technical report submitted by Far Western to Leidos Engineering, Inc., Carpinteria, California, to Naval Facilities Engineering Command, Southwest, San Diego, California. Contract N62470-15-D-8005, Task Order FZ03. May.</i>	In	Nebo
N/A	Loubser and Becker 2019	<i>Final Graffiti Removal at CA-SBR-73 (Rattlesnake Rock) Petroglyph Site for Marine Corps Logistics Base Barstow, San Bernardino County, California. Prepared by Stratum Unlimited LLC and ASM Affiliates for Naval Facilities Engineering Command Southwest. October.</i>	In	Yermo

Figure B-1. Previously Conducted Cultural Resources Surveys

Figure B-2. Previously Conducted Cultural Resources Surveys

Table B-2. Previously Recorded Archaeological Resources at MCLB Barstow

<i>Primary Number</i>	<i>Trinomial</i>	<i>Resource Description</i>	<i>Temporary Number or Other Designation</i>	<i>NRHP Eligibility</i>	<i>Recorded by and Year</i>	<i>MCLB Barstow Area</i>
<i>Archaeological Sites</i>						
P-36-000073	CA-SBR-73	Multi-component; Prehistoric: Rattlesnake Rock: Petroglyphs, lithic scatter; Historic: trash scatter/dump	CPHI, SBR-040	Eligible, nomination draft updated in 2016	Mallery 1889; Crossman 1890; Steward 1929; Smith 1939, 1941, 1967; Bierman and Mohr 1949; Mohr 1949; Haenszel 1968, 1977; Heizer and Clewlow 1973; Manley 1996; McCarthy and Manley 2000; Bryne 2015; Millington et al. 2016	Yermo
P-36-010910	CA-SBR-1910H	Historic: Union Pacific Railroad	--	Ineligible	Hanks 1976; Becker 1991; Neuenschwander 1997; Sander and Auck 2008; White 2001; Harry Reid Center for Environmental Studies 2002	Nebo
P-36-002910	CA-SBR-2910H	Historic: Route 66/National Old Trails Road	--	Eligible	Gallegos 1977; Berg, F. 1978; Van Buren 1986; Berg, G. 1989; Lerch 1990; Petersen 1991; Becker and Phillips 1993; Glover et al. 1993; Rafferty 1993; White 1993; Bricker 1994; Goodman et al. 2000; Underwood and Rose 2000; Dietler et al. 2001; Wedding 2001; Applied Earthworks 2004; EDAW 2004; LSA 2005; Caltrans 2006; Walters 2007; Erickson 2008; McLean 2008; McDougall 2009; Treffers et al. 2016	Nebo
P-36-003033	CA-SBR-3033/H	Historic: Mojave Trail/Old Government Road	CHL SBR-963	Not evaluated	Hanks 1975; Unknown 1976; Haenszel 1986; Bell et al. 1988; Neuenschwander 1997; Wedding 2001; Applied Earthworks 2007; Treffers et al. 2016	Yermo
P-36-008317	CA-SBR-8317	Prehistoric: Lithic scatter	--	Not evaluated	Manley 1996	Nebo
P-36-008318	CA-SBR-8318	Prehistoric: Lithic scatter	--	Not evaluated	Manley 1996; Berryman and Bull 2003; Willey et al. 2005;	Rifle Range
P-36-008319	CA-SBR-8319	Prehistoric: Rock rings	--	Recommended potentially eligible	Manley 1996; Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
P-36-010663	CA-SBR-10663	Prehistoric: Lithic scatter	--	Recommended not eligible	Berryman and Cheever 2003; Willey et al. 2005	Rifle Range
P-36-010664	CA-SBR-10664	Prehistoric: Lithic scatter	--	Not evaluated	Berryman and Cheever 2003	Rifle Range
P-36-010665	CA-SBR-10665	Prehistoric: Lithic scatter	--	Not evaluated	Berryman and Cheever 2003	Rifle Range

Table B-2. Previously Recorded Archaeological Resources at MCLB Barstow

<i>Primary Number</i>	<i>Trinomial</i>	<i>Resource Description</i>	<i>Temporary Number or Other Designation</i>	<i>NRHP Eligibility</i>	<i>Recorded by and Year</i>	<i>MCLB Barstow Area</i>
P-36-010666	CA-SBR-10666	Prehistoric: Lithic scatter	--	Not evaluated	Berryman and Cheever 2003	Rifle Range
P-36-010667	CA-SBR-10667	Prehistoric: Lithic scatter	--	Not evaluated	Berryman and Cheever 2003	Rifle Range
P-36-010668	CA-SBR-10668	Prehistoric: Lithic scatter	--	Not evaluated	Berryman and Cheever 2003	Rifle Range
P-36-010669	CA-SBR-10669	Prehistoric: Lithic scatter	--	Not evaluated	Berryman and Cheever 2003	Rifle Range
P-36-010670	CA-SBR-10670	Prehistoric: Lithic scatter	--	Not evaluated	Berryman and Cheever 2003	Rifle Range
P-36-010671	CA-SBR-10671	Prehistoric: Lithic scatter	--	Not evaluated	Berryman and Cheever 2003	Rifle Range
P-36-010672	CA-SBR-10672	Prehistoric: Lithic scatter	--	Not evaluated	Berryman and Cheever 2003	Rifle Range
P-36-010673	CA-SBR-10673	Historic: Trail segment	--	Not evaluated	Berryman and Cheever 2003	Rifle Range
P-36-010674	CA-SBR-10674	Prehistoric: Lithic scatter	--	Not evaluated	Berryman and Cheever 2003	Rifle Range
P-36-010675	CA-SBR-10675	Prehistoric: Lithic scatter	--	Not evaluated	Berryman and Cheever 2003	Rifle Range
P-36-010676	CA-SBR-10676	Prehistoric: Lithic scatter	--	Not evaluated	Berryman and Cheever 2003	Rifle Range
P-36-010677	CA-SBR-10677	Prehistoric: Lithic scatter	--	Not evaluated	Berryman and Cheever 2003	Rifle Range
P-36-010678	CA-SBR-10678	Prehistoric: Lithic scatter	--	Not evaluated	Berryman and Cheever 2003	Rifle Range
P-36-010679	CA-SBR-10679	Prehistoric: Lithic scatter	--	Not evaluated	Berryman and Cheever 2003	Rifle Range
P-36-010680	CA-SBR-10680	Prehistoric: Lithic scatter	--	Not evaluated	Berryman and Cheever 2003	Rifle Range
P-36-011294	CA-SBR-11294	Prehistoric: Lithic scatter	--	Recommended not eligible	Berryman and Bull 2003	Rifle Range
P-36-011295	CA-SBR-11295	Prehistoric: Lithic scatter	--	Recommended not eligible	Berryman and Bull 2003	Rifle Range
P-36-011296	CA-SBR-11296/H	Historic: Trail segment	--	Recommended not eligible	Berryman and Bull 2003	Rifle Range
P-36-011297	CA-SBR-11297	Prehistoric: Lithic scatter	--	Recommended not eligible	Berryman and Bull 2003	Rifle Range

Table B-2. Previously Recorded Archaeological Resources at MCLB Barstow

<i>Primary Number</i>	<i>Trinomial</i>	<i>Resource Description</i>	<i>Temporary Number or Other Designation</i>	<i>NRHP Eligibility</i>	<i>Recorded by and Year</i>	<i>MCLB Barstow Area</i>
P-36-011298	CA-SBR-11298	Prehistoric: Lithic scatter	--	Recommended not eligible	Berryman and Bull 2003	Rifle Range
P-36-011299	CA-SBR-11299	Prehistoric: Lithic scatter	--	Recommended not eligible	Berryman and Bull 2003; Willey et al. 2005; Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
P-36-011300	CA-SBR-11300	Prehistoric: Lithic scatter	--	Recommended not eligible	Berryman and Bull 2003	Rifle Range
P-36-011301	CA-SBR-11301	Prehistoric: Lithic scatter	--	Recommended not eligible	Berryman and Bull 2003	Rifle Range
P-36-011302	CA-SBR-11302	Prehistoric: Lithic scatter	--	Not evaluated	Berryman and Bull 2003; Willey et al. 2005	Rifle Range
P-36-011836	CA-SBR-11836	Prehistoric: Lithic scatter	--	Not evaluated	Willey et al. 2005	Rifle Range
P-36-011837	CA-SBR-11837	Prehistoric: Lithic scatter	--	Recommended not eligible	Willey et al. 2005; Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
P-36-011838	CA-SBR-11838	Prehistoric: Lithic scatter	--	Recommended not eligible	Willey et al. 2005; Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
P-36-011839	CA-SBR-11839	Prehistoric: Lithic scatter	--	Recommended not eligible	Willey et al. 2005	Rifle Range
P-36-011840	CA-SBR-11840	Prehistoric: Rock ring	--	Recommended not eligible	Willey et al. 2005; Bryne 2015; Byerly and Byrd 2018	Rifle Range
P-36-011841	CA-SBR-11841	Prehistoric: Lithic scatter	--	Recommended not eligible	Willey et al. 2005; Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
P-36-011842	CA-SBR-11842	Prehistoric: Lithic scatter	--	Recommended not eligible	Willey et al. 2005; Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
P-36-011843	CA-SBR-11843	Prehistoric: Lithic scatter	--	Recommended not eligible	Willey et al. 2005; Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
P-36-011844	CA-SBR-11844	Prehistoric: Lithic scatter	--	Recommended not eligible	Willey et al. 2005; Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
P-36-011845	CA-SBR-11845	Prehistoric: Lithic scatter	--	Recommended not eligible	Willey et al. 2005; Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
P-36-011846	CA-SBR-11846	Prehistoric: Lithic scatter	--	Recommended not eligible	Willey et al. 2005; Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
P-36-011847	CA-SBR-11847	Prehistoric: Lithic scatter	--	Recommended not eligible	Willey et al. 2005; Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
P-36-011848	CA-SBR-11848	Prehistoric: Lithic scatter	--	Recommended not eligible	Willey et al. 2005	Rifle Range
P-36-011849	CA-SBR-11849	Prehistoric: Lithic scatter	--	Recommended not eligible	Willey et al. 2005	Rifle Range

Table B-2. Previously Recorded Archaeological Resources at MCLB Barstow

<i>Primary Number</i>	<i>Trinomial</i>	<i>Resource Description</i>	<i>Temporary Number or Other Designation</i>	<i>NRHP Eligibility</i>	<i>Recorded by and Year</i>	<i>MCLB Barstow Area</i>
P-36-011850	CA-SBR-11850	Prehistoric: Lithic scatter	--	Recommended not eligible	Willey et al. 2005; Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
P-36-020763	CA-SBR-13385H	Historic: Trash scatter	--	Recommended not eligible	Hale 2008	Yermo
P-36-023500	CA-SBR-14833	Prehistoric: Lithic scatter	JTD-02	Not evaluated	Daniels et al. 2011	Rifle Range
P-36-023501	CA-SBR-14834	Prehistoric: Lithic scatter	JTD-03	Not evaluated	Daniels et al. 2011	Rifle Range
P-36-8319	CA-SBR-14835	Prehistoric: Quarry	JTD-06	Recommended not eligible	Daniels et al. 2011; Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
P-36-023503	CA-SBR-14836/H	Multi-component: Historic: Rock ring; Prehistoric: Lithic scatter	JTD-07	Recommended not eligible	Daniels et al. 2011; Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
P-36-023504	CA-SBR-14837H	Historic: Well	Well 1	Not evaluated	Daniels et al. 2011	Nebo
P-36-023505	CA-SBR-14838H	Historic: Well	Well 2	Not evaluated	Daniels et al. 2011	Nebo
-	CA-SBR-29320H	Historic refuse scatter	MCLB-Site-1	Recommended not eligible	Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
-	CA-SBR-29321H	Historic can scatter	MCLB-Site-2	Recommended not eligible	Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
-	CA-SBR-26465H	Historic refuse scatter	MCLB-Site-3	Recommended not eligible	Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
-	CA-SBR-29322H	Historic refuse scatter	MCLB-Site-4	Recommended not eligible	Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
-	CA-SBR-29323H	Historic can scatter	MCLB-Site-5	Recommended not eligible	Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
-	CA-SBR-29324H	Historic camp	MCLB-Site-6	Recommended not eligible	Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
-	CA-SBR-29325	Rock Ring	MCLB-Site-7	Recommended potentially eligible	Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
-	CA-SBR-29326	Prehistoric lithic scatter	MCLB-Site-8	Recommended not eligible	Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
-	CA-SBR-29327	Prehistoric lithic scatter	MCLB-Site-9	Recommended not eligible	Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
-	CA-SBR-29328H	Historic can scatter	MCLB-Site-10	Recommended not eligible	Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
-	CA-SBR-29329H	Historic refuse scatter	MCLB-Site-11	Recommended not eligible	Bryne 2015	Rifle Range

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<i>Primary Number</i>	<i>Trinomial</i>	<i>Resource Description</i>	<i>Temporary Number or Other Designation</i>	<i>NRHP Eligibility</i>	<i>Recorded by and Year</i>	<i>MCLB Barstow Area</i>
-	CA-SBR-29330H	Historic camp	MCLB-Site-12	Recommended not eligible	Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
-	CA-SBR-29331	Prehistoric lithic scatter	MCLB-Site-13	Recommended not eligible	Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
-	CA-SBR-29332H	Historic refuse scatter	MCLB-Site-14	Recommended not eligible	Bryne 2015	Yermo
-	CA-SBR-29333H	Historic can scatter	MCLB-Site-15	Recommended not eligible	Bryne 2015	Yermo
-	CA-SBR-29334H	Historic refuse scatter	MCLB-Site-16	Recommended not eligible	Bryne 2015	Yermo
-	CA-SBR-29335H	Historic refuse scatter	MCLB-Site-17	Recommended not eligible	Bryne 2015	Yermo
-	MCLB-Site-18	Prehistoric lithic scatter	MCLB-Site-18	Recommended not eligible	Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
-	MCLB-Site-19	Prehistoric lithic scatter	MCLB-Site-19	Recommended not eligible	Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
-	CA-SBR-29336H	Historic can scatter	MCLB-Site-20	Recommended not eligible	Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
-	CA-SBR-29337H	Historic refuse scatter	MCLB-Site-21	Recommended not eligible	Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
	CA-SBR-29338H	Historic refuse scatter	MCLB-Site-22	Recommended not eligible	Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
-	CA-SBR-29339H	Historic refuse scatter	MCLB-Site-23	Recommended not eligible	Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
-	CA-SBR-29340H	Historic can scatter	MCLB-Site-24	Recommended not eligible	Bryne 2015	Nebo
-	CA-SBR-29341	Prehistoric lithic scatter	MCLB-Site-25	Recommended not eligible	Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
-	CA-SBR-29342	Historic refuse scatter	MCLB-Site-26	Recommended not eligible	Bryne 2015	Yermo
<i>Isolated Finds</i>						
P-36-012236	N/A	Prehistoric: Isolated resourced flake	--	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Wise and Way 2004	Yermo
P-36-020356	N/A	Prehistoric: Isolated resourced flake	--	Not eligible	Willey et al. 2005	Rifle Range
P-36-020357	N/A	Prehistoric: Isolated resourced flake	--	Not eligible	Willey et al. 2005	Rifle Range

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<i>Primary Number</i>	<i>Trinomial</i>	<i>Resource Description</i>	<i>Temporary Number or Other Designation</i>	<i>NRHP Eligibility</i>	<i>Recorded by and Year</i>	<i>MCLB Barstow Area</i>
P-36-020358	N/A	Prehistoric: Isolated resourced core	--	Not eligible	Willey et al. 2005	Rifle Range
P-36-020359	N/A	Prehistoric: Isolated resourced flake	--	Not eligible	Willey et al. 2005	Rifle Range
P-36-020360	N/A	Prehistoric: Isolated resourced flake	--	Not eligible	Willey et al. 2005	Rifle Range
P-36-020361	N/A	Prehistoric: Isolated resourced flake	--	Not eligible	Willey et al. 2005	Rifle Range
P-36-020362	N/A	Prehistoric: Isolated resourced flake	--	Not eligible	Willey et al. 2005	Rifle Range
P-36-061564	N/A	Historic: Isolated resourced license plate (1932)	--	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	McCabe and Moslack 1990	Rifle Range
P-36-061573	N/A	Historic: Isolated resourced cairn (mining claim)	--	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Yohe 1990	Rifle Range
P-36-061577	N/A	Prehistoric: Isolated resourced flake	--	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Manley 1996	Rifle Range
P-36-061578	N/A	Prehistoric: Isolated resourced flaking station	--	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Manley 1996	Rifle Range
P-36-061579	N/A	Prehistoric: Isolated resourced flaking station	--	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Manley 1996	Rifle Range
P-36-064594	N/A	Prehistoric: Isolated resourced core	--	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Berryman and Bull 2003	Rifle Range
P-36-064595	N/A	Prehistoric: Isolated resourced core and flake	--	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Berryman and Bull 2003	Rifle Range
P-36-064596	N/A	Prehistoric: Isolated resourced flake	--	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Berryman and Bull 2003	Rifle Range
P-36-064597	N/A	Prehistoric: Isolated resourced core and flake	--	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Berryman and Bull 2003	Rifle Range

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P-36-064598	N/A	Prehistoric: Isolated resourced flake	--	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Berryman and Bull 2003	Rifle Range
P-36-064599	N/A	Prehistoric: Isolated resourced core	--	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Berryman and Bull 2003	Rifle Range
P-36-064600	N/A	Prehistoric: Isolated resourced flake	--	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Berryman and Bull 2003	Rifle Range
P-36-064601	N/A	Prehistoric: Isolated resourced flaking station	--	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Berryman and Bull 2003	Rifle Range
P-36-064602	N/A	Prehistoric: Isolated resourced flake	--	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Berryman and Bull 2003	Rifle Range
P-36-064603	N/A	Prehistoric: Isolated resourced flake	--	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Berryman and Bull 2003	Rifle Range
P-36-064604	N/A	Prehistoric: Isolated resourced core	--	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Berryman and Bull 2003	Rifle Range
P-36-064605	N/A	Prehistoric: Isolated resourced core and flake	--	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Berryman and Bull 2003	Rifle Range
P-36-023506	N/A	Prehistoric: Isolated resourced flake	JTD-01	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Daniels et al. 2011	Rifle Range
P-36-023507	N/A	Prehistoric: Isolated resourced flake	JTD-04	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Daniels et al. 2011	Rifle Range
P-36-023508	N/A	Historic: Isolated resourced insulator	JTD-08a	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Daniels et al. 2011	Yermo
P-36-023509	N/A	Historic: Isolated resourced bottle	JTD-08b	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Daniels et al. 2011	Yermo
P-36-023510	N/A	Historic: Isolated resourced glass fragments	JTD-08c	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Daniels et al. 2011	Yermo

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P-36-029208	N/A	Isolated Resource: Two metal cans, one with church-key-type opening and one with aluminum top and pull-tab opening	MCLB-ISO-1	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
P-36-029209	N/A	Isolated Resource: One metal can with church-key-type opening	MCLB-ISO-2	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
P-36-029210	N/A	Isolated Resource: One metal fuel or oil can	MCLB-ISO-3	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
P-36-029211	N/A	Isolated Resource: One metal can with church-key-type opening	MCLB-ISO-4	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
P-36-029212	N/A	Isolated Resource: One green glass 7UP bottle	MCLB-ISO-5	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
P-36-029213	N/A	Isolated Resource: One metal can with church-key-type opening	MCLB-ISO-6	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
P-36-029214	N/A	Isolated Resource: One metal can with church-key-type opening	MCLB-ISO-7	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
P-36-029215	N/A	Isolated Resource: One metal can with church-key-type opening	MCLB-ISO-8	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
P-36-029216	N/A	Isolated Resource: One metal can with church-key-type opening	MCLB-ISO-9	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
P-36-029217	N/A	Isolated Resource: One metal can with church-key-type opening	MCLB-ISO-10	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
P-36-029218	N/A	Isolated Resource: One metal can with church-key-type opening	MCLB-ISO-11	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
P-36-029219	N/A	Isolated Resource: Lithic flake of CCS material	MCLB-ISO-12	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Rifle Range

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P-36-029220	N/A	Isolated Resource: Lithic flake of CCS material	MCLB-ISO-13	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
P-36-029221	N/A	Isolated Resource: Two metal cans, one with church-key-type opening and one with aluminum top and pull-tab opening	MCLB-ISO-14	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
P-36-029222	N/A	Isolated Resource: One metal can with aluminum top	MCLB-ISO-15	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
P-36-029223	N/A	Isolated Resource: One metal can with church-key-type opening	MCLB-ISO-16	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
P-36-029224	N/A	Isolated Resource: One lithic flake of CCS material and one metal can with aluminum top	MCLB-ISO-17	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
P-36-029225	N/A	Isolated Resource: One metal can with aluminum top	MCLB-ISO-18	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029226	N/A	Isolated Resource: One metal can with aluminum top	MCLB-ISO-19	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029227	N/A	Isolated Resource: One metal can with aluminum top and pull-tab opening	MCLB-ISO-20	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029228	N/A	Isolated Resource: One metal can with church-key-type opening	MCLB-ISO-21	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029229	N/A	Isolated Resource: One steel can with friction lid	MCLB-ISO-22	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029230	N/A	Isolated Resource: One metal can with church-key-type opening	MCLB-ISO-23	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029231	N/A	Isolated Resource: Glass bottle manufactured by Hazel Atlas Co.	MCLB-ISO-24	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo

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P-36-029232	N/A	Isolated Resource: One metal can with church-key-type opening and one metal can fragment	MCLB-ISO-25	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029233	N/A	Isolated Resource: One metal can with aluminum top and one metal can base	MCLB-ISO-26	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029234	N/A	Isolated Resource: One aqua glass bottle base, embossed; and one crushed metal can	MCLB-ISO-27	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029235	N/A	Isolated Resource: One metal hole-in-top can fragment	MCLB-ISO-28	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029236	N/A	Isolated Resource: One crushed metal can	MCLB-ISO-29	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029237	N/A	Isolated Resource: One metal can with aluminum top and pull-tab opening	MCLB-ISO-30	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029238	N/A	Isolated Resource: One small metal can and one metal toy shovel	MCLB-ISO-31	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029239	N/A	Isolated Resource: One crushed metal can	MCLB-ISO-32	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029240	N/A	Isolated Resource: One metal can with church-key-type opening and one metal sanitary can lid	MCLB-ISO-33	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029241	N/A	Isolated Resource: One metal can fragment and one metal oil or solvent can and one round metal can with wire handle and friction lid	MCLB-ISO-34	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029242	N/A	Isolated Resource: One crushed metal can	MCLB-ISO-35	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029243	N/A	Isolated Resource: One metal can with church-key-type opening and one metal sanitary can lid	MCLB-ISO-36	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo

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<i>Primary Number</i>	<i>Trinomial</i>	<i>Resource Description</i>	<i>Temporary Number or Other Designation</i>	<i>NRHP Eligibility</i>	<i>Recorded by and Year</i>	<i>MCLB Barstow Area</i>
P-36-029244	N/A	Isolated Resource: One metal hole-in-top can	MCLB-ISO-37	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029245	N/A	Isolated Resource: One metal sanitary can and one metal oil or brake fluid can and two metal can fragments	MCLB-ISO-38	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029246	N/A	Isolated Resource: One clear glass jug base	MCLB-ISO-39	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029247	N/A	Isolated Resource: One lithic shatter fragment of CCS material	MCLB-ISO-40	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
P-36-029248	N/A	Isolated Resource: One chert flake	MCLB-ISO-41	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029249	N/A	Isolated Resource: One metal can with church-key-type opening	MCLB-ISO-42	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029250	N/A	Isolated Resource: One chert flake, red	MCLB-ISO-43	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029251	N/A	Isolated Resource: One solarized or amethyst glass bottle base and one peach-colored flat glass fragment, embossed	MCLB-ISO-44	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
P-36-029252	N/A	Isolated Resource: Military magazine	MCLB-ISO-45	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
-	N/A	Isolated Resource: One crushed metal can	MCLB-ISO-46	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
-	N/A	Isolated Resource: One CCS core	MCLB-ISO-47	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
-	N/A	Isolated Resource: One CCS flake	MCLB-ISO-48	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Rifle Range

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<i>Primary Number</i>	<i>Trinomial</i>	<i>Resource Description</i>	<i>Temporary Number or Other Designation</i>	<i>NRHP Eligibility</i>	<i>Recorded by and Year</i>	<i>MCLB Barstow Area</i>
P-36-029253	N/A	Isolated Resource: Prehistoric biface midsection fragment	MCLB-ISO-49	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
P-36-029254	N/A	Isolated Resource: Two steel cans, one with church-key-type opening	MCLB-ISO-50	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
P-36-029255	N/A	Isolated Resource: Milk glass jar base	MCLB-ISO-51	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
P-36-029256	N/A	Isolated Resource: Steel can with church-key-type opening	MCLB-ISO-52	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
P-36-029257	N/A	Isolated Resource: Steel can with church-key-type opening	MCLB-ISO-53	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
P-36-029258	N/A	Isolated Resource: Two steel, 1-gallon fuel cans	MCLB-ISO-54	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
P-36-029259	N/A	Isolated Resource: Steel beverage can, labeled "CHOCOLATE FLAVORED DRINK"	MCLB-ISO-55	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
P-36-029260	N/A	Isolated Resource: Steel sanitary can with twist-key opening	MCLB-ISO-56	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
P-36-029261	N/A	Isolated Resource: Steel beer can with aluminum top, labeled "OLYMPIA"	MCLB-ISO-57	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
P-36-029262	N/A	Isolated Resource: Two steel Bubble Up cans with aluminum tops	MCLB-ISO-58	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Nebo
P-36-029263	N/A	Isolated Resource: All-steel can with church-key-type opening	MCLB-ISO-59	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Nebo
P-36-029264	N/A	Isolated Resource: Two steel cans with aluminum tops and pull-tab closures and one partial, cone-top steel can	MCLB-ISO-60	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Nebo
P-36-029265	N/A	Isolated Resource: Two steel cans with church-key-type openings	MCLB-ISO-61	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Nebo

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P-36-029266	N/A	Isolated Resource: Two steel cans with aluminum tops; one is a FANTA soft drink can	MCLB-ISO-62	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Nebo
P-36-029267	N/A	Isolated Resource: Steel can with aluminum top, labeled "SCHLITZ"	MCLB-ISO-63	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Nebo
P-36-029268	N/A	Isolated Resource: All-steel can, opened with a knife	MCLB-ISO-64	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
P-36-029269	N/A	Isolated Resource: Steel sanitary can with twist-key opening	MCLB-ISO-65	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
P-36-029270	N/A	Isolated Resource: Three steel cans. One is solder dot closure and two are twist-key-type openings	MCLB-ISO-66	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
P-36-029271	N/A	Isolated Resource: Steel sanitary can with twist-key-type opening	MCLB-ISO-67	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
P-36-029272	N/A	Isolated Resource: Two steel cans. One with twist-key-type opening and one with church-key-type opening	MCLB-ISO-68	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
P-36-029273	N/A	Isolated Resource: Two steel cans with twist-key-type openings and two steel sanitary cans	MCLB-ISO-69	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
P-36-029274	N/A	Isolated Resource: Steel can with church-key-type opening and interlocking side seam	MCLB-ISO-70	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Rifle Range
P-36-029275	N/A	Isolated Resource: Steel can with church-key-type opening	MCLB-ISO-71	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029276	N/A	Isolated Resource: Steel can with church-key-type opening	MCLB-ISO-72	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029277	N/A	Isolated Resource: Three steel cans with church-key-type openings and one crushed steel can	MCLB-ISO-73	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029278	N/A	Isolated Resource: Five steel cans including one with aluminum top and pull-tab closure	MCLB-ISO-74	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo

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P-36-029279	N/A	Isolated Resource: Steel can with solder dot closure	MCLB-ISO-75	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029280	N/A	Isolated Resource: Steel can with solder dot closure	MCLB-ISO-76	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029281	N/A	Isolated Resource: Steel can with church-key-type opening	MCLB-ISO-77	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029282	N/A	Isolated Resource: Steel can with church-key-type opening	MCLB-ISO-78	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029283	N/A	Isolated Resource: Steel can with church-key-type opening	MCLB-ISO-79	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029283	N/A	Isolated Resource: Steel can with church-key-type opening	MCLB-ISO-80	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029284	N/A	Isolated Resource: Four steel cans with church-key-type openings	MCLB-ISO-81	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029285	N/A	Isolated Resource: Three steel cans with church-key-type openings	MCLB-ISO-82	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029286	N/A	Isolated Resource: Five steel cans, four with church-key-type openings and one with solder dot closure	MCLB-ISO-83	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029287	N/A	Isolated Resource: Five steel cans with church-key-type openings	MCLB-ISO-84	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029288	N/A	Isolate Resource: Three steel cans with church-key-type openings	MCLB-ISO-85	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029289	N/A	Isolated Resource: Five steel cans, three with church-key-type openings and two with solder dot closures	MCLB-ISO-86	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029290	N/A	Isolated Resource: Steel can with church-key-type opening	MCLB-ISO-87	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo

Table B-2. Previously Recorded Archaeological Resources at MCLB Barstow

<i>Primary Number</i>	<i>Trinomial</i>	<i>Resource Description</i>	<i>Temporary Number or Other Designation</i>	<i>NRHP Eligibility</i>	<i>Recorded by and Year</i>	<i>MCLB Barstow Area</i>
P-36-029291	N/A	Isolated Resource: Steel can with church-key-type opening	MCLB-ISO-88	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029292	N/A	Isolated Resource: Two steel cans, one with church-key-type opening and one with twist-key-type opening	MCLB-ISO-89	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029294	N/A	Isolated Resource: Steel can with church-key-type opening	MCLB-ISO-90	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029295	N/A	Isolated Resource: Steel can with solder dot closure	MCLB-ISO-91	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029296	N/A	Isolated Resource: Two steel cans with church-key-type openings	MCLB-ISO-92	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029297	N/A	Isolated Resource: Two steel cans with church-key-type openings	MCLB-ISO-93	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029298	N/A	Isolated Resource: Steel can with church-key-type opening	MCLB-ISO-94	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029299	N/A	Isolated Resource: Steel can with church-key-type opening	MCLB-ISO-95	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029300	N/A	Isolated Resource: Two steel cans with church-key-type openings	MCLB-ISO-96	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029301	N/A	Isolated Resource: Two steel cans with church-key-type openings	MCLB-ISO-97	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029302	N/A	Isolated Resource: Two steel cans with church-key-type openings	MCLB-ISO-98	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029303	N/A	Isolated Resource: Four steel cans with church-key-type openings	MCLB-ISO-99	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029304	N/A	Isolated Resource: Steel can with church-key-type opening	MCLB-ISO-100	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo

Table B-2. Previously Recorded Archaeological Resources at MCLB Barstow

<i>Primary Number</i>	<i>Trinomial</i>	<i>Resource Description</i>	<i>Temporary Number or Other Designation</i>	<i>NRHP Eligibility</i>	<i>Recorded by and Year</i>	<i>MCLB Barstow Area</i>
P-36-029305	N/A	Isolated Resource: Two steel cans with church-key-type openings	MCLB-ISO-101	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029306	N/A	Isolated Resource: Steel can, crushed	MCLB-ISO-102	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029307	N/A	Isolated Resource: Steel can with solder dot closure	MCLB-ISO-103	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029308	N/A	Isolated Resource: Steel can with solder dot closure	MCLB-ISO-104	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029309	N/A	Isolated Resource: Steel can with church-key-type opening	MCLB-ISO-105	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029310	N/A	Isolated Resource: Amethyst glass bottle neck	MCLB-ISO-106	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029311	N/A	Isolated Resource: Steel can with church-key-type opening	MCLB-ISO-107	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029312	N/A	Isolated Resource: Amethyst glass fragment	MCLB-ISO-108	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029571	N/A	Isolated Resource: Steel can with church-key-type opening	MCLB-ISO-109	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029313	N/A	Isolated Resource: Steel can with solder dot closure	MCLB-ISO-110	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029314	N/A	Isolated Resource: Steel can with solder dot closure	MCLB-ISO-111	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029315	N/A	Isolated Resource: Prehistoric chalcedony core	MCLB-ISO-112	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029316	N/A	Isolated Resource: Steel can with church-key-type opening	MCLB-ISO-113	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo

Table B-2. Previously Recorded Archaeological Resources at MCLB Barstow

<i>Primary Number</i>	<i>Trinomial</i>	<i>Resource Description</i>	<i>Temporary Number or Other Designation</i>	<i>NRHP Eligibility</i>	<i>Recorded by and Year</i>	<i>MCLB Barstow Area</i>
P-36-029317	N/A	Isolated Resource: Amethyst bottle glass (10 fragments)	MCLB-ISO-114	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029318	N/A	Isolated Resource: Steel can with church-key-type opening	MCLB-ISO-115	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo
P-36-029319	N/A	Isolated Resource: Steel can with church-key-type opening	MCLB-ISO-116	Not eligible (Isolated resource)	Bryne 2015	Yermo

Section 304 of the National Historic Preservation Act [16 U.S.C. 470w-3], requires federal agencies, to “withhold from disclosure to the public, information about the location, character, or ownership of a historic resource...”.

Therefore, figures depicting the previously recorded archaeological site locations are not available to the public.

Table B-3. Buildings and Structures Located at MCLB Barstow

<i>Primary Number</i>	<i>Facility Number</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Year Built</i>	<i>Location</i>	<i>Eligibility</i>	<i>Recorded by and Year</i>	<i>SHPO Concurrence</i>
P-36-030043	1A	Storage	1946	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-030043	1B	Storage	1946	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-030043	1C	Warehouse	1946	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-030003	2	Warehouse	1942	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-030003	3	Warehouse	1942	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-030003	4	Warehouse	1942	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-030004	5	Warehouse	1942	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-030004	6	Warehouse	1942	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-030004	7	Warehouse	1942	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-030004	8	Warehouse	1942	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-030004	9	Warehouse	1942	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-030004	10	Warehouse	1942	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-030005	11	Warehouse	1944	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-030005	12	Warehouse	1944	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-030005	13	Warehouse	1944	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-030005	14	Warehouse	1944	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-030006	15	Headquarters MCLB Barstow	1942	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019317	15A	Miscellaneous utility building	1952	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-030008	17	Medical dispensary	1943	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	17D	Medical clinics	1943	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-030009	18	Fire Station	1942	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	26	Well 3- Water distribution	1949	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
P-36-030013	27*	Hazardous and flammables storehouse	1945	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019198	29	Electrical distribution system	1957	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-030015	33	Public Affairs	1942	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes

Table B-3. Buildings and Structures Located at MCLB Barstow

<i>Primary Number</i>	<i>Facility Number</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Year Built</i>	<i>Location</i>	<i>Eligibility</i>	<i>Recorded by and Year</i>	<i>SHPO Concurrence</i>
P-36-030055	35	Pump house/dressing room/ swimming pool	1944	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-030018	38	Officers' Club	1946	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019148	44	Recreational facility	1950	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019285	46	Truck scales	1955	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	62*	Recreational facility	1958	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	63*	Recreational facility	1958	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	64	Recreation facility	2014	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	100	Golf club house	2015	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	101	Pass and Identification building	2007	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
P-36-030029	103	Childcare center	1944	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-030030	114	Temporary Lodging Facility	1946	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019344	124	Water system facilities	1959	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	126	Chapel	1952	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019199	127	Electrical distribution system	1952	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019190	128	Chapel	1952	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019149	129*	Administration building	1956	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	131A*	Training facility	1955	Rifle	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019588	140	Garage	1950	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019589	141	Garage	1950	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019720	144	Storage building	1951	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019721	145	Storage building	1951	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019722	146	Storage building	1952	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019723	147	Storage building	1952	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019191	149	Medical clinic	1954	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes

Table B-3. Buildings and Structures Located at MCLB Barstow

<i>Primary Number</i>	<i>Facility Number</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Year Built</i>	<i>Location</i>	<i>Eligibility</i>	<i>Recorded by and Year</i>	<i>SHPO Concurrence</i>
P-36-019724	150	Storage building	1952	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	151	Scale House	2001	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
P-36-019725	152	Storage building	1952	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019726	154	Storage building	1951	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019727	155	Storage building	1951	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019728	156	Storage building	1951	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019729	157	Storage building	1952	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019730	158	Storage building	1951	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019731	159	Storage building	1951	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019732	160	Storage building	1952	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019733	161	Storage building	1951	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019734	162	Storage building	1952	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019735	163	Storage building	1952	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019736	164	Storage building	1953	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019737	165	Storage building	1953	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	168	Police station	2007	Nebo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
P-36-019151	170	Administration building	1958	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-030031	172	Garage	1942	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019302	174	Public restrooms	1954	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	175	Bachelor's Enlisted Quarters	2011	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
P-36-019159	177	Barracks	1956	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019287	178	Truck scales	1959	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019160	185	Temporary Lodging Facility	1952	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	186*	Temporary Lodging Facility	1952	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	187*	Temporary Lodging Facility	1952	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019738	191	Storage building	1952	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019739	192	Storage building	1952	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes

Table B-3. Buildings and Structures Located at MCLB Barstow

<i>Primary Number</i>	<i>Facility Number</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Year Built</i>	<i>Location</i>	<i>Eligibility</i>	<i>Recorded by and Year</i>	<i>SHPO Concurrence</i>
N/A	194	Kennel administration	2007	Nebo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
P-36-019740	196	Administration building	1959	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	197	Maintenance and repair facility	1959	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019153	198	Administration building	1959	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	199	Administrative storage	1992	Nebo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	203	Maintenance and repair facility	1956	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019742	204	Administration building	1956	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019192	218	Base Library	1956	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019744	226	Administration building	1956	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	226A	Truck inspection radiation portal detectors	2013	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
P-36-019745	227	Storage building	1957	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019746	232	Storage building	1958	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019264	233	Maintenance and repair facility	1957	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	233A	Interior fencing-DLA distribution	2000	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
P-36-019154	236	Administration building	1952	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019155	238*	Miscellaneous utility building	1952	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019747	243	Storage building	1955	Rifle	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019249	249	Administration building	1943	Rifle	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	252	Target storage building	1994	Rifle	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	254	Rifle range sound building	1994	Rifle	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	279*	Storage building	1948	Rifle	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	280	Public facility	2002	Yermo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
P-36-019319	290	Miscellaneous utility building	1963	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019305	293*	Public restrooms	1964	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019749	300	Storage building	1968	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019193	301	Family restaurant	1969	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes

Table B-3. Buildings and Structures Located at MCLB Barstow

<i>Primary Number</i>	<i>Facility Number</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Year Built</i>	<i>Location</i>	<i>Eligibility</i>	<i>Recorded by and Year</i>	<i>SHPO Concurrence</i>
N/A	303	Well 6- Water distribution building	1969	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
P-36-019203	319	Marine Corps Exchange	1972	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019156	321	Administration building	1971	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019266	322	Maintenance and repair facility	1975	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	324	Filling station	1998	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
P-36-019322	325	Sewage/industrial waste facilities	1976	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019323	325A*	Sewage/industrial waste facility	1976	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	325B	Sewage/industrial waste facilities	1977	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	325C	Sewage/industrial waste facilities	1977	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	325D	Sewage/industrial waste facilities	1991	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
P-36-019324	326	Sewage/industrial waste facility	1976	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019215	331	Storage building	1978	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019750	340	Storage building	1981	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019751	341	Storage building	1981	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	342	Leatherneck lanes	1982	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019752	343	Storage building	1982	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	344	Golf cart storage shed	2003	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
P-36-019228	359	Heat system facilities	1982	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019243	361	Personnel shelters	1984	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019157	362	Administration building	1985	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	363	Housing community center	2008	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
P-36-019194	364	Commissary	1985	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019753	368	Storage building	1987	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019356	370	Armory facility	1988	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	370A*	Detached sunshade	1991	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019310	371	Training facility	1988	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes

Table B-3. Buildings and Structures Located at MCLB Barstow

<i>Primary Number</i>	<i>Facility Number</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Year Built</i>	<i>Location</i>	<i>Eligibility</i>	<i>Recorded by and Year</i>	<i>SHPO Concurrence</i>
N/A	372	Childcare facility	1989	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	373	PMO training facility	2005	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	374	Telephone exchange	1991	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	375	Wood shop	1991	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
P-36-030033	401	Warehouse	1942	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-030033	402	Warehouse	1942	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-030033	403	Warehouse	1942	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-030033	404	Warehouse	1942	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-030033	405	Warehouse	1942	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-030033	406	Warehouse	1942	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-030034	411*	Public restrooms	1942	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-030035	414*	Stables corral	1942	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	428	Public restrooms	1942	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-030036	430	Hazardous Storehouse	1948	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-030036	431	Hazardous Storehouse	1948	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-030036	432	Hazardous Storehouse	1948	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	436	Fire truck shelter	2010	Yermo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
P-36-030037	437	Fire station	1942	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-030041	484	Water distribution building	1942	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	487A	Well 6A- Water treatment facility	2000	Yermo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	488	Vehicle Battery Storage	2001	Yermo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	535	Storage building	1952	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019716	536	Storage building	1952	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019755	537	Storage building	1952	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019756	538	Storage building	1952	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019757	539	Storage building	1952	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	540	Storage building	1952	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes

Table B-3. Buildings and Structures Located at MCLB Barstow

<i>Primary Number</i>	<i>Facility Number</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Year Built</i>	<i>Location</i>	<i>Eligibility</i>	<i>Recorded by and Year</i>	<i>SHPO Concurrence</i>
N/A	541	Storage building	1952	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	542	Storage building	1952	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	543	Storage building	1952	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	544	Storage building	1952	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	545	Storage building	1952	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	547	DLA hazard/ flammable storage	1953	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019289	548	Storage building	1953	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019290	549	Storage building	1953	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019291	550	Storage building	1953	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	551	Maintenance	1990	Yermo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	552	Repair shop/ Storage building	1990	Yermo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	553	Hazmat Storage	1993	Yermo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
P-36-019292	554	Storage building	1954	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019293	555	Storage building	1953	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019320	558	Miscellaneous utility building	1960	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019294	560	Storage building	1956	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019295	561	Storage building	1956	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019296	562	Storage building	1957	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	563	Decontamination facility	2010	Yermo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	564	Break/lunch	2009	Yermo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	565	Super blast	2006	Yermo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	566	Plastic media bast booth	1999	Yermo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	567*	Maintenance and repair facility	1979	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	568	Utility building for air compressor	1997	Yermo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	569	Plastic media bast booth	1992	Yermo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	570	Maintenance and repair facility	1982	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	571	Engine Repair	1990	Yermo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A

Table B-3. Buildings and Structures Located at MCLB Barstow

<i>Primary Number</i>	<i>Facility Number</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Year Built</i>	<i>Location</i>	<i>Eligibility</i>	<i>Recorded by and Year</i>	<i>SHPO Concurrence</i>
P-36-019236	572	Stables coral	1957	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019268	573	Maintenance and repair facility	1960	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	573C	Pedestrian bridge at guard shack entry	1995	Yermo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	573D	Pedestrian bridge-turnstyle	1995	Yermo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
P-36-019229	574	Heat system facility	1960	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	574A	Satellite exchange	2010	Yermo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	574B	Multi-purpose facility	2010	Yermo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
P-36-019766	575	Maintenance and repair facility	1960	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	S576	Maintenance and repair facility	2011	Yermo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	578	Well 7- Water treatment facility	2004	Yermo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	579	Dynamometer Building	1993	Yermo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
P-36-019351	580	Water system facility	1961	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	581	Naval engine repair	1997	Yermo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
P-36-019185	582	Barracks	1961	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	584	Maintenance and repair facilities	Unknown	Yermo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	588	Maintenance and repair facility	1954	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	589	Public Toilet	2002	Yermo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	590	Automotive repair facility	2002	Yermo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	592	Maintenance and repair facility	1964	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	593	Maintenance and repair facility	1964	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	594	Army barracks	2003	Yermo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
P-36-019270	595	Maintenance and repair facility	1965	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	596	Marine Corps Exchange	2008	Yermo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
P-36-019271	598	Maintenance and repair facility	1969	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019272	599	Maintenance and repair facility	1969	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	600	Well 5- Water treatment facility	1970	Yermo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	601	Non-destruction testing facility	2010	Yermo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A

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<i>Primary Number</i>	<i>Facility Number</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Year Built</i>	<i>Location</i>	<i>Eligibility</i>	<i>Recorded by and Year</i>	<i>SHPO Concurrence</i>
N/A	602	Armor repair facility	2012	Yermo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	607	Sewage/waste operations	2002	Yermo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	607B	Valve house	2007	Yermo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	607C	Valve house	2007	Yermo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	608	Industrial waste treatment	1996	Yermo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
P-36-019332	610	Sewage/industrial waste facility	1976	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	610B	Water treatment shed	1973	Yermo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
P-36-019335	611	Sewage/industrial waste facility	1976	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019337	612	Sewage/industrial waste facility	1976	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019230	613	Maintenance and repair facility	1977	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	614	Maintenance and repair facility	1977	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	S615	Storage building	2000	Yermo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	616	Smalls Arms Test Firing Range	1998	Yermo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	617	Forward kitting storage facility	2012	Yermo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
P-36-019298	618	Storage building	1981	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	619	Radome test facility	1993	Yermo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	T-620*	Repair office	1995	Yermo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	621	Special weapons repair	1999	Yermo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	622	Maintenance and repair facility	1985	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	623	Maintenance and repair facility	1985	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	624	Maintenance and repair facility	1985	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019299	625	Storage building	1986	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019273	626	Maintenance and repair facility	1985	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019309	627	Public restrooms	1985	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019274	628	Maintenance and repair facility	1986	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019275	629	Maintenance and repair facility	1986	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019321	630	Miscellaneous utility building	1986	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019300	631	Storage building	1984	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes

Table B-3. Buildings and Structures Located at MCLB Barstow

<i>Primary Number</i>	<i>Facility Number</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Year Built</i>	<i>Location</i>	<i>Eligibility</i>	<i>Recorded by and Year</i>	<i>SHPO Concurrence</i>
P-36-019339	632*	Sewage/industrial waste facility	1987	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019276	633	Maintenance and repair facility	1988	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	634	Maintenance and repair facility	2003	Yermo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
P-36-019301	635	Storage building	1988	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	636	Maintenance and repair facility	2001	Yermo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	637	Maintenance and repair facility	2004	Yermo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	638	Industrial machine shop	2010	Yermo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	639	Storage building	2012	Yermo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	640	Corrosion control-cleaning dip tank	2014	Yermo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	641	Maintenance facility	2017	Yermo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
P-36-019593	1019	Garage	1953	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019594	1033	Garage	1953	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	1047	Storage building	1987	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019345	1548	Water system facility	1953	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	3000	Enlisted housing A-D	2008	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	3001	Housing WO, 01/03 A-B	2008	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	3002	Desert view housing A-B	2008	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	3003	Desert view housing A-B	2008	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	3004	Desert view housing	2008	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	3005	Desert view housing A-B	2008	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	3006	Desert view housing	2008	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	3007	Desert view housing A-B	2008	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	3008	Desert view housing- enlisted A-D	2008	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	3009	Desert view housing A-B	2008	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	3010	Desert view housing A-D	2008	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	3011	Housing A-D	2008	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A

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<i>Primary Number</i>	<i>Facility Number</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Year Built</i>	<i>Location</i>	<i>Eligibility</i>	<i>Recorded by and Year</i>	<i>SHPO Concurrence</i>
N/A	3012	Desert view housing- enlisted A-B	2008	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	3013	Desert view housing- enlisted A-D	2008	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	3014	Desert view housing enlisted A-D	2008	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	3015	Desert view housing enlisted A-D	2008	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	3016	Desert view housing A-D	2008	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	3017	Desert view housing enlisted A-D	2008	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	3019	Desert view housing A-D	2008	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	3021	Desert view housing enlisted A-D	2008	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	3023	Desert view housing A-D	2008	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	3025	Desert view housing enlisted A-D	2008	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	200009	Compressed air distribution system	1954	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	200067	Parade and drill field	1958	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	200073	Electric power- photovoltaic	2014	Yermo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	200074	Electric power- photovoltaic	2010	Yermo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	200075	Retaining wall- range	1955	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	200076	Retaining wall	1993	Yermo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	200077	Retaining wall- housing	1964	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	200099	Yerbo solar farm	2013	Yerbo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	200100	Nebo solar farm	2012	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	200103	Fencing in lot 500	1949	Yermo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	200110	Fencing- MDMC	1971	Yermo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	200114	Perimeter fence at Rattlesnake Rock	1980	Yermo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	200120	Perimeter fence- 63 rd	2018	Yermo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	200123	Flagpole billboard marker	2010	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A

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<i>Primary Number</i>	<i>Facility Number</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Year Built</i>	<i>Location</i>	<i>Eligibility</i>	<i>Recorded by and Year</i>	<i>SHPO Concurrence</i>
N/A	200127	Flagpole billboard marker	2012	Yermo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	200157	Electric power-photovoltaic	2019	Yermo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	200163	Open storage area- concrete ponds	1982	Yermo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	200252	Drainage ditch	1942	Nebo	Ineligible	Unknown	Unknown
N/A	200254	Monument/ grave	1942	Nebo	Ineligible	Unknown	Unknown
N/A	200257	Flagpole billboard marker	1988	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	200265	Retaining wall	1951	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	200286	Railroad track	1943	Nebo	Ineligible	Unknown	Unknown
N/A	200287	Security and perimeter fencing	1942	Nebo	Ineligible	Unknown	Unknown
N/A	200538	Drainage ditch	1942	Yermo	Ineligible	Unknown	Unknown
N/A	200539	Railroad track	1954	Yermo	Ineligible	Unknown	Unknown
N/A	200551	Security and perimeter fencing	1949	Yermo	Ineligible	Unknown	Unknown
N/A	201147	Interior fencing	1949	Nebo	Ineligible	Unknown	Unknown
N/A	201148	Interior fencing	1949	Yermo	Ineligible	Unknown	Unknown
N/A	201168	Compressed air distribution system	1969	Yermo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	201470	Security and perimeter fence	2005	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	201563	Electric power-photovoltaic system	2011	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	201573	Interior fencing	2011	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	201579	Mechanical security barricade	2011	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	201580	Mechanical security barricade	2011	Yermo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	201585	Electric power-photovoltaic system	2012	Yermo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	200157A	Paved transformer pad	2019	Yermo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	200157B	Paved transformer pad	2019	Yermo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	MOQ1	Family housing	2008	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	MOQ2	Family housing	2008	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	MOQ3	Family housing	2008	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	MOQ4	Family housing	2008	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	MOQ5	Family housing	2008	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	MOQ6	Family housing	2008	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	MOQ7	Family housing	2008	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
P-36-030046	MOQ8	Quarters	1942	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	MOQ9	Family housing	2008	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A

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<i>Primary Number</i>	<i>Facility Number</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Year Built</i>	<i>Location</i>	<i>Eligibility</i>	<i>Recorded by and Year</i>	<i>SHPO Concurrence</i>
P-36-030046	MOQ11	Quarters	1942	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	N003	Unknown	1990	Nebo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	N004	Unknown	1990	Nebo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	P48	Pump station	1949	Nebo	Ineligible	Unknown	Unknown
N/A	S17	Personnel weather shelter	1995	Nebo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	S26*	Water system facility	1942	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019244	S28	Personnel shelter	1965	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-030053	S29	Electrical distribution system	1942	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	S30	Recreation pavilion	1995	Nebo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	S35	Utility building	1945	Nebo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	S42	Obstacle course	2014	Nebo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	S43	Potable water storage tank	2005	Nebo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	S44A	Combat pit	2012	Nebo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
P-36-030061	S45	Load/unload ramp	1942	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019286	S46	Truck scales	1955	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-030063	S48	Pump station potable water	1942	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	S62*	Unknown	2000	Nebo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	S62A*	Unknown	2000	Nebo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	S73	Potable water storage tank	2004	Nebo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	S74	Wind turbine	2009	Nebo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	S100	Recreation pavilion	1995	Nebo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	S129	Recreation pavilion	2005	Nebo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	S103*	Playground	2005	Nebo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
P-36-019200	S130	Electrical distribution system	1950	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	S143	Family pool	1951	Nebo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	S153	Flagpole	1949	Nebo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	S165	Antenna communication	2007	Nebo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
P-36-019252	S166	Recreational facility	1950	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019238	S168	Bridge	1950	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	S169*	Bridge	1946	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes

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N/A	S175B	Carport for photovoltaic system	2011	Nebo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	S175C	Overhead cover with BBQ pit	2011	Nebo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	S175D	Utility block wall	2011	Nebo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
P-36-019288	S178*	Truck scales	1959	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019346	S184*	Water system facility	1958	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	S185	RV campground	1996	Nebo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	S185A	RV campground	1995	Nebo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	S185B	RV campground	2006	Nebo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	S185C	Recreation pavilion	2006	Nebo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
P-36-019254	S190	Recreational facility	1950	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	S190A	Recreation facility-announcer booth	1955	Nebo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
P-36-019239	S200	Bridge	1953	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	S202	Bridge	1943	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	S203	Bridge	1943	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-030047	S211	Load/unload ramp	1942	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019256	S221	Recreational facility	1956	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019257	S222	Recreational facility	1956	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	S223	Recreational facilities	2008	Nebo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	S244	Recreational facility	1950	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	S244A	Pedestrian bridge at golf course	1951	Nebo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	S249	Receiver building and antenna	1992	Nebo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	S258	Flagpole	1965	Nebo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	S258A	Obstruction lighting and marking	2016	Nebo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
P-36-019201	S277*	Electrical distribution system	1962	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	S278	Recreation facility	1995	Nebo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	S283	Small Arms Range	1955	Rifle	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes

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P-36-030051	S285	Recreational facility	1944	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	S285A	Recreational facility	1984	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019313	S286	Training facility	1957	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019234	S288	Helicopter landing pads	1962	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-030052	S289*	Sewage/industrial waste facility	1942	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	S290	Carport for photovoltaic system	2011	Nebo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
P-36-030054	S291*	Sewage/industrial waste facility	1942	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019314	S294*	Training facility	1964	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019350	S303*	Water system facility	1969	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	S326A*	Sewage/industrial waste facility	1976	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	S326B*	Sewage/industrial waste facility	1976	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	S326C*	Sewage/industrial waste facility	1976	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	S327E	Transformer station	1980	Nebo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
P-36-019196	S334*	Dump station	1977	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019188	S336*	Ceremonial structure (saluting battery gun & flagpole)	1979	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	S343	Storage facility	1973	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	
P-36-019259	S350*	Recreational facility	1982	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	S350A*	Recreational facility	1982	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019260	S360*	Recreational facility	1984	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	S360A*	Recreational facility	1984	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	S357	Recreational facility	1981	Nebo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	S357A	Recreation facility	1973	Nebo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	S357B	Recreation facility	1995	Nebo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
P-36-019240	S366	Bridge	1985	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes

Table B-3. Buildings and Structures Located at MCLB Barstow

<i>Primary Number</i>	<i>Facility Number</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Year Built</i>	<i>Location</i>	<i>Eligibility</i>	<i>Recorded by and Year</i>	<i>SHPO Concurrence</i>
P-36-019358	S367	Armory facility	1987	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	S371	Wheeled vehicle drivers' course	2014	Nebo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	S372*	Recreational facility	1982	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	S393	Storage shed	1995	Nebo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
P-36-030057	S418	Loading ramp	1942	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-030057	S419	Loading ramp	1942	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	S420	Loading ramp	1954	Yermo	Ineligible	Unknown	Unknown
P-36-019241	S423	Bridge	1965	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	S426	Percolating ponds	1954	Yermo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
P-36-030059	S435	Ceremonial structure (flagpole)	1942	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-030060	S446	Load/unload ramp	1942	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-030060	S447	Load/unload ramp	1942	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-030060	S448	Load/unload ramp	1942	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	S473	Potable water storage tank	2012	Yermo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
P-36-030062	S474*	Potable water reservoir	1947	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-030065	S485	Potable water reservoir	1947	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-030066	S530	Electrical Substation	1942	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019237	S566*	Stables corral	1966	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	S572	Horse stables/barn	2005	Yermo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	S575*	Maintenance and repair facility	1960	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	S577	Recreational facility	1950	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	S580	Potable water tank	2005	Yermo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	S583*	Unknown	1995	Yermo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	S584*	Heavy gun shop repair	1990	Yermo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	S585*	Maintenance and repair facilities	1990	Yermo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	S586*	Maintenance and repair facility	1990	Yermo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
P-36-019281	S587	Maintenance and repair facility	1960	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes

Table B-3. Buildings and Structures Located at MCLB Barstow

<i>Primary Number</i>	<i>Facility Number</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Year Built</i>	<i>Location</i>	<i>Eligibility</i>	<i>Recorded by and Year</i>	<i>SHPO Concurrence</i>
P-36-019235	S590	Helicopter landing pads	1962	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019282	S592*	Maintenance and repair facility	1963	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	S593	Unknown	2006	Yermo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
P-36-019340	S596*	Sewage/industrial waste facility	1965	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
P-36-019354	S600*	Water system facility	1969	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	S603	Maintenance facility	2012	Yermo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	S610*	Water system facility	1976	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	S612	Vehicle cable test	1993	Yermo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	S622	Test track for amphibious vehicle training	2000	Yermo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	S628	Utility building	2001	Yermo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	S632	Storage building	2009	Yermo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	S634A	Storage building	1968	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	S634B	Storage building	1968	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	S636	Maintenance and repair facility	n.d.	Yermo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	S-K009	Dog kennel	2007	Nebo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	SK009A	Field training course (dog)	2015	Nebo	Not evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	N/A	Outdoor monument	1933	Nebo	Ineligible	Manley 1996; JRP 2011	Yes
N/A	Y003	Gate/Sentry House	1990	Yermo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A
N/A	Y004	Gate/Sentry House	1990	Yermo	Not Evaluated	N/A	N/A

Notes: *Building listed in JRP 2011 but not in Real Property List

Appendix C. Discovery Treatment Plan

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1 **DISCOVERY TREATMENT PLAN**

2 The discovery treatment plan provides a framework for evaluating and treating unanticipated
3 archaeological resources discovered during general activities on the base and specifically
4 during ground-disturbing activities. These procedures are designed to facilitate communication
5 and the decision-making process, and to ensure that unanticipated cultural resources are
6 evaluated and treated with minimum delay.

7 **PRECONSTRUCTION ORGANIZATION**

8 During planned construction projects, the list of agencies, individuals, and other parties that
9 must be notified in case of unanticipated discoveries should be reviewed. Specific points of
10 contact and their telephone numbers should be compiled, as well as alternative points of
11 contact. Minimally, the list should include the Marine Corps Logistics Base (MCLB) Barstow
12 Cultural Resources Manager (CRM) and the Project Engineer, State Historic Preservation
13 Officer (SHPO), interested Native American groups, and Tribal Historic Preservation Officers
14 (THPO).

15 **DISCOVERY PROCEDURES**

16 Based on the location of sites identified within the vicinity of the proposed project area at
17 MCLB Barstow, all monitors and construction personnel shall be briefed about the potential
18 for unanticipated discoveries.

19 If any archaeological materials are encountered during normal activities or during construction,
20 the CRM shall be notified immediately. Once a discovery is made, any work in the vicinity
21 (within 10 to 15 meters) will stop temporarily or be redirected to other locations. Within 24
22 hours of discovery, the CRM will inspect the resource and notify the Commanding Officer of
23 his/her findings. If it is a construction project, the Project Engineer will also be notified. Within
24 2 weeks of discovery, in consultation with the Naval Facilities Engineering Command
25 Southwest (NAVFAC SW), an archaeological consultant will assess and evaluate the discovery
26 and develop an approach to avoid or mitigate impacts to the find. The evaluation and treatment
27 plan will be in accordance with the *Secretary of the Interior's Standards and Guidelines*. These
28 recommendations will be communicated to the Project Engineer and other involved parties.
29 MCLB Barstow will also immediately notify the SHPO of these recommendations. Specific
30 management and treatment measures recommended will vary according to resource type and
31 complexity, location within the project area, and anticipated project effects.

32 **Recording New Discovery and Noncompliance Incidents**

33 Descriptions of new discoveries are reported directly to the CRM. Depending on the
34 circumstances, the individual who reported the new resource may be requested to submit a
35 written report to the CRM.

36 **Human Remains**

37 Procedures taken upon discovery of human remains shall be consistent with the Native
38 American Graves Protection and Repatriation Act (NAGPRA). These procedures are discussed
39 more fully below.

1 **STANDARD PROCEDURES FOR EVALUATION AND TREATMENT** 2 **OF UNANTICIPATED RESOURCES**

3 Types of archaeological sites within the base may include quarry sites, low-density/low-
4 diversity artifact scatters, historic trails, rock circles, petroglyphs, structural remains, or isolated
5 features. While stratified habitation sites, burials, or cemeteries are not expected on MCLB
6 Barstow, provision should be made to deal with any unforeseen event.

7 Clearly, not all types of archaeological sites possess the same data potential. Some site types,
8 such as stratified habitation sites, may yield a highly diverse and productive assemblage of
9 artifacts, ecofacts, and other materials that may contribute to important research questions
10 relating to cultural chronology, paleoenvironments, site formation processes, and past lifeways.
11 Other site types, such as sparse scatters of flaked stone or historic-era trash deposits, may yield
12 a restricted set of constituents that have less potential to address important issues.

13 **Assessment of Effects**

14 Following the discovery of an unanticipated cultural resource, any project activity shall be
15 redirected to other areas while the site limits are determined. This shall be done on the basis of
16 intensive surface examination, hand excavation, or mechanical excavation as appropriate.
17 When the horizontal limits are established, a temporary Exclusion Zone shall be marked using
18 stakes and a predetermined color ribbon with appropriate signage. Following this, the depth of
19 the archaeological deposit shall be determined using hand or mechanical excavation.

20 Once the basic dimensions of the deposit are established, the site's data potential shall be
21 assessed. Should the resource possess characteristics that may qualify it for the National
22 Register of Historic Places (NRHP), it shall be determined if the undertaking adversely and/or
23 significantly alters the resource (36 Code of Federal Regulations [CFR] 800.9 [a & b]).

24 All archaeological sites recorded will be evaluated using the criteria established for NRHP
25 eligibility (36 CFR § 60.4 A-D). The criteria for evaluating cultural resources in terms of their
26 potential nomination to the NRHP provide a systematic, definable means to evaluate historic
27 and cultural properties. Properties that have been altered over the course of time may still be
28 included in the NRHP, but they must retain integrity of location, design, setting, materials,
29 workmanship, feeling, and association in order to be considered significant according to NRHP
30 standards. The criteria for significance are contained in 36 CFR § 60.4 and include cultural
31 resources that:

- 32 (a) are associated with events that have made a significant contribution to the broad patterns
33 of our history; or
- 34 (b) are associated with the lives of persons significant in our past; or
- 35 (c) embody the distinctive characteristics of a type, period, or method of construction, or
36 that represent the work of a master, or that possess high artistic values, or that represent a
37 significant and distinguishable entity whose components may lack individual distinction; or
- 38 (d) have yielded, or may be likely to yield, information important in prehistory or history.

1 Cultural resources can also be eligible for listing in the NRHP if they meet the special
2 requirements of the Criteria Considerations in addition to meeting one or more of the criteria
3 set forth in 36 CFR § 60.4. The special requirements consist of the following:

4 (a) a religious property deriving primary significance from architectural or artistic
5 distinction or historical importance; or

6 (b) a building or structure removed from its original location, but which is significant
7 primarily for architectural value, or which is the surviving structure most importantly
8 associated with a historic person or event; or

9 (c) a birthplace or grave of a historical figure of outstanding importance if there is no
10 appropriate site or building directly associated with his or her productive life; or

11 (d) a cemetery which derives its primary significance from graves of persons of
12 transcendent importance, from age, from distinctive design features, from association with
13 historic events; or

14 (e) a reconstructed building when accurately executed in a suitable environment and
15 presented in a dignified manner as part of a restoration master plan and when no other building
16 or structure with the same association has survived; or

17 (f) a property primarily commemorative in intent if design, age, tradition, or symbolic
18 value has invested it with its own exceptional significance; or

19 (g) a property achieving significance within the past 50 years if it is of exceptional
20 importance.

21 These Criteria Considerations need only be applied to individual sites, and do not have to be
22 applied to eligible districts unless they make up the majority of the district or are the focal point
23 of the district (National Park Service [NPS] 2002:25).

24 To better define a property’s significance, the NRHP developed the concept of “areas of
25 significance”, which are general categories that help describe a property’s place in American
26 history. Areas of significance include, but are not limited to, categories such as architecture,
27 archaeology, commerce, ethnic heritage, engineering and invention, industry, the military,
28 politics/government, and social history.

29 Properties that have been altered over the course of time may still be included in the NRHP,
30 but they must retain integrity of (1) location, (2) design, (3) setting, (4) materials, (5)
31 workmanship, (6) feeling, and (7) association in order to be considered significant according
32 to NRHP standards. Further, a period of significance must be defined for each eligible property.
33 The NRHP defines the period of significance as “the length of time when a property was
34 associated with important events, activities, or persons, or attained the characteristics which
35 qualify it for National Register listing.”

36 **Treatment**

37 Treatment of any cultural resource discovered during project activities must consider a number
38 of variables, including the property’s location, setting, integrity, structure, contents, age, and

1 data potential. Where avoidance is not feasible and significant archaeological remains may be
2 affected by project activities, various measures are available to recover jeopardized specimens
3 and data. These include additional analysis of extant collections, archival/library research, oral
4 history, photo documentation, further testing and evaluation, data recovery excavation, and
5 controlled destruction. Additional data recovery may also be conducted if construction
6 monitoring or post-construction field checks reveal additional materials.

7 If a planned activity may result in the excavation of human remains, funerary objects, sacred
8 objects, or objects of cultural patrimony from MCLB Barstow lands, the MCLB Barstow or
9 CRM official must notify in writing the Tribes that are likely to be culturally affiliated with the
10 items that may be excavated. The written notice must describe the planned activity, its general
11 location, the basis upon which it was determined that the objects may be excavated, and the
12 basis for determining likely custody. Following consultation with the associated Tribes, the
13 Federal agency official must complete a written plan of action as described in 43 CFR § 10.5(e)
14 and execute the actions called for in it.

15 Generally, treatment programs for significant archaeological resources that cannot be avoided
16 include data recovery investigations. These may include mapping, surface collection, auguring,
17 excavation of shovel test pits, and excavation units, as well as mechanical excavation of
18 stratigraphic trenches. In addition, manual stripping can be used to identify and document
19 features and deposits, as well as to salvage important specimens that might otherwise be lost.

20 The following discussion presents proposed treatment for the kinds of sites that could be
21 discovered at MCLB Barstow. The Discovery Treatment Plan does not prescribe treatments or
22 mitigations as consultation takes place during the preparation of treatment plans.

23 ***Native American or Other Burial/Cemetery***

24 See discussion below on human remains (“Discovery and Treatment of Burials”) for
25 procedures to be used if human remains are encountered.

26 ***Low-Density/Low-Diversity Prehistoric Artifact Scatter or Isolated Features***

27 Archaeological deposits of this type usually offer few opportunities to address important
28 research questions. In general, low-density/low-diversity artifact scatters shall be formally
29 recorded and the site form including the site location will be sent to the information center
30 located at California State University-Fullerton. On occasion, a site containing multiple flaking
31 stations may be able to contribute manufacturing data and shall be evaluated further. Diagnostic
32 artifacts may be collected from the surface or excavated soils for future description and
33 analysis, and excavation profiles recorded to characterize the horizontal and vertical
34 distribution of site deposits and their stratigraphic setting. Features (e.g., hearths) shall be
35 excavated in their entirety as described below.

36 ***Complex Prehistoric Archaeological Deposits***

37 Although it is not assumed that each prehistoric-period complex archaeological deposit has the
38 potential to contribute equally to each research domain, a common range of treatment measures
39 can be proposed for this property type. Methods used vary in accordance with the nature of the

1 material encountered. The data potential of complex prehistoric archaeological deposits is high,
2 and efforts shall be made to retrieve data that may contribute to significant research questions.
3 At such sites a premium shall be placed on recovering data from “single component” features
4 or other concentrations of cultural materials that can be demonstrated to represent a limited
5 temporal span. Chronological indicators such as obsidian hydration analysis and radiocarbon
6 dating, among others, shall be emphasized. If human bone is present, the procedures discussed
7 below in “Discovery and Treatment of Burials” section will be followed.

8 Mechanical excavation can be used to rapidly expose stratigraphic profiles and cultural
9 features, if present, and to examine a relatively large volume of soil in an economical fashion.
10 Once exposed, features shall be excavated by hand. Both controlled and rapid-recovery
11 excavation techniques can be used to recover sufficient samples of cultural and ecofactual
12 materials for description and analysis depending on the composition and extent of the site.

13 Data recovery methods chosen shall be those most appropriate to recover important data
14 sources present at each site. For example, if small beads are found to occur within the site
15 matrix, controlled excavation units using c-inch mesh most likely will be employed to recover
16 these constituents. Conversely, if projectile points are determined to be the most significant
17 cultural constituent present within the site matrix, rapid recovery methods using ¼-inch screen
18 mesh and 20-centimeter level increments may be used, and only diagnostic and formed tools
19 collected after a statistically valid sample of debitage has been collected from excavation of
20 other units within the site. Photo documentation should be performed during any data recovery
21 efforts at all sites.

22 Controlled mechanical removal of cultural deposits can be employed at some sites where it is
23 not feasible to search for discrete cultural features using hand excavation methods. If features
24 or other significant cultural remains are encountered during mechanical stripping, excavation
25 of such features and remains shall proceed by hand in controlled or manual rapid recovery
26 units, as appropriate.

27 Following data recovery, monitoring and post-construction monitoring by an archaeological
28 monitor may be employed as a final treatment method where applicable. The archaeological
29 monitor would observe and record any hearths or other features that might be exposed and help
30 ensure that no damage occurs to intact cultural deposits. Periodic post-construction monitoring
31 may be recommended for sites that are particularly visible and subject to vandalism, or to
32 ensure that prescribed protection or stabilization measures have been adequately carried out.

33 ***Complex Historic Deposits***

34 As with complex prehistoric deposits, not all complex historic deposits have the same research
35 potential. There are certain generalized treatments that can be used to apply to all deposits,
36 however, that can be modified to accommodate the data potential of each deposit. In each case,
37 the methods used shall be designed to recover data that may contribute to research questions.
38 For instance, items may be recovered from structural features that contribute to our
39 interpretation of technological methods and their chronological development.

1 Mechanical excavations may be necessary to rapidly expose stratigraphic profiles and features.
2 Once exposed, these items shall be excavated by hand with techniques designed to recover
3 sufficient samples of cultural materials for description and analysis. It may be necessary to
4 draw stratigraphic profiles and/or plan views. In such cases, trenches shall be left open until
5 this is accomplished.

6 Data recovery methods shall be designed to recover sufficient samples of diagnostic cultural
7 material. For example, if the primary component of the site is structural, it may be more
8 expedient to use machine excavation techniques to rapidly expose the diagnostic architectural
9 items. Additional hand excavation may not be necessary for such features. Photo
10 documentation should be performed during data recovery efforts.

11 Once data recovery has been completed, additional monitoring both during and after
12 construction may be necessary as a final treatment method where applicable. Additional
13 features shall be recorded to ensure that no damage occurs to intact cultural deposits. Periodic
14 post-construction monitoring may be recommended for sites that are highly visible or subject
15 to vandalism.

16 **COLLECTIONS AND RECORDS MANAGEMENT**

17 All archaeological materials recovered during site treatment measures shall be subject to
18 processing including cleaning, detailed description, and analysis, as appropriate. The treatment
19 of human remains and associated funerary objects will be treated in accordance with procedures
20 outlined in NAGPRA (43 CFR 10) and in the “Discovery and Treatment of Burials” section of
21 the Discovery Treatment Plan. Large structural objects shall be recorded, and photo
22 documented in situ.

23 Following completion of laboratory and analytical procedures, project collections shall be
24 suitably packaged and transferred to appropriate facilities for long-term storage. Materials to
25 be curated include archaeological specimens and samples, field notes, feature and burial
26 records, maps, plans, profile drawings, photo logs, photographic negatives, consultant reports
27 of special studies, and a copy of the final technical report. These materials shall be deposited
28 at a facility that meets the standards set forth in the NPS Regulation *Curation of Federally*
29 *Owned and Administered Archaeological Collections* (36 CFR 79). Curation arrangements
30 shall be made by MCLB Barstow. Collections shall be prepared and packaged accordingly to
31 the specifications of the appropriate curation facility.

32 **SITE ASSESSMENT/TREATMENT DOCUMENTATION AND SCHEDULE**

33 Once a site has been discovered, site assessment and treatment efforts shall be documented on
34 a weekly basis by the Lead Archaeologist. Following the completion of field efforts at specific
35 locations, the Lead Archaeologist shall make recommendations to MCLB Barstow regarding
36 the resumption or initiation of construction in the vicinity. A “Notice to Proceed” shall then be
37 issued as appropriate. Draft and final report scheduling, and distribution shall be arranged in
38 consultation with MCLB Barstow.

1 DISCOVERY AND TREATMENT OF BURIALS

2 Upon discovery of human remains, work shall be halted in the immediate vicinity (10-15
3 meters) of the discovery. The CRM and the Provost Marshal Office (PMO) shall be notified
4 immediately. In consultation, the CRM and the PMO shall determine if the remains are recent
5 or of prehistoric Native American origin. If necessary, they shall call in other consultants. The
6 CRM shall also notify, by telephone and with written confirmation, the Commanding Officer.

7 If the remains are of recent origin, the PMO shall notify and consult with local law enforcement
8 authorities.

9 Should the remains prove to be Native American, SHPO and the appropriate Native American
10 tribes and interested groups shall be notified as required by NAGPRA (43 CFR 10 Section
11 3(d)). The following details the procedures relating to Native American burials in accord with
12 the provisions of NAGPRA.

13 Definitions Relating to Native American Burials

- 14 1. *Associated Funerary Objects* means objects that, as a part of the death rite or ceremony
15 of a culture, are reasonably believed to have been placed with the individual human
16 remains at the time of death or later.
- 17 2. *Cultural Affiliation* means a relationship of shared group identity that can be reasonably
18 traced historically or prehistorically between a present-day Indian tribe and an
19 identifiable earlier group.
- 20 3. *Burial Site* means the physical location of human remains.
- 21 4. *Discovery* means the identification of any human remains during archaeological or
22 construction-related excavations conducted on MCLB Barstow.
- 23 5. *Human Remains* are any physical remains of a human being.
- 24 6. *Inadvertent Discovery* refers to the accidental and unexpected finding of cultural
25 resources, especially of human remains.
- 26 7. *Interested Group* shall, for the purposes of this Integrated Cultural Resources
27 Management Plan (ICRMP), mean any non-federally recognized Native American group
28 that claims cultural affiliation with a discovery and that has represented an intent to
29 participate in the treatment and disposition of remains.
- 30 8. *Objects of Cultural Patrimony* are objects having ongoing historical, traditional, or
31 cultural importance central to a Native American group or culture itself, rather than
32 property owned by an individual Native American. Objects of cultural patrimony cannot
33 be alienated, appropriated, or conveyed by an individual regardless of whether the
34 individual is a member of the Native American group, and such objects must have been
35 considered inalienable at the time they were separated from the group.
- 36 9. *Project* refers to any specific activities that led to the discovery of the human remains.
- 37 10. *Remains* means human remains, any remains thought to be human remains, and all other
38 cultural items as defined by NAGPRA, including associated funerary objects, sacred
39 objects, and objects of cultural patrimony.

- 1 11. *Sacred Objects* are specified ceremonial objects that are needed by traditional Native
 2 American religious leaders for the practice of traditional Native American religions by
 3 their present-day adherents.
- 4 12. *Native American Monitor* shall, for the purposes of this ICRMP, mean an observer
 5 chosen by the tribe(s) to watch and/or participate in archaeological activities, particularly
 6 as they relate to the recovery of human remains.
- 7 13. *Tribe* means any tribe, band, nation, or other organized group or community of Native
 8 Americans that claims cultural affiliation to the project area and is recognized as eligible
 9 for the programs and services provided by the United States to Native Americans because
 10 of their status as Native Americans.

11 **Discovery, Treatment, and Disposition of Remains**

- 12 1. The following procedures regarding the discovery, treatment, and disposition of Native
 13 American remains shall be implemented after consultation and in accordance with the
 14 express wish of, or in conformity with, the policies and guidelines of the tribes.
- 15 2. All discovery remains shall be treated with respect and dignity in order to avoid any
 16 unnecessary disturbance, separation of human remains from their associated funerary
 17 objects, or physical modification of remains.
- 18 3. All remains discovered during the course of a project shall receive the agreed upon
 19 treatment and disposition measures set forth herein.
- 20 4. A Native American Monitor to be chosen by the tribe(s) shall be on-call during any
 21 excavations. The Native American monitor shall be consulted should human remains,
 22 associated funerary objects, sacred objects, and objects of cultural patrimony be
 23 recovered.
- 24 5. Unless otherwise agreed among MCLB Barstow, the tribe(s), and any other interested
 25 group, the treatment and disposition of human remains shall be conducted as described as
 26 follows:
- 27 a. Human remains and associated funerary objects, sacred objects, and objects of
 28 cultural patrimony discovered during a project shall be left in situ and as
 29 undisturbed as is reasonably possible to ensure their protection, pending
 30 appropriate notification and consultation as described below.
- 31 b. The Commanding Officer, SHPO, appropriate Native American
 32 groups/individuals, and Native American Heritage Commission (NAHC), will be
 33 notified of the find. MCLB Barstow has 30 days to consult with tribes and
 34 interested groups as described below. At the end of the 30 days, if the remains
 35 cannot remain in situ, they shall be removed by archaeological excavation. Such
 36 excavation shall be undertaken in accordance with the Standards of Research
 37 Performance of the Register of Professional Archaeologists and professional
 38 standards for archaeological data recovery. Such remains shall be excavated after a
 39 written plan of action regarding the remains has been prepared, approved, and
 40 signed by the appropriate Native American tribes as required by NAGPRA (43
 41 CFR§ 10.5 (e)).

- c. If the lineal descendants of the deceased Native American cannot be identified, then representatives of the tribes and interested groups shall be consulted regarding disposition of the remains. Should there be any disagreements between the wishes of tribes and those of interested groups, the wishes of the tribes take precedence.
6. Lineal descendants and/or representatives of the tribes and interested groups shall be afforded the opportunity to be present and to carry out religious ceremonies or rituals during the excavation, treatment, and disposition of the remains.
7. Prior to disposition, a qualified physical anthropologist shall make nondestructive measurements and other observations to determine the age, sex, health, and other attributes of the remains. Such measures and observations shall be conducted and documented within 60 days after excavation of the remains.
8. If the remains are to be reinterred, they shall be reinterred within 90 days of their excavation.
9. No excavated human remains shall be put on public display in any manner nor photographed except for the purpose of scientific documentation. No photographs of the human remains shall be distributed to the public or published without the written permission of the tribes and interested groups.
10. In instances where cultural affiliation cannot be determined and/or the tribes and interested groups do not state a claim to the remains, MCLB Barstow shall determine their treatment and disposition.
11. The location of the discovery shall be reported solely to the appropriate MCLB Barstow land manager(s) having immediate administrative responsibility and to representatives of the tribes and interested groups, the Tribal Chairman, President, Chairman’s Designated Representative, THPO, Tribal Monitor or other designated representative as appropriate, of the tribes and any other interested group subsequently signatory to this agreement.
12. The specific location of the discovery of remains shall be withheld from public disclosure and protected to the fullest extent allowed by law.
13. If the disposition is by reburial, the reburial shall occur in a location reasonably secure from further disturbance and the location shall be recorded and mapped on California Department of Parks and Recreation forms 523 and 523C. If the reburial is located near a known archaeological site, the record forms of that site shall be modified to clearly indicate the reburial location. Recordation will help protect the reburial location from future disturbance. MCLB Barstow shall plot and label this location on base maps as a Native American Sensitive Area.
14. Within 90 days after the disposition of the remains, MCLB Barstow shall submit a final report documenting the discovery, treatment, and disposition of those remains to the tribes and any other interested groups.

Dispute Resolution

1. MCLB Barstow shall seek out the comments of tribes or interested groups regarding the procedures set forth in this ICRMP. Should any interested group make a conflicting claim of cultural affiliation or dispute the methods of treatment or disposition of remains

- 1 as set forth herein, MCLB Barstow shall convene a meeting with the disputing parties
2 within 30 days of receiving notice of disputation.
- 3 2. The disputing parties shall attempt to reach a resolution with the assistance of the
4 MCLB Barstow CRM.
- 5 3. If a resolution cannot be reached within 90 days, the CRM shall forward all pertinent
6 documentation to the Review Committee established under NAGPRA with a request
7 for the Committee to provide their recommendations.

8 **Summary**

9 This discovery treatment plan discusses the procedures to be followed as a result of the
10 inadvertent discovery of any archaeological remains during base activities. In particular, it
11 addresses the steps to be taken if human remains are discovered. An Unanticipated Discovery
12 Response Flowchart is presented in Figure C-1.

Figure C-1 Unanticipated Discovery Response Flowchart

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Appendix D. Agreement Documents

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**UNITED STATES MARINE CORPS
MARINE AIR GROUND TASK FORCE TRAINING COMMAND
MARINE CORPS AIR GROUND COMBAT CENTER
BOX 788100
TWENTYNINE PALMS, CALIFORNIA 92278-8100
MARINE CORPS LOGISTICS BASE
BOX 110115
BARSTOW, CALIFORNIA 92311-0115**

MCLB
4000
B440

MAGTFTC, MCAGCC
5000
4E

17 NOV 2014

**MEMORANDUM OF UNDERSTANDING
BETWEEN
THE MARINE AIR GROUND TASK FORCE TRAINING COMMAND
MARINE COPRS AIR GROUND COMBAT CENTER
TWENTYNINE PALMS, CALIFORNIA
AND
MARINE CORPS LOGISTICS BASE
BARSTOW, CALIFORNIA**

Subj: MEMORANDUM OF UNDERSTANDING IN SUPPORT OF CURATORIAL SERVICES

1. This is a Memorandum of Understanding (MOU) between the Marine Air Ground Task Force Training Command, Marine Corps Air Ground Combat Center, hereinafter referred to as "MAGTFTC, MCAGCC" and Marine Corps Logistics Base, Barstow hereinafter referred to as "MCLB, Barstow" in support of curatorial services. When referred to collectively, MAGTFTC, MCAGCC and MCLB, Barstow are referred to as the "Parties".

2. Background. MCLB, Barstow has the responsibility under Federal Law to preserve for future use certain collections of archaeological artifacts, specimens and associated records, herein called "Collections". To ensure the Collections are suitably managed and preserved for the public good, MCLB, Barstow is desirous of obtaining curatorial services from MAGTFTC, MCAGCC. MAGTFTC, MCAGCC recognizes the benefits that will accrue to the Collections, as well as the public and scientific interests by housing and maintaining the Collections for study and other educational purposes and is desirous of obtaining, housing, and maintaining the Collections.

3. Purpose. This MOU establishes responsibilities to preserve, obtain, house, and maintain certain collections of archeological artifacts, specimens, and associated records.

4. Understanding of the Parties

a. MAGTFTC, MCAGCC will:

- (1) Provide professional care and management of the Collections.
- (2) Perform all work necessary to protect the Collections in accordance with regulation 36 Code of Federal Regulations part 79 for the curation of federally-owned and administered archeological Collections.
- (3) Assign as the Curator, a Collections Manager and Conservator responsible for the work under this MOU who are qualified museum professionals and whose expertise is appropriate to the nature and content of the Collections.

Subj: MEMORANDUM OF UNDERSTANDING IN SUPPORT OF CURATORIAL SERVICES

(4) Provide and maintain a repository facility having the requisite equipment, space, and adequate safeguards for the physical security and controlled environment of the Collections and any associated records in MAGTFTC, MCAGCC's possession.

(5) Not in any way adversely alter or deface any of the Collections except as may be absolutely necessary in the course of stabilization, conservation, scientific study, analysis, and research. Any activity that will involve the intentional destruction of any of the Collections must be approved in advance and in writing by MCLB, Barstow.

(6) Annually inspect the Collections and perform only those conservation treatments as are absolutely necessary to ensure the physical stability and integrity of the Collections, and report the results of the inventories, inspections, and treatments to MCLB, Barstow.

(7) Within five days of discovery, report all instances of and circumstances surrounding loss of, deterioration and damage to, or destruction of the Collections to MCLB, Barstow and those actions taken to correct any deficiencies in the Curation Center or operating procedures that may have contributed to the loss, deterioration, damage, or destruction.

(8) Not pledge, assign, repatriate, transfer, exchange, give, sublet, discard, or part with possessions of any of the Collections in any manner to any third party either directly or in-directly without the prior written permission of MCLB, Barstow.

(9) Return any deposited items to MCLB, Barstow upon request, at MCLB Barstow's expense.

b. MCLB, Barstow will:

(1) Deliver or cause to be delivered, at MCLB, Barstow's expense, the Collections to MAGTFTC, MCAGCC.

(2) Submit Collections in accordance with the MAGTFTC, MCAGCC Instructions for Submission of Collections. Any deviation by MCLB, Barstow from the MAGTFTC, MCAGCC Instructions for Submission of Collections must be negotiated with MAGTFTC, MCAGCC in advance, on a case by case basis.

(3) Assign as MCLB, Barstow's representative having full authority with regard to this MOU, MCLB, Barstow's Cultural Resource Program Manager or a designee who meets the pertinent professional qualifications.

(4) Review and approve or deny requests for consumptively using the Collections (or a part thereof).

5. Personnel. Each Party is responsible for all costs of its personnel, including pay and benefits, support, and travel. Each party is responsible for supervision and management of its personnel.

6. General Provisions

a. Points of Contact (POC). The following POCs will be used by the Parties to communicate in the implementation of this MOU. Each Party may change its POC upon reasonable notice to the other Party.

Subj: MEMORANDUM OF UNDERSTANDING IN SUPPORT OF CURATORIAL SERVICES

(1) MAGTFTC, MCAGCC

Primary: Cultural Resources Specialist/Collections Manager
COM: (760) 830-7650/1196

Alternate: Archeologist
COM: (760) 830-7641

(2) MCLB, Barstow

Primary: Ms. Stephanie White
Cultural Resource Program Manager
COM: (760) 577-6111
Email: Stephanie.White@usmc.mil

Alternate: Mr. Jon Aunger
Environmental Operations Officer
COM: (760) 577-6424
Email: Jonathan.Aunger@usmc.mil

b. Correspondence. All correspondence to be sent and notices to be given pursuant to the MOU will be addressed to or as may from time to time otherwise be directed by the Parties:

(1) MAGTFTC, MCAGCC

DIRECTOR
ATTN: AGREEMENTS PROGRAM MANAGER
BUSINESS PERFORMANCE OFFICE
BOX 788350
TWENTYNINE PALMS, CA 92278-8350

(2) MCLB, Barstow

SUPPORT AGREEMENTS PROGRAM MANAGER
BUSINESS PERFORMANCE OFFICE
BOX 110115
BARSTOW, CA 92311-0115

c. Funds and Manpower. This MOU does not document nor provide for the exchange of funds or manpower between the Parties nor does it make any commitment of funds or resources.

d. Modification of the MOU

(1) This MOU may only be modified by the written agreement of the Parties, duly signed by their authorized representatives.

(2) Written requests for modification will be forwarded by one Party to the other not less than 30 days prior to the desired effective date of such modification.

(3) This MOU will be reviewed annually on or around the anniversary of its effective date, and triennially in its entirety.

Subj: MEMORANDUM OF UNDERSTANDING IN SUPPORT OF CURATORIAL SERVICES

e. Disputes. Any disputes relating to this MOU will, subject to any applicable law, Executive Order, directive, or instruction, be resolved by consultation between the Parties or in accordance with the Department of Defense Instruction 4000.19 of April 25, 2013.

f. Termination of Understanding. This MOU may be cancelled at any time by mutual consent of the Parties concerned. The MOU may also be terminated by either Party upon giving 90 days written notice to the other Party. In the case of mobilization or other emergency, the MOU may be terminated immediately upon written notice by either Party, and it will remain in force during mobilization or other emergency only within the Parties' capabilities.

g. Transferability. This MOU is not transferable except with the written consent of the Parties.

h. Entire Understanding. It is expressly understood and agreed that this MOU embodies the entire understanding between the Parties regarding the MOU's subject matter.

i. Effective Date. This MOU takes effect beginning on the day after the last Party signs.

j. Expiration Date. This MOU expires in nine years.

APPROVED

For MCLB, Barstow

M. L. SCALISE
Commanding Officer

20141114
Date

For MAGTF/TC, MCAGCC

J. B. HANLON
Chief of Staff

20141103
Date

Appendix E. SHPO and THPO Consultation Concurrence

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**DEPARTMENT OF PARKS AND RECREATION
OFFICE OF HISTORIC PRESERVATION**

Lisa Ann L. Mangat, Director

Julianne Polanco, State Historic Preservation Officer

1725 23rd Street, Suite 100, Sacramento, CA 95816-7100

Telephone: (916) 445-7000 FAX: (916) 445-7053

calshpo.ohp@parks.ca.gov www.ohp.parks.ca.gov

August 29, 2018

Reply In Reference To: USMC_2018_0711_001

Mr. J. P. Auger
Director, Facilities Department
Marine Corps Logistics Base
Box 110100
Barstow, CA 92311-0100

RE: Final Technical Synthesis Report – Enhancement of Training Ranges and Areas
at USMC Logistics Base, Barstow

Dear Mr. Auger:

In a letter dated July 02, 2018, the U. S. Marine Corps (USMC) initiated consultation with the State Historic Preservation Officer (SHPO) on the above-cited undertaking, in accordance with Section 106 of the *National Historic Preservation Act*, as amended. The USMC proposed to enhance and update operational capabilities of approximately 1,306 acres of existing training ranges and areas, at the USMC Logistics Base Barstow, to accommodate components of regional Marine Air-Ground Task Force training activities.

The SHPO initially responded in a letter dated August 17, 2018 requesting information on the following: (1) the status of CA-SBR-11840 in regards to its eligibility for listing on the National Register of Historic Places (NRHP), and (2) tribal consultation status with the San Manuel Band of Mission Indians (SMBMI). Initially the USMC had determined that the site was ineligible under Criterion D. The USMC stated that the SMBMI concurred with that determination, but that the SMBMI questioned whether the site also should have been evaluated under Criteria A, B, and C. The USMC conducted an archaeological evaluation of the site on November 16, 2017. Based on that evaluation and the subsequent report, the USMC has determined that CA-SBR-11840 is ineligible for listing on the NRHP under any of the four criterion. During a telephone conversation between the USMC and the SHPO on August 29, 2018, the USMC clarified the eligibility status of CA-SBR-11840, stated that SMBMI had no further comments on USMC's eligibility determination for the site, and confirmed that the tribal consultation with the SMBMI was concluded in accordance with 36 CFR 800.4.

Subsequently, the SHPO offers the following amended comments:

- The SHPO has no objections to identification and delineation of the APE, pursuant to 36 CFR Parts 800.4(a)(1) and 800.16(d);
- USMC has proposed to treat as eligible *for the purposes of Section 106* the following sites: CA-SBR-73, CA-SBR-8319, and CA-SBR-29325. The SHPO does not object.
- The USMC has determined that CA-SBR-11840 is not eligible for listing on the NRHP under any of the four criterion. The SHPO concurs.
- USMC has determined the 40 archaeological sites (which includes CA-SBR-11840) and 116 isolated artifacts (identified in the USMC's letter and report) are not eligible for listing on the NRHP. The SHPO concurs.
- The SHPO agrees that the proposed undertaking could have an effect on CA-SBR-73, CA-SBR-8319, and CA-SBR-29325, but that effect would not be adverse subject to the implementation of the buffer zones as described,
- The SHPO acknowledges that the USMC has concluded the tribal consultation process in accordance with 36 CFR 800.4; and
- The SHPO does not object to your finding of No Adverse Effect to Historic Properties and agrees that it is appropriate for this proposed undertaking, as described above.

Be advised that under certain circumstances, such as an unanticipated discovery or a change in project description, the USMC may have additional future responsibilities for this undertaking under 36 CFR Part 800. Should cultural artifacts be encountered during ground disturbing activities, please halt all work until a qualified archaeologist can be consulted on the nature and significance of such artifacts.

If there are any questions or concerns, please contact Ed Carroll at (916) 445-7006 or via e-mail at Ed.Carroll@parks.ca.gov.

Sincerely,

Julianne Polanco
State Historic Preservation Officer